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AI ETHICS AUDITING

**RISK IMPACT ASSESSMENT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE PUBLIC
ADMINISTRATION OF JUSTICE**

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“Computers are like Old Testament Gods; lots of rules and no mercy.”

Joseph Campbell

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Introduction

This thesis emerges as a response to the increasing adoption of Artificial Intelligence systems in the domain of justice, as well as the ethical challenges that these systems entail. If left unchecked, these systems can generate strikingly unfair decisions, and real-world examples of such negative impacts are plentiful.

Between 2013 and 2019, an automated decision system deployed by the Dutch Tax and Customs Administration wrongly flagged around 26,000 innocent parents as child benefit fraudsters in the infamous *Toeslagenaffaire* ('child benefit scandal'), causing them significant financial and psychological distress. The overwhelming majority of affected parties held dual citizenship, which the system perplexingly regarded as a risk factor. In 2016, the investigative journalism organization ProPublica's reported on racial bias in incarceration decisions made by the recidivism risk assessment software COMPAS ('Correctional Offender Management Profiling for Alternative Sanctions'). These scandals brought to light concerns about disparate impacts and unacceptable risks embedded in systems that had perhaps been adopted too hastily.

While the introduction of AI in the public administration of justice can bring about increased judicial efficiency, processing speed and access, it can also feature errors that engender grave repercussions to human life and freedom, and whose rationale is hidden in an inscrutable *black box*. Therefore, an ex-ante risk assessment for AI systems is called for.

Algorithmic Impact Assessments (AIA) are policy mechanisms aimed at documenting the development and impact of an algorithmic system (Moss, Watkins, Metcalf, & Elish, 2020) and the respect of specific ethical principles. AIAs have the goal of mitigating and preventing negative impacts of AI systems by recognizing and addressing them before implementation (Ada Lovelace Institute, AI Now Institute and Open Government Partnership, 2021), to maximise the benefits of AI systems (High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, 2019b).

Impact assessments involve balancing acts between harms, benefits and risks, to evaluate the appropriateness of the deployment of an algorithmic system in a specific context (Ada Lovelace Institute, AI Now Institute and Open Government Partnership, 2021). The definition of what constitutes the 'impacts' and 'harms' that are assessed is not straightforward and can usher in assumptions based on subjective

values and personal biases. The process of identifying and operationalizing impacts is not neutral to power relations among actors and communities (Ada Lovelace Institute, AI Now Institute and Open Government Partnership, 2021), and it becomes a domain of contestation (Moss et al., 2020). It is a discursive process through which priorities and essential values are set, resulting in the implicit judgment of what impacts are more worthy of assessment, which societal values should weigh more in a balancing act, and what impacts are more or less tolerable.

For this reason, the European Commission’s High Level Expert Group on AI recommends proactive communication with developers, deployers, end-users, and the general public throughout the AI system’s life cycle (High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, 2019b). The aim is allowing realistic expectation setting about the capabilities and limitations of AI systems, as well as how trustworthiness requirements are implemented. (High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, 2019b) However, AIAs rarely engage substantively all stakeholders, in particular leaving behind impacted communities (Ada Lovelace Institute, AI Now Institute and Open Government Partnership, 2021). Their use for internal self-assessment, without a concrete effort to fostering the participation of the most vulnerable stakeholders, risks resulting in a mere ‘ethics wash’ (Morley, Elhalal, et al., 2021) of superficial self-regulation (Moss et al., 2020). It is a missed opportunity for an increased legitimacy (Moss et al., 2020) and accountability (Ada Lovelace Institute, AI Now Institute and Open Government Partnership, 2021) of the AIA process, while also falling short of establishing an ecosystem of trust towards these technologies, where noxious applications are weeded out and shared values are protected.

This thesis aims at providing an informative overview on the ethical considerations connected to AI, especially in terms of human autonomy and fairness, and it presents a novel AIA framework. This risk assessment tool, first developed in 2021 (Cavosi, 2021), is currently being developed by the ethical innovation consulting firm *ReD Open*, a participated spin-off of University of Milano-Bicocca, in partnership with a hybrid research team from *MUDI Lab* at University of Milano-Bicocca. As a research intern at *ReD Open* and member of *MUDI Lab*, I contributed to the translation, expansion, and enhancement of this AIA.

In Chapter 1, I will first discuss the definition and main characteristics of Artificial Intelligence, including the foundational concepts of algorithms, Big Data and Machine Learning. I will then focus on Automated Decision-Making systems, drawing attention to the phenomena of *technological dominance* and *automating injustice*, both having problematic implications for fairness and human autonomy.

Chapter 2 is dedicated to the emerging field of AI ethics, a form of applied ethics that investigates the moral dilemmas and trade-offs that can arise when AI is developed and deployed. I will provide an overview of the plurality of values that characterize AI ethics, in particular those discussed by the High-Level Expert

Group on Artificial Intelligence (2019b) in their *Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI*. The chapter will close with a discussion on bridging the gap between principles and practice in this field.

Chapter 3 is dedicated to the current governance frameworks around AI, discussing the role of soft and hard regulation in the fast-paced environment of Artificial Intelligence. In particular, I will explain the concept of *risk-based approach* and its increasing popularity for AI regulation. I will introduce the reader to the global competition in regulating AI, to then analyze the current European regulatory framework, in particular the General Data Protection Regulation and the Draft AI regulation. Industry, too, can play a role in AI governance: I will discuss both the opportunities and pitfalls of industry self-regulation, including the risk of *ethics-washing*.

Chapter 4 concerns the application of automated decision-making systems in algorithmic governance, predictive justice, and predictive policing. After providing comprehensive definitions of each these terms, I will contextualize them by discussing two case studies of what I defined *algorithmic (in)justice*: the case of the recidivism risk assessment system COMPAS in the USA, and the welfare fraud risk assessment SyRI, that was deployed in the Netherlands and led to the *Toeslagenaffaire*.

Chapter 5 discusses the relevance of auditing for AI systems, providing information over the processes, targets and types of assessment. In line with the ethical focus on the thesis, I dedicated a section to the assessment procedure known as *Human Rights, Ethical and Social Impact Assessment (HRESIA)* and I then presented some challenges and limitations of AI audits. This final chapter ends with a description of my research internship at ReD Open, whose objective is the development of an AI auditing checklist together with a multidisciplinary team. In Annex I, a draft of the AI audit checklist is available in full.

Chapter 1

Artificial Intelligence: the automation of human judgment?

The expression *Artificial Intelligence* can boast well over half a century of history, having its first occurrence at the fateful *Dartmouth Summer Research Project on Artificial Intelligence* held in 1956 at Dartmouth College, New Hampshire, United States. More than sixty years after, academics, professionals and regulators alike are still searching for a definition of AI that is both uncontroversial and comprehensive in its scope. This is a pressing issue in light of the international efforts to regulate Artificial Intelligence. Since the European Commission issued its regulation proposal in April 2021, there has been a heated debate over the overarching definition presented.¹

In this chapter, I will go over the history of Artificial Intelligence, briefly explaining the three foundational concepts of *Algorithm*, *Big Data* and *Machine Learning*. All three are enabling factors for Artificial Intelligence: in very simple terms, algorithms define the *rules of the game* (or even the *recipe* to be followed); Big data provides the raw material from which to infer new patterns, rules and associations; Machine learning is the process of autonomous self-adaption that allows the system to learn from experience.

Among the possible applications of AI, I will focus on Automated Decision Making (ADM) systems due to their increasing implementation in the public administration of justice, welfare and beyond (Special Rapporteur on Extreme Poverty and Human Rights Philip Alston, 2019a). Unlike traditional systems, which make decisions based on the rules and knowledge base supplied by the programmers, ADM systems employ Machine Learning techniques to learn from experience, developing their own (often inscrutable) rules to infer knowledge. What is most controversial

¹“‘Artificial intelligence system’ (AI system) means software that is developed with one or more of the techniques and approaches listed in Annex I and can, for a given set of human-defined objectives, generate outputs such as content, predictions, recommendations, or decisions influencing the environments they interact with” (European Commission, 2021b)

about ADM systems is their capacity to *automate human judgment*, substituting the human factor in repetitive and well-structured tasks, allowing humans to focus on more complex, and more valued, work (Nishant, Kennedy, & Corbett, 2020). As ADMs are increasingly employed for tasks of higher complexity (Sutton, Arnold, & Holt, 2018), their role supposedly becomes that of advisors to human decision-makers who retain full autonomy and oversight over the process; or at least, this is auspicated. The phenomena of *technological dominance* and *automation bias* tell another story. The human decision-maker may pay undue deference to the AI system, perhaps persuaded by its appearance of authoritative objectivity - also termed *algority* (Floridi & Cabitza, 2021) - or, more simply, they might be using algorithms as heuristics, choosing the way of least cognitive effort and therefore developing complacency and inattentiveness towards the output provided by the AI system, validating it every time. The *automation of human judgment* may therefore be happening in two ways: on the one hand, human judgment is simulated by AI systems replacing human agents in simple and predictable tasks; on the other hand, human judgment is swayed by the AI output through cognitive biases and heuristics.

1.1 Winters and Springs of AI

Artificial Intelligence as a scientific subject has roots dating back to the 1940s, when the first modern computers were invented (Gillies & Gillies, 2022; Zuiderveen Borgesius et al., 2018). As fiction draws from reality to explore uncharted territories, the visionary Isaac Asimov published the short story *Runaround* (1942) where he first developed his famous *Three Laws of Robotics*. According to the first law, robots must not harm human beings; the second law prescribes obedience to the commands of humans (lest they contradict the First Law); according to the third law, robots must protect their own existence, as long as this does not contradict the first and the second law. In the story, the robot *SPD-13* (or ‘Speedy’) finds itself in an inescapable feedback loop after finding it impossible to respect both the Second and Third Law at once, since the high expenses incurred in its development led the programmers to strengthen Speedy’s self-preservation requirement.

In that decade, Norber Wiener defined the influential discipline of *cybernetics* in his book *Cybernetics: Or Control and Communication in the Animal and the Machine* (1948). Relevantly for the development of Artificial Intelligence, cybernetics was concerned with the parallels between the brain and *computing machines*. Already in the 1950s, researchers had turned to the exciting project of simulating human intelligence through computers, starting from Alan Turing’s seminal work *Computing Machinery and Intelligence* (1950) where he described the concept of intelligent machines and devised a way to test their intelligence based on their capability to respond in a human-like manner, and therefore deceive humans on their

nature in an imitation game: the *Turing test*. Other fields that influenced AI (and were eventually influenced by it) are engineering, biology, experimental psychology, communication theory, game theory, mathematics and statistics, logic and philosophy, and linguistics (Buchanan, 2005).

However, it is in 1956, with the previously mentioned *Dartmouth Summer Research Project on Artificial Intelligence*, that the term *Artificial Intelligence* is first used, as coined by John McCarthy 1955. In terms of disciplinary focus, while cybernetics was mostly preoccupied with analog devices, Dartmouth AI welcomed symbolic systems (Trzesicki, 2020). The multidisciplinary participants to the Dartmouth Conference displayed great optimism, believing that the development of a machine displaying intelligence equal to that of a human was imminent (i.e., happening within a generation) (Coeckelbergh, 2020). Such enthusiasm was echoed by the governments of the United States, United Kingdom, and Japan, that started funding research on intelligent machines (Radu, 2021). The *First Spring* of AI was in bloom. Indeed, the history of AI has been portrayed as a dynamic cycle of hype and skepticism, respectively dubbed *spring* and *winter* (Y. Shin, 2019). When the moon-shot promises of the First Spring failed to materialize, the chilling criticism precipitated the first AI Winter, which restricted public funding and research activities in this sector. The hype of the Dartmouth Conference confronted itself with the limitations of early processors and memory, as well as the awkwardness of the first operating languages and systems: as a consequence, the range of early AI application was limited (Buchanan, 2005). Hubert Dreyfus' 1968 book *What Computers Can't Do: A Critique of Artificial Reason* was particularly scathing in its criticism. For example, Dreyfus was skeptical that computers would ever be able to play chess skillfully, claiming that : "further significant progress ... in Artificial Intelligence is extremely unlikely." (Dreyfus 1968, p. 197)

Due to the lack of governmental funding in academia, it was companies that stepped in to further the research and innovation in the faltering AI field (Radu, 2021). The innovation that would bring in a new AI Spring was the development of *expert systems*, which can be defined as "collections of rules which assume that human intelligence can be formalized and reconstructed in a top-down approach as a series of *if-then* statements." (Haenlein & Kaplan, 2019) The success of Expert System was based on the translation into code of the knowledge of experts in specific fields, automating their decision-making processes (Gillies & Gillies, 2022). The first example of expert system was *DENDRAL*, whose development started in 1965. Given the atomic composition and mass spectrogram of a compound, *DENDRAL* was capable of inferring its molecular structure. Another successful example of expert system was *MYCIN*, specialized in the diagnosis of blood infections. Its knowledge base consisted of over 400 *if-then* rules. MYCIN was shown to outperform human doctors in 1979, when its performance was compared with that of nine

Figure 1.1: Garry kasparov vs. IBM Deep Blue, May 11 1997. Credits to Stan Honda/AFP/Getty Images

experts. While expert systems can achieve impressive results in domains that lend themselves well to formalization, they score badly in more ambiguous areas, such as image recognition. To perform adequately in less formalized activities, a system must be able to accurately interpret external input, learn from it, and apply these learning while constantly and flexibly adapting itself to them to use such learnings to fulfill specified goals and tasks through flexible adaptation (Haenlein & Kaplan, 2019). Furthermore, programming expert systems was costly and time-consuming as it required interviewing experts. This effort did not always pay off: in certain circumstances, experts cannot recollect the exact principles underpinning their own decision-making process, performing tasks almost instinctively over time. In sum, the systems' logical principles did not always correspond to real-world needs and situations. (Zuiderveen Borgesius et al., 2018) The limitations of Expert Systems preannounced a new AI winter from the late '80s, that ended with a sequence of milestones in the AI field. On May 11, 1997, the best chess player at the time competed in a televised chess tournament in New York. It was an exceptional confrontation, starring the chess Grandmaster Garry Kasparov and its AI opponent, IBM's expert system Deep Blue (See Figure 5.7). The match was brought to a close by Kasparov's capitulation. Deep Blue was specialized on the sole objective of winning chess games and was capable of evaluating 200 million of moves per second.

The opportunity to evade the onerous programming process underlying expert systems arose with the rediscovery of a statistical approach to learning that was

Figure 1.2: Number of AI research publications per country. *OECD.AI (2022)*, visualisations powered by JSI using data from MAG, version of 31/12/2021, accessed on 20/8/2022, www.oecd.ai

first introduced in the 1940s by Donald Hebb, a Canadian psychologist. In *Hebbian Learning*, artificial neural networks simulate the processes of neurons in the human brain (Hebb, 1949). However, it was evident that the computational capacity of computers at the time was insufficient to withstand this workload (Haenlein & Kaplan, 2019). It took until 2015 for artificial neural networks to make their comeback. AlphaGo, a software built by Google, was able to defeat the world champion in the board game Go, which is regarded to be much more complicated than chess, in 2015. Just like Dreyfus doubted computers would ever beat humans in chess playing, it was assumed that computers would never be able to defeat humans in this game. Deep Learning, a specific form of artificial neural network, was behind AlphaGo's exceptional performance. Together with artificial neural network, Deep Learning is now the basis for the majority of AI applications (Haenlein & Kaplan, 2019). AI has seen tremendous success in both academia and industry in recent years. A solid interdisciplinary foundation has been established for AI research, which has moved from its original core of informatics, mathematics and logic to welcome new insights from a variety of other fields, ranging from statistics and economics, to psychology and neuroscience, to philosophy and law, and so on (Sartor & Lagioia, 2020). The United States, China, and the European Union have led the world in AI publication growth during the previous two decades, as shown in Figure 5.3. (OECD, 2021a) Moreover, AI applications are increasingly integrating into our daily lives and work in a seamless way (Sartor & Lagioia, 2020).

What drove this exponential acceleration in research and innovation? At least two enabling factors for AI characterize the current socio-economic and technical

environment. One is the substantial advancements in machine learning, that have resulted from a massive increase in processing power, together with the transformational power of big data for training (Calo, 2017). The second factor is the rise of the regulation of intelligent systems as a major policy issue, in light of the manifold benefits and threats of AI. This has led numerous countries to publish their own AI strategies, aiming to seize the potential of AI as a driver for development and prosperity, promoting higher education in this field to both educate and attract from abroad future promising researchers (OECD, 2019d). Examples of public investments in research and innovation for AI include the creation of national AI research institutes, the promotion of AI investments through specific policies and incentives, and the acquisition of AI systems for the public sector (OECD, 2021a). Businesses, technical organizations, academia and civil society are also taking action, in concert with international organizations such as the G7, G20, OECD, the European Commission and the United Nations (OECD, 2019d). It is important to ensure that the present AI spring does not turn out to be a vacuous AI hype, where brittle hopes are dashed facing the limitations of boisterous claims and evidence of real-world harm. The current rhetoric around Artificial Intelligence promises to reshape economies by generating productivity gains, enhancing efficiency and reducing costs, ultimately contributing to the improvement of people's lives better and more effective policymaking through AI-informed predictions. Conversely, AI also fuels ethical challenges concerning the trustworthiness of AI systems, such as the risk of exacerbating inequalities and harming minorities through the reinforcement of biases in automated decision-making. (OECD, 2019b)

1.2 Defining *Artificial Intelligence*

The lack of a stable, consensual definition of artificial intelligence hinders efforts to establish a suitable policy framework (Calo, 2017). The first definition provided by McCarthy at the Dartmouth Conference read: “The study is to proceed on the basis of the conjecture that every aspect of learning or any other feature of intelligence can in principle be so precisely described that a machine can be made to simulate it. An attempt will be made to find how to make machines use language, form abstractions and concepts, solve kinds of problems now reserved for humans, and improve themselves.” (McCarthy et al., 1955) More concise contemporary understandings of AI are “non-symbolic machine learning techniques” or “the science of getting computers to act without being explicitly programmed” (A. Kaminski et al., 2020), or even a “set of techniques aimed at approximating some aspect of human or animal cognition using machines.” (Calo, 2017) AI may be described broadly as technology that automatically discovers patterns in data and makes predictions based on them. It is an inferential analytic approach that discovers correlations within datasets to

identify informative patterns and delineate a specific course of action (Daly et al., 2019).

This lack of consensus displays how Artificial Intelligence is better understood as an umbrella term (Calo, 2017) or *suitcase word* (Trzesicki, 2020). It comprises several different techniques and can refer at the same time to “the device, the machine, and the theory of how this device works”, but also to a whole research field aiming at replicating human intelligence in machines (*ibid.*). This view is reinforced by the European Economic and Social Committee: “there is no single accepted and rigid definition of AI. AI is a catch-all term for a large number of sub(fields) such as: cognitive computing (algorithms that reasons and understand at a higher (more human) level), machine-learning (algorithms that can teach themselves tasks), augmented intelligence (cooperation between human and machine) and AI robotics (AI embedded in robots)” (European Economic and Social Committee, 2017)

Deep learning methodologies, which entail many-layered structures to extract features from massive data sets, are referred to in technical definitions of AI, as are other techniques to similar effect (Calo, 2017). The desired defining feature might be automation, or the ability of AI systems to perform by themselves operations that formerly needed human operators, without requiring human intervention (Yeung, 2019). Another candidate feature is self-learning, “their capability to learn and change over time, dynamically setting their own sub-goals, and their ability to adapt to local conditions via external sensor information or updated input data.” (*ibid.*)

A further layer of difficulty in defining AI is the *AI effect* (McCorduck & Cfe, 2004), which states that the concept of AI evolves as technology progresses (Fjeld, Achten, Hilligoss, Nagy, & Srikumar, 2020). AI-powered tasks that are already part of our daily lives, such as sorting genuine from *junk* e-mail, are dismissed as not requiring “real” intelligence. The target of AI is constantly moving (Medaglia, Gil-Garcia, & Pardo, 2021), since “intelligence is whatever machines haven’t done yet” (Hofstadter, 1980).

Any definition of AI needs to include the elusive concept of intelligence, and this represents a critical point of disagreement among scholars. Some researchers prefer focus instead on rationality, which is not the sole component of intelligence, but is a significant one. Rationality refers to the capacity to determine the optimal course of action to attain a certain objective, given predefined criteria to be optimized and a specific amount of resources (High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, 2019a). To evade the concept of intelligence, Floridi (2021) claimed that, rather than expressing intelligence, AI represents the divorce between intelligence and agency.

The intelligence currently displayed by AI is defined as *Narrow*: it is hyper-specialized on specific tasks. The aforementioned *Deep Blue* and *AlphaGo*, while displaying superhuman capacities in strategic thinking, would not be able to tell apart a chihuahua from a blueberry muffin, or even play tic-tac-toe. Narrow AI

represents the totality of Artificial Intelligence as of today. Artificial General Intelligence (AGI), on the other hand, would display the whole range of human intellectual capacities (including “cognitive, emotional, and social intelligence” (Haenlein & Kaplan, 2019)), being able to *generalize* its base knowledge in order to perform each task it is presented with, irrespective of the scope of its initial programming. The almost Messianic coming of AGI has been predicted at different points from the 1950s until today, with experts affirming each time that only few years were left before the achievement of AGI. This hope is tied with the idea of *technological singularity*, that is, the hope or fear that AI will one day surpass human intelligence and lead to a planetary *intelligence explosion* that would radically change our life (for the better or for the worse). A recent phenomenon is the increased private and public funding allocated to research centers that adhere to the philosophy of *Longtermism* (Greaves & MacAskill, 2019), whose concern with AI safety regards, very shortly put, avoiding the hypothetical rise of an almighty AI system that would one day endanger the human race. For the purpose of this thesis, I will not delve into the topic of AGI nor entertain the increasingly influential theories of Longtermism, which are “at best distracting and at worst irresponsible” (Floridi, 2022), choosing instead to prioritize the real-world harm that narrow AI is causing today.

The definition of AI that I will endorse is that proposed within the European Commission’s *Communication on AI*.

“Artificial intelligence (AI) refers to systems that display intelligent behaviour by analysing their environment and taking actions – with some degree of autonomy – to achieve specific goals. AI-based systems can be purely software-based, acting in the virtual world (e.g. voice assistants, image analysis software, search engines, speech and face recognition systems) or AI can be embedded in hardware devices (e.g. advanced robots, autonomous cars, drones or Internet of Things applications).”

High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (2019a)

To better understand the meaning and functioning of Artificial Intelligence, it is useful to explore its related and enabling concepts: mainly, algorithms, Big Data, and Machine Learning.

1.2.1 Algorithm, Big Data, and Machine Learning

Just like Artificial Intelligence, *algorithm*, too, is a contested concept (Tsamados et al., 2022). Not all algorithms involve AI, but all AI requires one or several algorithms to perform its various functions, to the point where it can be seen as a single, complex algorithm (Sartor & Lagioia, 2020). Despite their nature as a mathematical construct, references to algorithms in the public discourse typically address specific

implementations, especially in the field of social media. *The algorithm* is the invisible hand that made your tabby cat go viral on *TikTok*; it is the silent deliberator that decided that a *tweet* encouraging readers to forgo vaccines and turn to hibiscus tea instead, was better off removed for the sake of community regulations (and well-being). It is the judgmental agent that finds and removes from Instagram any trace of *female-presenting* nipples.

In its simplest form, algorithm can be defined as a “set of rules that precisely define a sequence of operations.” (Stone, 1971) This implies that your grandma’s treasured casserole recipe is, too, an algorithm: it just requires to be written down (in programming code) and the availability of the right input (data, or in this case, ingredients) to perform various predetermined steps. But a key characteristic of algorithms underlying the recent developments in AI is their autonomy: an algorithm is “any process that can be carried out automatically” (Chabert, Barbin, Borowczyk, Guillemot, & Michel-Pajus, 1999). The algorithmic recipe of your grandma’s casserole, given available ingredients, would be a “machine-executable software program” (Sartor & Lagioia, 2020) that results in a piping hot stew without any human input besides its earlier programming.

What makes algorithms powerful, besides their autonomy, is their scalability (Levy, Chasalow, & Riley, 2021). Algorithms influence decision-making on a large scale, automating decision processes over time and across different contexts, performing time-consuming tasks in mere seconds. This implies that choices that were first made by humans, are being delegated to algorithms (or *Automated Decision-Making (ADM) systems*). This has obvious ethical implications, threatening for example human autonomy as well as societal well-being. (B. D. Mittelstadt, Allo, Taddeo, Wachter, & Floridi, 2016)

The technical foundation of the algorithms that today shape our lives in unpredictable ways is *Machine Learning*. Its centrality is such that algorithms can also be described as “technologies that rely on machine learning techniques” to inform specific actions. (Levy et al., 2021) Machine learning “relies on training algorithms to learn a pattern between inputs and outputs of interest”; however, both the training algorithm and the final learned model are algorithms (*ibid.*). The training algorithm works by outlining a procedure for drawing inferences from data, while the final learned model receives the input data, applies to it the formula derived by the training algorithm, and produces its output (*ibid.*).

In Machine Learning, programmers set a first set of parameters and define the main goal that the system aims at optimizing (Yeung, 2019). This is similar to the *recipe*-type of algorithm that I presented above. What sets Machine Learning apart is its capacity to evolve with use, constantly redefining its parameters and calibrating its actions to reach its overarching goal. Through Machine Learning, a system can “make independent decisions that choose between alternatives in ways that are not

pre-programmed in advance, and to do so without any human intervention.” (Yeung, 2019) This learning can happen under various degrees of human supervision.

In supervised learning, that is the most widespread approach at the moment, the model is taught through inputs that are labelled by *data workers*, who are often precarious workers located in poorer countries (K. Crawford, 2021). This labelled training set teaches the system to recognize the correct answers to its task (Sartor & Lagioia, 2020). Reinforcement learning, too, is based on training by examples, but in this case the system learns through the rewards and penalties that arise when the system performs a correct or wrong action. As the system is programmed to maximize its score, it constructs its own strategies to avoid penalties and gain rewards, therefore increasing its accuracy (Sartor & Lagioia, 2020). This can lead to unexpected results: a telling example is that of a robot that is taught not to bump into the objects in front of it. As its sensors on its front bumper send penalty signals, the robot could adopt the strategy of only moving backwards.

In unsupervised learning, the system is not instructed in what constitutes a right or a wrong answer: starting from the training data, the system finds patterns and creates clusters (Sartor & Lagioia, 2020), which can hopefully be informative for further decision-making.

A troubling characteristic of machine learning is that the programmer might not have an insight over the rationale of the decisions made by the system (B. D. Mittelstadt et al., 2016). In this case, we speak of a *black box* algorithm. (Pasquale, 2015)

The process of machine learning is dependent on the quality and quantity of input data, to the point that definitions of machine learning often mention data as well: an example is the moniker of *data-driven predictions* (Zuiderveen Borgesius et al., 2018) or “any methodology and set of techniques that can employ data to come up with novel patterns and knowledge, and generate models that can be used for effective predictions about the data” (Van Otterlo, 2013)

A powerful form of Machine Learning is deep learning, that is based on multilayered structures that detect patterns in massive datasets for the performance of specific tasks (Calo, 2017). Machine Learning, and Deep learning in particular, is the reason for the breakthroughs in AI the last decade (Coeckelbergh, 2020; Zuiderveen Borgesius et al., 2018). These developments were enabled by rising processing power and availability of data, (Calo, 2017) also known as the *data deluge* (Hey & Trefethen, 2003) of Big Data.

Big Data is composed of immense and heterogeneous sets of information shared and stored on servers, gathered in real time from multiple sources, in a scale above terabytes (Wigan, 2015). These data are ever-growing – roughly doubling every other year – and they concern anything that can be done via an Internet connection such as GPS-based location, user behavioral data and orienteering patterns when

visiting websites, online purchase records, multimedia shared on social networks (Hansson & Manfredsson, 2020), altogether painting a picture of the user's habits and taste. More than just being a new international commodity, big data is regarded as "a new structure of investment or capital within the sphere of business" (Hansson & Manfredsson, 2020). The analysis of big data can provide actionable knowledge for complex choices, based on multi-dimensional factors and non-predefined criteria (Sartor & Lagioia, 2020).

The collection of big data can happen in two ways, depending on the type of interaction between the person who produces data (the data subject) and the storage system. In the first case, termed *active Big Data*, the user is directly sending data to a storage system (using mobile apps to which they gave explicit analytic consent, submitting data to receive newsletters or create a new digital identity). Conversely, we have *passive Big Data* when personal data are collected by another person and input into an online storage system (for example, by hospital staff providing care for a patient and uploading their information). (European Economic and Social Committee, n.d.) Even in case of active big data, data transfer can happen without proper notification. In this case, we can draw another set of distinctions between *consciously transferred data* and *not consciously transferred data*. While in the first case the data subject was clearly and timely notified about the collection and storage of their data, in the case of not consciously transferred data the data subject did not receive proper notification about the use of their data, therefore not providing explicit and informed consent. (European Economic and Social Committee, n.d.)

After data collection and analysis, data is processed to gain insights about a specific cluster of subjects. In this case we distinguish an individual dimension (when the analysis aims at understanding the behavior of an individual, e.g. analyzing cell phones location data to generate restaurant recommendations), a social dimension (identifying and labelling specific groups for future use, e.g. a bank identifying risk-averse clients to offer specific plans to) and a hybrid dimension (where an individual is assigned to a pre-existing group due to some specific trait, e.g. discrimination due to gender identity or religion) (European Commission, 2017).

The ethical implications of the collection, use, reuse and misuse of Big Data represent a dynamic field of inquiry that is strictly related to the ethics of AI. The questions over privacy and autonomy that characterize the domain of personal data are echoed by those who are subject to AI-enabled profiled and personalization; while discriminatory patterns in data are reflected in discriminatory patterns in automated decision-making. In the following section, I will go over the relevance of Automated Decision making (ADM) systems for public governance and their several issues.

1.3 Automated Decision-Making Systems

The most striking characteristic of Artificial Intelligence is its capacity to be delegated with decision-making (van Noordt, Medaglia, & Misuraca, 2020) with varying degree of human involvement, if any (Article 29 Data Protection Working Party, 2018).

Complete automation in the form of Automated Decision-Making Systems (ADM) is desirable for time-consuming and repetitive task that “may be done completely by a computer based on some predetermined formula.” (Abdolmohammadi, 1999, p. 54) For semi-structured tasks requiring a degree of flexibility, instead, Decision Support Systems (DSS) are used. A Decision Support System is “an interactive computer-based software that assists decision makers by using certain models (e.g. statistical or mathematical models in analytical review procedures) and data to make inferences for the use of the decision maker” (*ibid.*, p. 54-55).

Automation can be justified in all situations where it can enhance performance, for example through faster processing and fewer errors compared to a human decision-maker. In decision support, technology is usually applied under the assumption that is jokingly known as the *fundamental theorem of Informatics* (C. P. Friedman, 2009): “the use of technology must improve the unaided human (i.e., $H + A > H$)” (Cabitza, Campagner, Angius, Natali, and Reverberi, *forthcoming*). The limitations of human cognitive capacities, when facing massive amounts of data, are evident. DDS and ADMSs can provide a much-needed support in making complex or time-consuming problems attainable (Jensen, Lowry, Burgoon, & Nunamaker, 2010). In these domains, ADMS and DDS have been observed to be cheaper, more precise and impartial than humans (Sartor & Lagioia, 2020), and are increasingly substituting them (Jussupow, Benbasat, & Heinzl, 2020).

As it concerns impartiality, AI is lauded for its immunity against the typical biases that characterize human cognition such as overconfidence, confirmation bias, priming and loss aversion, and its blindness to racial and gender prejudice (Sartor & Lagioia, 2020). And yet, real-world incidents demonstrated that ADMS can provide outputs that disparately impact the most vulnerable strata of society (Gwagwa, Kraemer-Mbula, Rizk, Rutenberg, & De Beer, 2020) by replicating and reinforcing biases already existing in societies (Mayson, 2018).

A problematic application of ADM systems regards their potential of making value-laden decisions that affect society at large (Taeihagh, 2021). It is the case of algorithms that predict recidivism scores and influence judgments in the field of justice, or provide to the police the estimated time and location of possible future crimes, which are both investigated in Sections 4.2 and 4.3. In high-stakes domains, algorithmic biases can be more dangerous than human biases: while a judge who systematically assigns a higher risk score to Black defendants can be called out for blatant racism, algorithms that display similar behavior are protected by the widely

held belief that algorithms, being first and foremost a mathematical construct, are by nature objective and immune to human biases (Monteiro, 2022).

Other risks regard loss of accountability due to delegation of decision-making; loss of human oversight due to the black box nature of some ADMS and DSS; data protection and privacy, with the right not to be subject to fully automated decisions; manipulation and deskilling (International Risk Governance Center, 2018). Moreover, the legitimation of ADMS as inexpensive and efficient decision-making systems may have problematic second-order consequences, whereby automation reduces the cost of collecting and storing and processing personal information in order to make increasingly more informed choices about individuals. This way, automation makes surveillance more appealing and easily applicable (Cannataci, Falce, & Pollicino, 2020). Another issue is the possible substitution of political deliberation: taken to its limit, “the goal of automation is to develop systems that replace societal decisions governing life, liberty, and opportunity.” (Andrejevic, 2019b)

In the following section I will discuss the risks of deskilling and *technological dominance* that underlie the deployment of decision support aids and automated decision-making systems, to then focus on the topic of *automated injustice*, in which the biases embedded in the training datasets of ADMS result in outputs that disproportionately harm vulnerable groups.

1.3.1 Technological Dominance and Automation Bias

The challenge of achieving an adequate balance between people’s personal decision-making and what they delegate to algorithms has been cited as a fundamental issue in discussions about user autonomy (Floridi & Taddeo, 2016). Research has addressed on the negative effects of automated and supported decision making, which are commonly referred to as loss of situational awareness, automation complacency and bias, and deskilling, which refers to the non-acquisition, degradation or even loss of abilities. (Cabitza, Rasoini, & Gensini, 2017; Goddard, Roudsari, & Wyatt, 2014). As a result, the worries about using ADMS are that the user will lack or lose the necessary competences to make a choice without relying on algorithmic assistance, while the aid will be viewed as capable of autonomously making the decision. As such, the user is infantilized. (Coeckelbergh, 2020)

We should recognize that AI systems might inadvertently induce forms of complacency, deskilling, and avoidance of responsibility, undermining the same decision-making abilities they are designed to enhance. (Bond et al., 2018; Cabitza, Campagner, & Simone, 2021; Cabitza & Natali, 2022a; Cabitza, Rasoini, & Gensini, 2017; Grote & Berens, 2020; Tsamados et al., 2022) Over-reliance and mental outsourcing to technology has been shown to impact cognition (Carr, 2010) by remodeling the brain through a sort of negative neuroplasticity that has compared to a *digital dementia* (Spitzer, 2016). The pathological reliance on decision support systems is

defined as *decision atrophy*, (Cabitza & Natali, 2022a; Farindon, 2021) which affects the human traits we value most in decision making: autonomy, intuition, and accountability (Cabitza & Natali, 2022a; Farindon, 2021; Frischmann & Selinger, 2018)

The centrality of the issue of over-reliance has been addressed by the *theory of technology dominance* (Arnold & Sutton, 1998), which considers the main determinants of reliance (Jensen et al., 2010), and the main factors leading to its negative consequences.

This section was inspired by a conceptual and methodological framework for assessing technological dominance that is presently being developed at the Bicocca MUDI Lab. The impact of introducing AI systems into decision-making processes is analyzed in the forthcoming study *AI shall have no dominion: on how to quantify technological dominance in AI-supported human decision making*, of which I am co-author (Cabitza et al., *forthcoming*).

The theory of technological dominance (Arnold & Sutton, 1998; Jensen et al., 2010; Triki & Weisner, 2014) refers to the powerful influence of AI systems on human judgment and decision-making. This impact is determined by a set of different possible interaction patterns between human judgment and the AI output. These *reliance patterns* are linked to distinct cognitive impacts, which can make decision-makers over-reliant on AI in the short term (Jensen et al., 2010) and possibly causing their deskilling in the long term.

Technological dominance is not a straightforwardly negative concept: a form of positive technological dominance exists, whereby the ADM system helps the user in avoiding a mistake. Unfortunately, it is not possible to both reap the benefits of dominance and avoid its negative consequence.

Another definition of technology dominance is “the state of decision making where the intelligent decision aid, as opposed to its user, takes primary control of a decision making process” (Arnold & Sutton, 1998). Sutton et al. (2018) have recently related the concept of dominance to “the dominating influence that technology may have over the user, which allows the user to take a more subservient position—in essence, the user deferring to the technology in the decision-making process.” This reduced human control over AI decisions has severe implications for the assignment of responsibility and even legal liability for the resulting harms (Taeihagh, 2021).

Technological dominance is related to, but not synonymous with, the concept of *automation bias* (Mosier & Skitka, 1999), which emerges when people’s trust in the algorithm exceeds its actual capabilities. Three main factors causing automation bias are algorithmic authority, cognitive miser, and diffusion of responsibility (Koll, 2020).

Many applications that involve Artificial Intelligence are designed to formally preserve human discretion, such that the system’s output is presented to the user

as a recommendation. In determining whether or not to act on the proposal, the human user retains formal decision-making authority. (Yeung, 2019) But the demarcation between fully and partly automated decisions may not be as clear as previously thought. (Zuiderveen Borgesius et al., 2018) observed that the risk of discrimination is similar in both cases: “Recommendations by computers may have an air of rationality or infallibility, and people might blindly follow them.” Rather than being an active and dominant part to the decision-making process, the human agent may become complacent with the AI decision owing to automation bias - or even to the lack of time, context and competence to make an effective choice on their own. (Zuiderveen Borgesius et al., 2018) A telling example is that of *VioGén*, a Spanish risk assessment software that is applied in all reported gender-based violence situations (Falletti, 2022). *VioGén* evaluated the level of risk that is posed to the victim of gender violence, and its output can be crucial in the decision of whether a person is granted police protection. A worrying finding is that, although *VioGén* was designed as a recommendation system whose results could be adjusted, police officers validated the automated output in 95% of cases (Zurita Bayona et al., 2014), making *VioGén* a *de facto* automated system with poor human oversight (Eticas Foundation, 2022a) due to technological dominance.

1.3.2 Automating injustice?

As described by Sandvig (2015), AI systems have since long been considered as neutral decision-makers, capable of acting without displaying the biases that cloud the judgment of humans. This narrative has favored the automation of human decision-making, and Logg et al. (2019) even observed that decision makers value algorithmic support to the point that they adapt their own estimates to be closer towards the estimates provided by algorithms, compared to estimates provided by human agents. (Logg, Minson, & Moore, 2019) In their experiment, decision-makers rated the recommendations of an algorithm as superior to both their own and another person’s judgment. And yet, the shortcomings of the automation of judgment by algorithm are increasingly evident. In particular, Automated Decision-Making systems have been shown to replicate and reinforce biases and discrimination (Floridi et al., 2022; Monteiro, 2022). What is most concerning is not the display of some direct and blatant discrimination, whereby unjust decisions are made on the basis of protected features such as gender, socioeconomic status and ethnicity (Sartor & Lagioia, 2020). Rather, the system’s outcome’s rationale will often be obfuscated by proxy variables, seemingly innocuous pieces of information (like ZIP code) that are used to derive other protected features, such as income and likely ethnicity (International Risk Governance Center, 2018).

There can be multiple sources of bias in a system: usually, they derive from training and/or input data, or the manner in which they are processes, or even

from the human interpretation of the output (International Risk Governance Center, 2018). Some sources of bias in data are the embedding of real-world discrimination as a neutral status, and the phenomenon of *undersampling*, where the training data fails to capture the complexity of the world (Blackman, 2022) and may display specific blind spots, such as the relative lack of data on women of color in facial recognition systems, leading to increased error rates that tackle already vulnerable populations. Despite assurances of greater human oversight, training data can be biased even in the case of supervised learning: by being trained on human judgments, these systems may adapt the unexpressed biases of the decision-makers. It is the case of recruitment systems that generalize and reflect the hiring patterns shown by humans beforehand: these systems have been shown to discount CVs that contained references to women’s organizations, such as rowing teams or chess groups, using them as a proxy for gender (Blackman, 2022). Similarly proxies could be found for candidates of color, reflecting the racial bias of past hiring managers (Sartor & Lagioia, 2020).

An example of bias arising from wrongful interpretation is that of crime predictions: since they are based on arrest data, the output of the system does not exactly reflect the rate of *actual* crimes being committed. Many crimes, as in the unfortunate case of gender-based violence, are never reported to the police; others, like white-collar crime, are less easily detected and investigated; and some crimes end up with no perpetrator being arrested, perhaps because their privileged socioeconomic status made them appear unsuspecting. What crime predictors *actually* predict is arrest rate, which is contingent to racial stereotypes and the phenomenon of increased surveillance on marginalized communities (Eubanks, 2018; Mayson, 2018; Richardson, Schultz, & Crawford, 2019).

While debiasing techniques exist and are continuously being developed, they involve a dilemma: to evaluate whether proxy measures can be used to infer sensitive data, these same sensitive data ought to be included in the system for monitoring. However, this is not seen as socially acceptable (International Risk Governance Center, 2018).

Therefore, the unjust outcomes of AI systems become ‘automated’: human decision-makers tend to delegate their decision-making to decision support systems, effectively perpetrating the values embedded in the algorithm. Following Macnish (2012), “the values of the author, wittingly or not, are frozen into the code, effectively institutionalising those values.” Another issue is the shifting focus from addressing the risk factors of a specific problem to their criminalization: it is the case of recidivism risk assessment system that assign a higher recidivism risk score to defendants coming from disadvantaged backgrounds, turning a fact of life outside one’s control into an automatically-processed penalty. When human complacency allows the algorithmic output to dictate socially relevant decision, the principle of

presumption of innocence, judicial discretion and alleviating circumstances are at risk.

Chapter 2

Ethics of Artificial Intelligence

While the definition debate is ongoing, Artificial Intelligence is often associated with expressions that highlight a specific, albeit aspirational, quality that it is supposed to display: it is the case of the over-represented *trustworthy AI* and *ethical AI*. These expressions found acceptance and resonance in academic, institutional, and even legal discourse. However, it is unclear whether these traits are exclusive to the AI system *per se*: rather, they are *relational* attributes, as being a trustworthy AI system presupposes the presence of an agent who trusts it; and being ethical implies that the rights of individuals impacted by its outputs are not violated (Cabitza & Natali, 2022a). By discussing the influence that AI systems exert on its users and society at large, I will focus on the ethics of Artificial Intelligence, the values connected to it and their operationalization.

Applied ethics is one of the four primary areas of academic research in ethics. While *meta-ethics* is concerned with the truth-value and meaning of moral judgments, if any, *normative ethics* aims at determining right from wrong and delineate a specific course of moral action, while *descriptive ethics* investigates moral actions and beliefs empirically (High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, 2019b). Applied ethics aims to answer moral dilemmas or inform decision-making in specific and often novel circumstances and contexts (Casiraghi, Burgess, & Liden, 2021). AI ethics is an example of applied ethics, since it “focuses on the normative challenges presented by the design, development, implementation, and use of AI” (High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, 2019b). Just like applied ethics, it involves an inter-disciplinary dialogue, frequently outside of academia, and is connected to policymaking initiatives and decision-making processes in corporate or governmental entities (Casiraghi et al., 2021). It is a dialogue involving AI developers, users, citizens, and policymakers on issues such as the relationship between science and politics, allocation of public funding, the safety of AI systems, their impact of human autonomy and the risk of large-scale discrimination, the determination of moral responsibility and accountability in the event of malfunctioning or misuse (Floridi & Taddeo, 2016), the instillation and assessment of specific values in new technologies,

and the alignment between the goals of the technology sector and societal well-being (Daly et al., 2019).

Ethical considerations in AI arose from the real-world harm that poorly designed AI systems can cause (Morley, Floridi, Kinsey, & Elhalal, 2021), in particular with unintended effects that exacerbate inequality (Ulnicane, Knight, Leach, Stahl, & Wanjiku, 2021) and pose considerable social harm, as well as reputational risks for organizations developing and implementing AI systems (Blackman, 2022). These threats are always broad in scope because AI operates at scale, performing almost instantly tasks that humans would take hundreds of hours to complete. Consequently, in the case of unethical practices or biases, these can impact a large number of individuals at once (Blackman, 2022). On the other hand, the benefits from an ethically-aligned AI are plenty, especially in the field of *AI For Social Good* where AI applications are enhancing human well-being in unprecedented ways. (COWLS, King, Taddeo, & Floridi, 2019). Therefore, there is a strong incentive to pursue Ethical AI, that can be defined as “the development, deployment and use of AI that ensures compliance with ethical norms, including fundamental rights as special moral entitlements, ethical principles and related core values.” (High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, 2019b)

A plausible starting event for applied ethics in AI was when Batya Friedman and Helen Nissenbaum wrote *Bias in Computer Systems* (1996), a framework for evaluating and responding to discriminatory machines, in 1996 (Calo, 2017). Since then, it appears that the field of AI ethics has undergone three broad phases (Kazim & Koshiyama, 2021). The first phase was characterized by the composition and adoption of AI ethics sets of principles (Hagendorff, 2021; Kazim & Koshiyama, 2021), both by private companies and governments (Fjeld et al., 2020; OECD, 2019b). The first publication of such principles coincided with the *Asilomar Conference of Beneficial AI*, held in 2017 at Pacific Grove, California. The twenty-three Asilomar Principles set guidelines for doing responsible research, indicated several values that AI must respect, and considerations about long-term challenges (Whittlestone, Nyrup, Alexandrova, & Cave, 2019).

The second phase was more technically-minded. It was based on *ethical-by-design* approaches (Kazim & Koshiyama, 2021), that can be defined as “provisions for the systematic inclusion of ethical guidelines” (Panagiotopoulos & Rodrigues, 2021). The key to responsible innovation, during the second phase of AI ethics, was the integration of ethics in the design and development stage of new AI systems (Coeckelbergh, 2020).

The third and current phase of ethical AI is instead concerned with the translation of principles into practice (Hagendorff 2020, see Section 2.2) through the standardization and operationalization of AI ethics. Possible translation mechanisms are policy, industry standards, certification and audit procedures (Kazim &

Koshiyama, 2021).

AI ethics is now a fast emerging academic subject, with ethics courses being integrated into the computer science curricula of an increasing number of universities. (Fiesler, Garrett, & Beard, 2020; Fiesler et al., 2020; Grosz et al., 2019; R. Reich, Sahami, Weinstein, & Cohen, 2020) New research institutions and dedicated conferences have been established, with the *ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency (FAccT)*¹ and the *AAAI/ACM Conference on AI, Ethics, and Society (AIES)*² conferences holding their first annual session in 2018 and flourishing since then. (Fjeld et al., 2020; Green, 2021a) Private companies have been pivotal players, by developing and sharing their own AI principles, (Fjeld et al., 2020) hiring philosophers, establishing ethical oversight councils, and promoting ethics and diversity training for employees, to the point where "Ethics is arguably the hottest product in Silicon Valley" (Metcalf, Moss, et al., 2019).

The fast methodological progress in the field stands in a striking contrast with the relative stalemate in terms of the issues explored, which mostly revolve around explainability, fairness, privacy, accountability, and safety (Hagendorff, 2021). It appears that the choice of to focus on such issues is influenced by relative ease in addressing them through technical solutions (*ibid.*). However, technology cannot be the only focus: against the hype of *ethical solutionism* (Floridi, 2018), it is vital to realize the limits of what tech ethics can do, and a broader socio-technical perspective should be considered (Fossa, Schiaffonati, & Tamburrini, 2021). A clear example of this is the discourse around algorithmic discrimination, that has so far been addressed via the implementation of algorithmic fairness solutions that are centered on narrow definitions of statistical parity and error rates, while leaving in place those structural and systemic conditions that generate algorithmic harms (Green, 2021b; Hoffmann, 2019).

Ethics principles, guidelines, and specific training must be integrated into multi-pronged approaches to improve the digital ecosystem. These include activism, policy reforms, and new engineering practices (Green, 2021a), such as effective legislation (Chapter 3) and auditing mechanisms (Chapter 5).

2.1 The values of Ethical AI and the HLEG AI Ethics Guidelines

The analysis of the values encoded in 100 highly cited machine learning papers presented at two major machine learning conferences, NeurIPS and ICML, led to concerning findings. According to the research conducted by Birhane, Kalluri, et

¹<https://facctconference.org>

²<https://www.aies-conference.com>

al. (2022), only a small percentage of papers (15%) mentioned their project’s relation to a social need, and just 1% acknowledged possible negative implications. *Performance, Generalization, Quantitative evidence, and Efficiency* were the most often mentioned values in these publications, with little room left for ethical considerations (Birhane, Kalluri, et al., 2022). These ‘technical’ values seem to have been echoed by public administrations. Since they are criticised for their slowness, costliness, and bureaucratic inefficiency, governments have a strong incentive to be perceived as inventive problem solvers. Therefore, they can spread a simplistic narrative, claiming that deploying algorithmic technologies will improve the cost-effectiveness of the public sector. Nonetheless, the many examples listed in the OASI Report (2022b) demonstrate how problematic the use of algorithms by the public administration can be, as well as the high risk of reproducing and reinforcing in a systematic manner bias and inefficiency in public decision-making processes (Eticas Foundation, 2022b). Introducing AI into complex socio-technical systems entails a broader range of value considerations besides task precision and efficiency: these priorities may not reflect public collective values, and in some cases they may even be misaligned with constitutional values upholding human rights (Yeung, 2019). The UN Secretary General, in his June 2020 report, highlighted that by then approximately 160 sets of corporate, national, and international ethical standards for AI had been published. “However”, he warned, “there is no one platform to connect these distinct activities.” (UN Secretary General, 2020)

Identifying which principles represent the key ideas of Ethical AI is a difficult process due to *principle proliferation* (Fjeld et al., 2020), that is, the increasing breadth and number of values advocated for in papers, reports and regulations. As of April 2020, 167 documents were included in the *AI Ethics Guidelines Global Inventory*³ managed by Algorithmwatch. The *LAIP - Linking Artificial Intelligence Principles* database⁴ managed to collect 90 AI principle proposals elaborated in international regulations and white papers by a variety of governmental and non-governmental, non-profit, institutional and industry actors. The wide array of proposed principles was clustered around eleven categories: *Sustainability, Collaboration, Share, Fairness, For human, Transparency, Privacy, Security, Safety, Accountability* and *Long-term AI*. In their 2020 study on principled Artificial Intelligence, Fjeld et al. (2020) from the Berkman Klein Center for Internet and Society analyzed 36 influential documents on Ethical AI, sampled for a high degree of variability. They pinpointed eight prominent principles on which increasing convergence was found. These principles are *Fairness and Non-discrimination* (found in 100% of analyzed documents), *Privacy* (97%), *Accountability* (97%), *Transparency and Explainability* (94%), *Safety and Security* (81%), *Professional Responsibility* (78%), *Human*

³<https://inventory.algorithmwatch.org/>

⁴<https://www.linking-ai-principles.org/keywords>

Control of Technology (69%) and *Promotion of Human Values* (69%).

This diversity of ethical concepts is prevalent throughout and among human communities. The presence of the value of *Harmony* in two of the three Chinese government-endorsed AI ethical principle-sets is a peculiar difference from the sets of principles provided by the EU (Roberts et al., 2021). Even within an ostensibly uniform ‘Western’ set of values, there are incompatible accounts of data privacy between the European Union and the United States (Tourkochoriti, 2014), and it seems there are as many philosophical conceptions of fairness as there are philosophers. As a result of the gender and racial diversity issue in the artificial intelligence industry, the values underlying and influencing emerging technologies cannot help but be skewed in favor of the overrepresented community (Special Rapporteur on Extreme Poverty and Human Rights Philip Alston, 2019b). To avoid this, it is necessary to audit in an ethically-informed manner the practices underlying the development and deployment of AI systems.

Recognizing these issues and limitations, global agreement may be confined to few ‘thin’ universalist values, differing in their interpretation accord to cultural contexts. (Roberts et al., 2021) The Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI, which were issued by the European Commission in April 2019 (High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, 2019b) and have since helped shape EU policy proposals pertaining to the digital world, can serve as a reference point for the proposed value pluralist approach. (Center for AI and Digital Policy, 2017) The High-Level Expert Group on AI, comprised of 52 specialists in diverse domains of AI from academia, business, and civil society, developed these guidelines after significant public engagement. They establish seven essential characteristics that AI systems must satisfy: human agency and oversight; technical robustness and safety; privacy and data governance; transparency; diversity, non-discrimination and fairness; societal and environmental well-being; accountability. In the following sections, I will go over each of these values.

2.1.1 Human agency and oversight

“AI systems should support human autonomy and decision-making, as prescribed by the principle of respect for human autonomy. This requires that AI systems should both act as enablers to a democratic, flourishing and equitable society by supporting the user’s agency and foster fundamental rights, and allow for human oversight.”

High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (2019b)

Human oversight involves technical human control over a specific AI system, and accountability for the whole process of development and deployment, which is based

on human judgment (Methnani, Aler Tubella, Dignum, & Theodorou, 2021). The principle of oversight aims at guaranteeing that AI systems do not infringe personal autonomy, nor display similar negative consequences. The general notion of human autonomy should be the key of the operation of any AI system, as users should be able to make independent, informed choices on their interaction with the system. They should be provided with the information and tools necessary to comprehend the decisions of AI systems, as well as challenging them.

In the *IEEE Ethical Aligned Design (Version 2)* report, oversight is related to the principles of transparency and accountability (Shahriari & Shahriari, 2017), whilst the European Commission AI Watch links oversight to the keywords “human control” and “human in the loop” (J. European Commission, Nativi, & De Nigris, 2021). The *Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI* drafted in 2019 by the High-level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence identify three possible governance mechanisms that can ensure proper oversight: the human-in-the-loop (HITL), human-on-the-loop (HOTL), or human-in-command (HIC) approaches, with HITL being the most discussed in academia and beyond (Cabitza & Natali, 2022a).

Human-on-the-loop refers to the capability for human monitoring and intervention during a system’s design cycle. The Human-in-command approach is centered on the user’s capacity to supervise the AI system’s activities and overall impact, while keeping control over whether or how the system is deployed in any given scenario. Finally, Human-in-the-loop is a method of human oversight where the user is allowed and even encouraged to intervene in every decision cycle of the system, even adjusting the algorithm or learning system itself (Meza Martínez, Nadj, & Maedche, 2019). This is not feasible, nor desirable, in many circumstances. (The Council of Europe’s Ad Hoc Committee on AI, 2020) “Human-in-the-Loop” typically implies the idea that computers will perform practically everything, but humans should be within reach in case some unexpected event happens. (Cabitza & Natali, 2022a) However, when workers’ primary function is reduced to that of alienated auditors of the technology well-functioning, we become complacent and inattentive to the circumstances (Cabitza & Natali, 2022a) hindering situational awareness resulting in *automation complacency* (Parasuraman & Manzey, 2010)). Moreover, “humans kept ‘in the loop’ of automated decision-making may be poorly equipped to identify problems and take corrective actions” (B. D. Mittelstadt et al., 2016)

Another factor hindering oversight is the opacity of algorithms, that Pasquale (2015) first defined as *black boxes*. The difference in the speed and scale of AI operations compared to human monitoring capacity is another impediment for meaningful oversight. (B. D. Mittelstadt et al., 2016; Yeung, 2019)

2.1.2 Technical robustness and safety

“Technical robustness requires that AI systems be developed with a preventative approach to risks and in a manner such that they reliably behave as intended while minimising unintentional and unexpected harm, and preventing unacceptable harm. This should also apply to potential changes in their operating environment or the presence of other agents (human and artificial) that may interact with the system in an adversarial manner. In addition, the physical and mental integrity of humans should be ensured.”

High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (2019b)

Robustness is a concept that encompasses protection from hacking and adversarial attacks; the reproducibility and accuracy of its outputs; its capability to provide satisfactory results when deployed in different contexts and exposed to different datasets (High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, 2019b). Tambon et al. (2022) define robustness as “the property of a system to remain effective even outside its usual conditions of operation.” (Tambon et al., 2022)

According to the OECD principles for trustworthy AI (2019c), robustness is linked to the idea of functioning appropriately in conditions of normal use, without posing “unreasonable” safety risks. In (OECD G20 Digital Economy Task Force, 2020), two ways to ensure robustness and safety are presented: first, “traceability and subsequent analysis and inquiry”, and second “applying a risk management approach.” (OECD G20 Digital Economy Task Force, 2020) The requirement of traceability encompasses data sets, processes and decisions made during the life cycle of the AI system, since only a comprehensive approach can enable the best possible analysis of the system’s outcomes. This entail the application of a systematic and continuous risk management approach (OECD, 2019c).

The emphasis on safety is particularly relevant due to persisting regulatory and liability vacuums in the case of harms caused by AI systems. Safety frameworks tend to be concerned with hardware products, and do not provide sufficient guidance for software products that autonomously learn and make decisions (OECD, 2019b). When AI systems encounter unexpected situations they were not trained for, they might produce outputs that pose safety hazards for users (Taeihagh, 2021). In case of malfunctioning, fallback plans should be guaranteed for example in the form of timely reestablishment of full human control, or temporarily switching to rule-based procedures (High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, 2019b).

Accuracy is relevant to safety especially when the AI system makes decisions that affect the lives of people: while it is impossible to avoid errors altogether, the system should inform users of its error rates.

Despite their technical definitions, robustness and safety can be considered full-fledged ethical issues as they act as preconditions for trust and play a relevant role in the prevention of harm at an individual and societal level. (A. Kaminski et al., 2020)

2.1.3 Privacy and data governance

“Privacy [is] a fundamental right particularly affected by AI systems. Prevention of harm to privacy also necessitates adequate data governance that covers the quality and integrity of the data used, its relevance in light of the domain in which the AI systems will be deployed, its access protocols and the capability to process data in a manner that protects privacy.”

High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (2019b)

Ever since photographs entered the mainstream, the concept of privacy evolved side by side with technological development. Today’s technology displays an unprecedented potential for surveillance (Andrejevic, 2019a, 2019b), and the flow of information we are embedded in poses unprecedented risks to privacy due to its scale, type of information considered and its distribution, its endurance, and the effect of erroneous personal information - that, in the case of Automatic Decision-making systems, can result in unfair decisions.

According to the World Economic Forum, the term “privacy” has a very broad use associated with the idea of “protection from harm” of the affected person (World Economic Forum, 2011). This conception is a negative one, in line with the earliest implications of the term, as privacy meant barring the State from abusing its powers – such as entering a private house without a warrant. Over time, privacy was increasingly conceived as a subjective right of the individual, related to dignity, autonomy, and freedom. This right implied the protection of personal interests (Van der Sloot, 2017). The same happened for data protection. While first focusing on the establishment of rules and obligation for the fair, safe and transparent processing of data, data protection was then interpreted as the individual right of personal data control (Van der Sloot, 2017). This individualistic conception of both privacy and data protection is increasingly obsolete and may result in the inability to fully grasp and curb the possible damages that an indiscriminate use of big data can exercise on a plurality of subjects and even society as a whole. For this reason, the political scientist Priscilla Regan (Regan, 1995) argued that privacy should be framed as a social good and not only as an individual one.

In this sense, “Data protection law does not have the single purpose of protecting only one fundamental right, but rather acts as an umbrella mechanism for multiple

fundamental rights whenever affected by the processing of personal data.” (Ioannidis, 2021a) Privacy acts as an enabler of other rights, aiding in particular in the enjoyment of the right to freedom of thought and religious belief, the freedom of expression, the right to non-discrimination and that to a fair trial (*ibid.*) Ethical AI requires data to be collected, processed, and shared in a privacy-mindful manner, empowering people in their right to be informed on the collection and the type of processing that their data is undergoing, their right of access to their data or to object to their collection or processing know what happens to their data, to access their data, to object to the collection or processing of their data. (Coeckelbergh, 2020) AI systems must provide privacy and data security guarantees for as long as they operate. This includes both the data that was first provided by the user, as well as the information that was inferred about the user via their interaction with the system (High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, 2019b). This is an example of data governance, which concerns “design choices, data collection, data preparation processes, the formulation of assumptions, assessments of the availability, quantity, and suitability of the data, bias examination, and the identification of, and solutions for, data gaps or shortcomings” (van Dijck, 2022) Further data governance requirements are relevant, representative, complete and error-free datasets that reflect the setting of application of the system. (van Dijck, 2022)

2.1.4 Transparency

“[Transparency] is closely linked with the principle of explicability and encompasses transparency of elements relevant to an AI system: the data, the system and the business models.”

High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (2019b)

Transparency is strictly connected to explainability, as it is necessary to clarify both the technical and organizational procedures behind the system operations. Among its requirements, there is the precise and available documentation on training data and collected data, on the characteristics of deployed algorithms and the decision-making processes that led to the final decision. In turn, this ensures the effective auditability of the system. However, even full disclosure of datasets and algorithmic models may not be sufficient to foster a meaningful understanding of the functioning of the system by its users and affected subjects, because of the inherent opacity of self-learning algorithms (Pasquale, 2015) and the cognitive impossibility for humans to interpret all this information. Explanations should be “tailored to the requirements of the target groups such as users and persons affected” (A. Kaminski et al., 2020), who may have different levels of technical savviness and different interests over *what* constitutes a useful explanation: drawing from a taxonomy of explanations delineated by researchers from the MUDI Lab and other international scholars

and to which I contributed (Cabitza et al., *in press*), while those in the technical field might be interested in *mechanistic* or *computational* explanations that explain *how* and *why* the system reached its output from its data input, citizens subject to an automated decisions could instead seek to receive an *informative* explanation, that describes the implications of a certain decision, and a *causal* explanation, defining the real-world elements that led to the decision (and that can therefore be acted upon, or challenged in case they display biased conceptions). For a judge evaluating an automated risk assessment, a *cautionary* explanation may be useful, whereby the output is accompanied by an estimation the uncertainty behind it. Possible solutions are the provision of visualization tools that provide insights into the code and data that are accessible even to laypersons (Floridi & Taddeo, 2016). Another solution to enhance explainability puts the principle of transparency at odds with that of accuracy that is embedded in *Technical robustness and safety*: in fact, preferring algorithms that take into consideration fewer parameters results in more explicable final decisions, albeit less accurate ones.

Transparency can also work as a mechanism to foster trustworthiness through responsible disclosure of meaningful information (OECD, 2019c), and can play a role for fairness considerations, as an explicable algorithmic decision-making process can reveal the presence of potential biases (Hagendorff, 2021), uncover discrimination and allow for the identification of human rights violations to be redressed in court. A transparent decision-making process clarifies the level of moral responsibility and accountability of the involved actors, and determines chains of causality (OECD G20 Digital Economy Task Force, 2020). This demonstrates how transparency, like privacy, is “a pro-ethical condition for enabling or impairing other ethical practices or principles.” (Turilli & Floridi, 2009)

2.1.5 Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness

“In order to achieve Trustworthy AI, we must enable inclusion and diversity throughout the entire AI system’s life cycle. Besides the consideration and involvement of all affected stakeholders throughout the process, this also entails ensuring equal access through inclusive design processes as well as equal treatment. This requirement is closely linked with the principle of fairness.”

High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (2019b)

The principle of diversity, non-discrimination and fairness requires that, throughout the whole life cycle of the AI system, inclusivity and justice are guaranteed. This entails avoiding unfair biases, which may arise from several factors: usually, the main suspect is datasets, both in training and operations. These datasets can be incomplete or contain errors; in some cases, they could include traces of historic bias, such

as unfair representation of specific vulnerable groups. When such datasets are used in the training or operation of an AI system, they propagate and amplify the same injustices that are inscribed in them, since “Discriminatory analytics can contribute to self-fulfilling prophecies and stigmatisation in targeted groups, undermining their autonomy and participation in society” (B. D. Mittelstadt et al., 2016). To avoid this, oversight mechanisms should be in place to assess several aspects of the system: its purpose, requirements, constraints and decisions.

Diverse teams, including professionals from different educational, socioeconomic, gender and ethnic backgrounds, can be an asset in reducing unfairness by including a wide range of sensibilities, opinions, and life experiences, providing to the team the necessary aerial view to detect those biases that would have otherwise flown under the radar (High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, 2019b). It is clear that, without the enactment of proactive inclusion strategies, the AI sector is in a diversity crisis: “the development of AI is currently taking place within a homogeneous environment principally consisting of young, white men, with the result that (whether intentionally or unintentionally) cultural and gender disparities are being embedded in AI.” (European Economic and Social Committee, 2017)

Another aspect of fairness is that of accessibility and user-centricity of AI systems, that is ensured by implementing the seven Universal Design Principles⁵: *Equitable use*, *Flexibility in use*, *Simple and intuitive use*, *Perceptible information*, *Tolerance for error*, *Low physical effort*, *Size and space for approach and use*. This includes the state-of-the-art of accessibility standards for people with disabilities. The application of these principles ensures that all people, regardless of age and abilities, can use AI products or services (High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, 2019b).

Finally, stakeholder participation should be encouraged: those who are directly or indirectly affected by the system should be consulted throughout the system’s life cycle, to receive regular feedback on the fairness of the system and detect possible emerging or underlying biases.

”First, there are roughly two dozen quantitative metrics for fairness, and crucially, they are not compatible with each other. You simply cannot be fair according to all of them at the same time.” (Blackman, 2022)

2.1.6 Societal and environmental well-being

“In line with the *principles of fairness* and *prevention of harm*, the broader society, other sentient beings and the environment should be also considered as stakeholders throughout the AI system’s life cycle. Sustainability and ecological responsibility of AI systems should be en-

⁵<https://universaldesign.ie/what-is-universal-design/the-7-principles/>

couraged, and research should be fostered into AI solutions addressing areas of global concern, such as for instance the Sustainable Development Goals. Ideally, AI systems should be used to benefit all human beings, including future generations.”

High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (2019b)

The principle of societal and environmental well-being requires that AI should be used to the advantage of all living and future creatures, considering the protection of the environment and intragenerational fairness. A definition of Sustainable AI is provided by van Wynsberghe (2021): “a field of research that applies to the technology of AI (the hardware powering AI, the methods to train AI, and the actual processing of data by AI) and the application of AI while addressing issues of AI sustainability and/or sustainable development.” Therefore, AI systems must be environmentally friendly and limit to the best extent possible their carbon footprint during its whole life cycle, including the supply chain of its hardware components and their disposal (A. Kaminski et al., 2020). In fact, it was calculated that the emissions related to the training of a large ML model are equal to those produced by five cars during their whole lifetime (K. Crawford, 2021); the training of a single Natural Language Processing model can lead to circa 300 tons of carbon dioxide emissions (Strubell, Ganesh, & McCallum, 2019). Supply chain issues concern not only the carbon emission linked with the transportation of hardware, but also to the procurement of resources such as rare-earth metals that entail child and slave labour, spark conflict for land, and disrupt local economies (K. Crawford, 2021; Hagendorff, 2021).

Supply chain does not only have a material and transport dimension, but it also concerns the outsourced data labor that is employed for the labeling of training data and output verification. This *microwork* represents a market worth \$1.7B in 2019, and likely to reach a value of \$4.1B by 2024. (Hagendorff, 2021). The most famous microwork platform is *Amazon Mechanical Turk*, where data labellers and output verifiers can earn as little as \$.01 per task completed, resulting in an estimated median hourly wage of \$1.38 (Casilli, 2017). In his work *Blind Spots in AI Ethics*, Hagendorff (2021) highlights that the current discourse around responsible AI largely ignored the externalities of AI development on “low-wage clickworkers, persons affected by ecological damages, exploited mineworkers, animals in laboratories, etc.”

This focus on well-being can provide an opposing narrative to that of growth at all costs, such as the unofficial Facebook motto *move fast and break things*. Instead, Floridi (2019) proposed the Renaissance adage of *festina lente*, make haste slowly. This slowness is instrumental to addressing the inherent tensions that lie within the principle of Sustainable AI. According to van Wynsberghe (2021), Sustainable AI

is characterized by three tensions between “AI innovation and equitable resource distribution; inter and intra-generational justice; and, between environment, society, and economy.” (van Wynsberghe, 2021) The societal impact of these technology should be assessed as to avoid costly trade-offs and favor the enhancement of living standards, avoiding pitfalls such as discrimination, political polarization, deterioration of social skills, extensive surveillance and loss of privacy.

The fair and inclusive development of AI is becoming a priority (OECD, 2019b). The first industry standard to explicitly address the implications of AI for well-being is *The Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineering’s (IEEE) Standard (Std) 7010-2020 Recommended Practice for Assessing the Impact of Autonomous and Intelligent Systems on Human Well-being*⁶, published in 2020. Moreover, increasing attention is given to the potential of AI to be a transformative technology for the achievement of United Nations Sustainable Development Goals⁷ by providing new solutions for efficient transport, better agriculture, increased health, quality education and the sustainability of cities (OECD, 2019b).

2.1.7 Accountability

“The requirement of accountability (...) is closely linked to the principle of fairness. It necessitates that mechanisms be put in place to ensure responsibility and accountability for AI systems and their outcomes, both before and after their development, deployment and use.”

High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (2019b)

Accountability describes a clear assignment of responsibility and related redress mechanisms to ensure compliance, report, oversight, and enforcement (Novelli, Taddeo, & Floridi, 2022). As such, this concept is linked to the notions of transparency, fairness, explainability and legal responsibility (International Risk Governance Center, 2018). In fact, the developers and deployers of accountable systems must be capable of providing information concerning the factors and processes that gave rise to a specific output: as put by Novelli et al. (2022), accountability is an *answerability relation*. In case of negative consequence of the system, redress mechanisms should be available. Other requirements of accountability are ensuring the correct functioning and accuracy of the AI system and its legal compliance (OECD G20 Digital Economy Task Force, 2020).

It is clear that ensuring accountability is increasingly difficult as systems and responsibility structures become more complex, favoring the phenomena of *responsibility diffusion* and *responsibility flight* (A. Kaminski et al., 2020). An example is

⁶<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9283454>

⁷<https://sdgs.un.org/goals>

the *accountability act* between the AI system’s behavior and its developer’s control that complicates the assignment of blame, as this concept requires some degree of control and intentionality by the agent (B. D. Mittelstadt et al., 2016). This is especially contentious when the decision-making rationale of the AI becomes inscrutable even for its developer, since “complex and fluid systems (i.e. one with countless decision-making rules and lines of code) inhibit holistic oversight of decision-making pathways and dependencies.” (B. D. Mittelstadt et al., 2016)

To ensure accountability, obligations and responsibilities ought to be specified and designated. (A. Kaminski et al., 2020) In particular the system should be auditable in all its components, including algorithms, data, and design processes. This audit process can be performed both by internal or external auditors but, whenever the AI system can have significant impact on fundamental rights, an independent audit is preferred. The process of auditing will be explored in depth in Chapter 5. Other accountability mechanisms are certifications, legal requirements, best practices and ethical guidelines (A. Kaminski et al., 2020).

2.2 From principles to practice

The power of high-level principles to build consensus facilitates the simplification of complex ethical issues into a few core aspects that are easily grasped by individuals from a variety of fields and sectors. This promotes adherence to this set of agreed-upon values, which can serve as the foundation for more formal commitments in professional ethics and regulation (Whittlestone et al., 2019). Their value lies in their ability to highlight significant moral concepts applicable to a broad range of situations. This means that they can be used as a type of checklist, collecting the essential factors to be considered in any given situation (*ibid.*). However, principles may be insufficient to ensure that society can reap the advantages of AI systems and limit their risks: to be effective and useful on a daily basis, they must be able to direct action (A. Kaminski et al., 2020). Yet, it is not clear how AI developers handle ethical concerns in their everyday work (Figueras, Verhagen, & Cerratto Pargman, 2021).

According to A. Kaminski et al. (2020), for an AI ethical framework to be action-guiding, its implementation must solve three challenges: context-dependence, the socio-technical nature of AI, and ease of use. Following context-dependence, “the realisation of values depends on the field of application and cultural context”, so any approach for the practical application of AI ethics must consider cultural differences in moral views, possible value conflicts, and the diversity of application environments (A. Kaminski et al., 2020). The most straightforward example of value conflicts is the one between privacy and security in the context of AI-enabled surveillance, or the requirement of explainability lowering in turn that of accuracy

as more explicable models are the ones with less parameters (High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, 2019b). The heterogeneity of application contexts calls for flexibility in allocating priority to a principle over the other, as in the case in the field of justice, where all things considered, fairness ought to be preponderant (A. Kaminski et al., 2020). In terms of the socio-technical character of AI, the societal impact of AI is dependent not only on the technology, but also on several components in the system’s development and deployment, its aims, and the way it is integrated in an organization. Finally, ease of use refers to the ethical framework’s applicability, which should be aided by specific tools. This requirement of usability means different things for different stakeholders; for examples, citizens may refer to the clarity with which these principles are presented and their role in ensuring public accountability, whilst developers may refer to technical applicability (A. Kaminski et al., 2020). Possible solutions to these three issues range from auditing and risk assessment, to the defining of general principles in terms of technical and implementation requirements, to the application of a labelling system, where an intuitive AI Ethics label, inspired by the well-known energy efficiency label, gives straightforward communication on the compliance level of each AI system (*ibid.*)

Another issue with high-level ethical principles lies in their ambiguity, which can disguise conceptual complexity and discrepancy in their interpretation between societies. (Whittlestone et al., 2019) Instead of offering a well-developed and coherent framework, these high-level values may obfuscate key moral conflicts. Perhaps it would be preferable to make these disagreements evident, so that they can be addressed and understood more clearly. (*ibid.*) For example, while everyone agrees that the principle of ‘fairness’ is desirable, there are heated political disagreements about what actually exactly constitutes fairness. Another element to consider is the relative importance that different groups place on one value against another when they conflict. Making principles more “practical, comparable, and measurable” (A. Kaminski et al., 2020) by formalizing them into standards and regulations (Whittlestone et al., 2019) is a central step in dealing with value conflict.

Many AI ethics and governance statements share similar, if not identical, principles (Daly et al., 2019). Hagendorff (2020) has pointed out that the most cited principles, such as explainability, privacy, accountability, safety and fairness, are often “the most easily operationalized mathematically” utilizing theories that assume idealized conditions and clear targets that do not consider the variety and complexity of real-world situations (Brown, Davidovic, & Hasan, 2021). In this manner, principles are easily implementable through technical methods (Hagendorff, 2020). The ethical challenges that are more difficult to analyze analytically are seldom mentioned, according to meta-studies on AI ethics standard. For example, explainability can be operationalized by adopting techniques for complexity reduction such as “visualizations, the segmentation of solution space for local ex-

planations, the computation of the sensitivity a feature has upon model outputs, by trying to find simplified models with similar performances, by extracting relevant examples that relate to certain machine behaviors or by text explanations or other symbols that represent a model’s functioning.” (Hagendorff, 2021) Likewise, privacy can be operationalized through privacy preservation techniques that alter datasets in a way to complicate reidentification of individuals (e.g. differential privacy, *k-anonymization*), in concert with “legally established measures like the right for rectification or erasure, informed consent, purpose limitation, data minimization, independent privacy impact assessments.” (Hagendorff, 2021) In turn, safety can be strengthened by *red teaming* exercises, or technical safety auditing. Therefore, it is disputed if AI ethics does more than just strengthening existing techniques in AI research and development for tackling technological issues at this moment (*ibid.*). Such an approach involves “stripping down the multidimensionality of very complex social constructs to something that is measurable and calculable” (*ibid.*), nudging the choice of value adoption from the most comprehensive principle to the one that is most easily described analytically.

This technical solutionism also limits public engagement, as those who are not technically savvy will be *de facto* excluded from deliberations on the acceptability and potential solutions to AI-related challenges. This is especially problematic given that research (Edelman, 2019), polls (Zhang & Dafoe, 2019), and general trends in public engagement (Whittaker et al., 2018) show widespread concern about the risks of AI development, with skepticism over effective self-regulation, monitoring and enforcement of commitments made by the main players in AI (Brundage et al., 2020). When it comes to enforcing sanctions, even professional computing organizations like the IEEE and ACM are powerless against those who violate their ethical guidelines. (B. Mittelstadt, 2019)

A proposed technique for bridging the gap between the principles and practice in AI ethics is ethics-based auditing. (Mökander & Floridi, 2021) Ethics-based auditing is defined as “a governance mechanism that allows organisations to operationalise their ethical commitments and validate claims made about their AI systems.” (Floridi et al., 2022) Third-party auditors can be entrusted with assessing the veracity of the safety, security, privacy, and fairness promises made by AI developers (Mökander & Floridi, 2021). The issue of Ethics-based auditing will be explored in Section 5.2. In general, top auditing firms like PwC⁸ and Deloitte⁹ are developing their proprietary frameworks to assess and help designing trustworthy AI (Mökander & Floridi, 2021).

While these and other attempts are happening within business, academia, and

⁸<https://www.pwc.com/gx/en/issues/data-and-analytics/artificial-intelligence/what-is-responsible-ai.html>

⁹<https://www2.deloitte.com/it/it/pages/risk/topics/trustworthy-ai---deloitte-italy---risk.html>

civil society to define and even operationalize the ethics of AI, it is clear that “Principles alone cannot ensure ethical AI” (B. Mittelstadt, 2019), owing to the lack of a strong enforcement mechanism (Calo, 2017). These initiatives are unlikely to be able to replace the introduction and enforcement of legislation (Calo, 2017) that more directly controls the conduct of AI developers (Brundage et al., 2020). Ethics is a highly fluid and contested construct (Calo, 2017) that can be characterized as a process of reflection on the questions and debates surrounding moral judgment. As a result, it cannot be determined unequivocally. Policy, on the other hand, has a sense of finality once established (Calo, 2017). The political process may serve as a deliberative forum for determining priorities, where ethical considerations procedurally integrated.

Chapter 3

The governance of AI and the risk-based approach

Digital governance is the activity of “establishing and implementing policies, procedures, and standards for the proper development, use, and management of the infosphere” (Floridi, 2014, 2018). It may involve, for example, the standardization of processes to enhance data quality, reliability, access, and security, as well as building new accountability frameworks for data-related operations (Floridi, 2018). Digital governance guidelines may overlap with digital regulation, which is a collection of policies developed and implemented by social and political institutions to oversee the conduct of relevant actors in the digital sector (Floridi, 2018).

AI governance is still in its early stages, but it is progressing at a staggering rate. While government financing of AI research dates back to the mid-1950s (Center for AI and Digital Policy, 2017), the challenges of AI governance have only lately emerged beyond the confines of technical and academic arguments to permeate the public. This is due to governments analyzing the implications of AI deployment and making critical judgments on appropriate objectives for this area, in a balancing act between global dangers and ambitions. Since 2016, national governments, as well as public and commercial actors, technical and academic, for-profit and non-profit organizations, have practically all unveiled AI initiatives at the same time. This happened concurrently with discussions at international forums such as the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) and the World Economic Forum (WEF), meaning that countries and organizations were inspired and learned from one another (Ulnicane et al., 2021). In its rank of 160 countries, the Oxford Insights *2021 AI Government Readiness Index* emphasised that “nearly 40% of countries included in the index have published or are drafting national AI strategies”.

Despite this enthusiasm, researchers point out the extensive challenges in regulating AI systems, among which the imbalance of technological expertise between the commercial and the public sectors (Scherer, 2015), as well as the unpredictability

of future AI impacts. The evolving ecosystem of AI developers, businesses, and users makes it difficult to assign responsibility and identify a starting point for government intervention (M. E. Kaminski, in press; Scherer, 2015).

The recent attempts of governments towards the regulation of AI continue to favor *soft* regulatory measures, such as drafting ethical guidelines, voluntary initiatives, endorsing technical standards, and establishing codes of conduct. (OECD, 2021a) The preference accorded to soft law can be explained by the fact that new technologies are reshaping the regulatory landscape at an unforeseen speed, (A. Wong, 2021) threatening to outpace the regulatory responses put into place to address the concerns raised by AI. (Taeihagh, 2021) Current regulatory frameworks are inadequate to respond to the societal problems brought by AI due to asymmetries of information between regulators and Big Tech: the latter has vast advantages in terms of resources and data over governments, making it more difficult for regulators to introduce new AI legislation (Taeihagh, 2021). Governments also lack the necessary technical know-how, due to difficulties in attracting bright engineers who are instead drawn to the competitive wages of Silicon Valley and the like. This may lead governments to seek the external consulting of tech companies (Calo, 2017), in faith that corporate self-interest does not trump public interest.

When establishing a governance framework for AI, the question arises on whether soft laws or hard laws should be favored (Castets-Renard, 2020). But there is also a third option: relying on already-established laws from other domains that could prove useful to assure fairness and possibly alleviate discrimination issues. Consumer law may be applicable to protect customers from some sorts of deceptive AI-driven advertising. Competition legislation may be useful in protecting people from discriminatory behavior by a firm that has a dominant position. Administrative and criminal law may be relevant in public sector applications of AI systems to safeguard fair procedures. Issues of transparency could be addressed through freedom of information laws. In particular, non-discrimination and data protection legislation could be the best candidates for safeguarding against AI-driven discrimination (Zuiderveen Borgesius et al., 2018).

Unfortunately, this scenario is unlikely. In its current form, the law is powerless when facing the issues of groups discriminated by algorithms. This is because of two characteristics of the legal system: the complaint-based system and the proof of harm (Wachter, 2021). The complain-based system is powerless in an environment where affected individuals might not even realize they were harmed (Wachter, 2021). The evidential requirement instead poses undue expectations on ordinary citizens to *open the black box* of the algorithm and claim direct damage by assessing all data-processing initiatives, its inner logic, and evaluating the fairness of the processing of their data (Van der Sloot, 2017). These requirement would make it impossible to tackle the most pressing and problematic issues arising from algorithmic decision-

making, eventually preserving the status quo. Therefore Van der Sloot (2017), argues for letting go of the focus on black letter law by focusing on ethical rules and adapting to the fluidity of AI era.

The inadequacy of the current legal system in tackling the issues arising from algorithmic harms stems from a difficulty in the enforcement of black letter law and its focus on subjective rights. Moreover, legal rules have the disadvantage of becoming obsolete at a faster pace than general codes of conduct (Van der Sloot, 2017). To impede fast obsolescence, technology-neutral legal provisions can be introduced. The prime example is the European General Data Protection Regulation (European Commission, 2016). While embracing the concept of technical neutrality provides the advantage of not having to modify legal definitions each time a new technology is developed, the resulting broad definitions are hardly guiding in practice (Zuiderveen Borgesius et al., 2018). A possible solution is adopting multi-level legislation, in which statutory regulations are combined with guidelines and recommendations. (*ibid.*) Guidelines can be more detailed and practical, provided they are evaluated on a regular basis and modified as needed. (*ibid.*) As Koops (2006) puts it, “Through multi-level legislation, open-ended formulations and a mixed approach of abstract and concrete rules that are periodically evaluated, adequate legal certainty with respect to current technologies may be ensured, while at the same time sufficient scope is given for future technological developments.”

A comprehensive examination of national strategy papers performed by van Noordt and Misuraca (2022) demonstrates that the bulk of policy measures implemented by European Union nations are soft policy instruments such as communication campaigns, public-private partnerships, employee training, and voluntary codes of conduct. Incentives-based efforts, which include the transfer of economic resources or regulatory tools such as binding laws and regulations, the development of intellectual property rights, competition regulation, or ethical norms, are less common (Medaglia et al., 2021; van Noordt et al., 2020).

AI policy with an ethical component has been advocated by a number of actors, including governments and governmental entities, tech firms, professional associations, intergovernmental and non-governmental organizations, non-profit actors, and scholars. Most of these texts begin with the justification of policy by defining principles and then make recommendations in response to the ethical concerns observed (Coeckelbergh, 2020). Ethical initiatives are unlikely to replace policymaking: ethics is at its core contested, and lack a strong enforcement mechanism even in the case of moral agreement. Its principles are abstract and vague, and rarely action-guiding. Policy instead, once enacted, has some level of finality, an established enforcement mechanism, and a clear scope (Calo, 2017). The issue of human rights protection, therefore, cannot be left to the goodwill of companies committing to self-regulation or soft legislation: in what is described as *ethics washing*, the discourse over ethics

is instrumentalized by private companies to avoid regulation and external oversight. Ethics is considered as the ‘simple’ or ‘soft’ alternative to undesirable regulation, possibly overshadowing the need for ‘hard’ legal control (Zuiderveen Borgesius et al., 2018). Risks are frequently externalities, which means that, in the absence of any type of regulation, a corporation may have no motivation to internalize the cost of their mitigation (M. E. Kaminski, in press).

3.1 Regulating risk

To maximize the advantages of AI while minimizing its threats, governments throughout the world must better comprehend the magnitude and depth of the risk faced, as well as build legislative and governance procedures and structures to handle these concerns. Managing the volume and pace of AI adoption, as well as the risks that come with it, is becoming an increasingly important challenge for governments (Taeihagh, 2021).

What is the definition of risk? Or, more particularly, what do policymakers mean when they speak about risks rather than harms? The current meaning of risk emphasizes the actuarial aspect of the concept: risk is something that must be quantified, consistently managed, and factored into the equation (A. Kaminski et al., 2020). Risk assessments can assist in determining whether AI systems require regulation, according to the severity of its possible impact and its probability of occurrence (Sibal, 2021). When it comes to AI technology, we must examine risks such as the expected impact and possibility of harm, the relevance and sensitivity of data usage, the application within a certain industry, the danger of non-compliance, and whether having a person in the loop mitigates risk to any extent (OECD, 2021a).

Risk regulation is comprised of both regulatory aims and regulatory mechanisms. In some ways, the aims are straightforward: to prevent, reduce, or mitigate severe dangers posed by complex systems or technology (M. E. Kaminski, in press). A risk-based approach to regulation entails using a systematized framework of risk classification to identify the type and degree of risk posed by the system (Ezeani, Koene, Kumar, Santiago, & Wright, 2021). Risk control is frequently, but not always, *ex ante*, systemic, and focused on aggregate consequences. It frequently tackles the architecture of a system and employs strategies to eliminate risk before it manifests as actual effects (M. E. Kaminski, in press). The goal of risk regulators is to analyze the benefits over the costs, and rate the various choices for identifying, assessing, and classifying risk in order to establish the suitable risk category and related regulatory requirements within the legal framework (De Cooman, 2022; Ezeani et al., 2021). When this cost-benefit analysis results in unsustainable risks, prudence must prevail, since even the most remote danger becomes intolerable. In the context of artificial intelligence, this would imply that not all AI systems are

regarded similarly under the law; legal requirements would differ based on the AI risk rating (De Cooman, 2022). Those in support believe that it is a method of making legal regulations more fair and balanced, as well as making better use of scarce regulatory resources (Ezeani et al., 2021). Such a gradation of risks is the core idea of the proposed European (AI) regulation, whose most distinguishing features is a “proportionate, risk-based approach” (Mökander, Axente, Casolari, & Floridi, 2022) based on an increasing ladder of risk corresponding to more stringent regulation. This risk-based approach is shared with two other European digital regulations: the Digital Services Act and the General Data Protection Regulation. However, they have a slight difference: while the goal of the GDPR and the DSA is to employ risk management techniques to better comply with the regulations, the proposed draft AI regulation’s risk assessment serves to determine whether a specific AI system should be regulated (Gellert, 2021). Internationally, a risk-based approach is also present in the Algorithmic Accountability Act of the United States, and in the Canadian Directive on Automated Decision-Making, hinting that it may set a standard on the international scene, especially with the entry into force of the draft AI act.

Risk-based approaches can be precautionary, or aim at mitigation, or entail post-market measures (M. E. Kaminski, in press) - or even display all of these three characteristics at once. Precautionary, or *ex ante*, regulation, can anticipate harms by evaluating and redressing harmful risk design. Instead of entailing a harm requirement, whereby systems are permitted insofar an individual does not demonstrate a negative impact, precautionary regulation can address harms on a collective and societal level (M. E. Kaminski, 2018). Examples of precautionary tactics include bans, sandboxing, and licensing (M. E. Kaminski, in press).

At the firm level, risk mitigation often means resolving the hazards identified during a risk assessment through system design and development. Risk assessment and mitigation frequently entail the assessment system to determine what risks it raises, the individuation and application of solutions apt for minimizing the risk, and subsequent testing to confirm that the procedures put in place were successful. This process ought to be iterated as an ongoing procedure assessing how a product interacts with users in real-life scenarios and whether specific incremental and long-term harms are present (M. E. Kaminski, in press).

When AI harms are classified as risks, governments must choose between prudence and risk management. Typically, risk regulation presumes that a technology will be deployed despite its risks. While certain elements of risk regulation may be helpful at mitigating particular types of harm, risk regulation as a legal mechanism obscures both certain types of harm and certain persons and communities afflicted by AI (M. E. Kaminski, in press). This is because assessing risks typically means discussing harms at the level of the collective (Boyd, 2012), with specific implications

for diversity and inclusion: individual differences are typically overlooked in the aggregate nature of risk. Acceptable risk is determined by taking into account the 'typical man' - the white, adult, heterosexual, abled, cisgender, man. Any minority deviating from this benchmark can suffer the consequences of a framework that makes them invisible. Moreover, risk management implies society-wide trade-offs, where, in a perfectly utilitarian fashion, even profound harm for one individual can be overlooked in the name of a corresponding societal benefit (M. E. Kaminski, in press). This makes risk-based approaches problematic when they deal with human rights issues.

The utilitarian ethics of risk-assessment, puts an emphasis on cost-benefit analysis and computability. This makes it so that harms that are clearly quantifiable often take precedents over more contentious harms (Boyd, 2012). Not all risks are quantifiable, (M. E. Kaminski, in press) especially those in connection to the enjoyment of human rights.

This quantitative risk-based method is beneficial in technical environments, where businesses assess their own operational risks. The EU approach, on the other hand, would require corporations to weigh operational risks against people's basic rights. But human rights are at their core not negotiable, and cannot be balanced with the interests of corporations, no matter the level of risk that was highlighted. A risk-based regulatory strategy, on its own, is insufficient to defend human rights (Hidvegi, Leufer, & Massé, 2021).

3.2 The global race to AI regulation

The progress in the development and implementation of national AI strategies and policies varies greatly from country to country. The EC-OECD database of national AI policies¹ includes the national AI strategies and related regulations of over 60 countries. Strategy and policy priorities include financing AI RD institutions and projects, addressing societal challenges, promoting AI uptake by business, fostering inclusive social dialogue, equipping the population with the skills for developing and using AI and fostering a fair labour market transition for workers (OECD, 2021a). The first national AI strategies appeared around 2017, with Canada, Finland, Japan, and the United Kingdom setting goals and allocating funds for AI development. In the following two years, it was the turn of Denmark, France, Germany, Korea, Russia and the United States, while Brazil, Bulgaria, Egypt, Hungary, Poland, and Spain announced their strategies between 2020 and 2021. Several other countries are in the midst of the consultation and development phase. (*ibid.*) All strategies share similar aims, such as supporting research and translating its findings into innovative applications for the public and private sectors. When it comes to contested issues

¹<https://www.oecd.ai/dashboards>

such as the socio-economic, ethical and legal ramifications of AI development, the OECD observed that “national initiatives reflect differences in national cultures, legal systems, country size and level of AI adoption” (OECD, 2019b). Other strategic efforts pursued globally are the establishment of dedicated bodies to oversee and coordinate the implementation of AI strategies, conducting impact assessment analyses, as well as setting up AI observatories operating at regional, national and supranational levels (*ibid.*).

The most influential framework for AI policy is the *G20 Global Framework* (G20, 2019), delineated during the Japanese Presidency in 2019. The year later, the G20 agreed to advance the G20 AI Principles in each member country (OECD, 2021a). The strategic importance of these principles comes from the institutional tenor of the G20, which is an international forum that includes Europe as a whole and 19 other countries, representing together 85% of global GDP, 75% of international trade and two-thirds of the world’s population. The G20 AI Principles are drawn from the OECD Recommendation of the Council on Artificial Intelligence (OECD, 2019d), that offers standards for the governance of AI and its ethical use. The OECD/G20 AI Principles have emerged from hundreds of trustworthy AI frameworks: they have been endorsed by over 50 national governments, gaining a prominent role in shaping their AI policies and guidelines (Center for AI and Digital Policy, 2017). Examples are the AI Ethics frameworks and guidelines published by Australia, Colombia and Hungary, as well as Belgium’s self-assessment tool for trustworthy AI, Scotland’s AI explainability framework and Japan’s guidelines for RD in AI (OECD, 2021a).

G20 countries are rapidly building trustworthy AI ecosystems by incorporating multiple G20 AI Principles at once into national agendas. International cooperation is one among the most endorsed principles, and yet AI policy discussions at high-level forums in the Global North have been marked by the marginalization or exclusion of voices from the Global South (OECD, 2019b). It is debatable whether some *global* initiatives can even be considered global at all: when the Government of France hosted the Global Forum on AI for Humanity in 2019, there were no representatives from African, Latin American, or Asian institutions other than Japan (Center for AI and Digital Policy, 2017).

This is reflected also in the concentration of National AI strategies, that demonstrate a strong North/South divide in global AI readiness (Oxford Insights, 2022). However, 2021 marked the adoption of Resolution 473 in Africa, (African Commission on Human and Peoples’ Rights, 2021) calling on State Parties to ensure that the development and use of AI is compatible with the principles of the African Charter and other regional and international human rights instruments (Center for AI and Digital Policy, 2017), to “uphold human dignity, privacy, equality, non-discrimination, inclusion, diversity, safety, fairness, transparency, accountability and economic development as underlying principles that guide the development and use

of AI, robotics and other new and emerging technologies.” (African Commission on Human and Peoples’ Rights, 2021)

A strong emphasis in many national AI strategies and policy initiatives is accorded to the aim of securing a leadership position in AI (OECD, 2019b). This issue has tremendous strategic importance as, according to the Russian President Vladimir Putin, “Whoever becomes the leader in [the AI] sphere will become the ruler of the world.” (Gigova, 2017)

Some examples of leadership ambitions expressed in national AI strategies come from Germany, that in its 2018 strategy aims at becoming a globally leading center for AI, and Korea, that in the national strategy published in 2019 expressed its efforts for becoming one of the leading three countries in AI worldwide (OECD, 2021a).

The United States and China are two of the leading players in AI development globally. Their interplay is sometimes characterized as a “race” for AI dominance, which is alarming given that the US and China are geopolitical competitors and military giants. Both countries have just recently established their national AI strategies: China in 2017 and the United States in 2019 (Hine & Floridi, 2022).

Some illuminating insights can be found in the frequency and sentiment analysis of AI policy documents from the United States performed by Hine and Floridi (2022). Their findings highlight an underlying competition with China, which is mentioned in several documents: three times in *AI, Automation and the Economy* (2017), six times in the National Security Commission on Artificial Intelligence’s report executive summary, and over 200 times in its accompanying *Full Report* (2021), where the rhetoric is explicitly competitive. (Hine & Floridi, 2022)

“[W]e must win the AI competition that is intensifying strategic competition with China. China’s plans, resources, and progress should concern all Americans. It is an AI peer in many areas and an AI leader in some applications. We take seriously China’s ambition to surpass the United States as the world’s AI leader within a decade.”

National Security Commission on Artificial Intelligence (2021)

The only national document that mentions the United States is the White Paper on AI Standardization, where they are referred to eight times; the tone of the document is less hawkish than NSCAI’s (2021) tirade, as the references to the United States are usually in the context of broader references to the international scene alongside the EU and Japan, or simply mentioning National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) as one institution among the many that are working on the development AI standards (Hine & Floridi, 2022). While the United States favors self-regulation, the European Union is about to position itself as a leader in setting

AI standards. AI law in the European Union tries to take into consideration the societal hazards posed by AI in specific sectors of activity and to mitigate these risks through a responsible and human-centered approach to AI (Castets-Renard, 2020). In AI Democratic Values Index, the first global survey to assess progress toward trustworthy AI, the US did not score well: AI policy process is opaque, and the U.S. lacks strong laws for data privacy (Center for AI and Digital Policy, 2017). China scored even lower due to its widespread use of facial recognition and social credit scoring, all of which are weaponized especially against minorities. Its practices are very far from globally accepted standards on human-centric AI (Center for AI and Digital Policy, 2017). Due to the USA's hands-off style to regulation, and the profound State ingerence in China, Europe will be the most likley winner of this regulatory race, as it is set to become the first global power to enact a comprehensive regulation on AI. It is also aided by the documented phenomenon of the *Brussels effect*, the regulatory power that the EU is capable of exerting indirectly outside of its border generating global compliance to its standard and progressively congruent regulation by foreign governments. All these elements will be explored in the next section, where I will trace the current and future perspectives of European governance of Artificial Intelligence.

3.3 Current regulatory frameworks in the EU and future perspectives

The widespread adoption of AI, and a desire to control the potentially harmful effects of use, prompted policy discussions about AI governance in the EU. (Cath, 2018) A clear priority was accorded to the mitigation of emerging ethical harms through hard and soft legislation (Roberts et al., 2021). In the *race to AI regulation* (Smuha, 2021b), Europe aims at leading the way in artificial intelligence by charting an “European third way” for AI development (Schmitt, 2022), a human-centric regulatory approach based on common European values, so that individuals and companies may have complete faith in the technology they use (Cyman, Gromova, & Juchnevicius, 2021). Fostering this “ecosystem of excellence and trust in AI” (Commission, 2020) implies reassuring European Union citizens about the protection of their rights and safety, as well as supporting entrepreneurial drive and interests by reducing legal ambiguity and market fragmentation at a European scale (Cyman et al., 2021). Higher investments in R&D, moreover, are crucial to counter the brain drain of top researchers and entrepreneurs towards the USA (De Bosschere, 2021).

AI has gained prominence on European political agendas since 2017, when political leaders acknowledged the potential of AI to improve political decision making in the Tallinn Declaration (van Noordt et al., 2020). So far, the main tenets of the European strategy (Commission, 2020; European Commission, Directorate-General for

Communications Networks, Content and Technology, 2018) have been to harmonize European efforts and legislation, to ensure an appropriate and ethical framework, to foster the skills to make the most of AI and automation at work, and to invest in Research & Development. The forerunner in AI policy in Europe was the European Commission, preceding most EU member states (Schmitt, 2022). The Commission Communication Artificial Intelligence for Europe (European Commission, Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology, 2018) outlines a human-centric strategy to technological development, which includes internal coordination and cross-border cooperation. This requires a careful preparation for the socio-economic changes that could result from AI adoption, whilst ensuring an appropriate ethical and legal framework for the development and deployment of AI solutions (Cyman et al., 2021; European Commission, Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology, 2018).

Concurrent with the publication of this strategy in April 2018, the Commission established the High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, which comprises 52 members who have contributed to the academic and industrial discussion on AI regulatory and governance issues on a global scale (Floridi, 2021; Schmitt, 2022). Their main contribution is the influential *Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI* (High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, 2019b), published in April 2019, whose contributions to the domain of Ethical AI were explored in Section 2.1. Since then, the Commission published a White Paper on AI (Commission, 2020) in February 2020, that acted as a preliminary step for a future legislative proposal aiming at regulating Artificial Intelligence at the European level (Schmitt, 2022).

The White Paper details mechanisms for coordinating European efforts to attain both an ‘ecosystem of excellence’ and an ‘ecosystem of trust’. The first goal is addressed by concentrating on the whole value chain, beginning with research and development, and providing suitable incentives to expedite the adoption of AI-based solutions, including small and medium-sized firms, for which private-public collaborations are encouraged. The ecosystem of trust describes the policy goal of providing citizens, businesses, and organizations with the confidence to make the most of Artificial Intelligence, both in terms of trustworthy design and legal certainty, which will be ensured through compliance with EU rules, particularly those protecting fundamental rights in general, and consumer rights in particular (Cyman et al., 2021). The White Paper also notes that AI should serve society as well as promoting human well-being, which has primary consideration. Both society and individuals can benefit from the AI-enabled achievement of UN Sustainable Development Goals, the digital development of European business (Roberts et al., 2021).

The Commission communication, Ethical Guidelines and White Paper are all examples of soft law: they are non-binding, therefore they do not give rise to specific legal obligations. The legally binding provisions for AI in EU are part of a

fragmented framework, where each law regulates specific aspects of AI systems. This multi-regime framework for AI is governed both by EU primary and secondary law, with the first referring to the Charter of Fundamental Rights and the Treaties of the European Union; secondary law refers to a plethora of legislation relating to consumer rights, privacy rights, anti-discrimination provisions, security and liability laws. The most important example of EU secondary law legislating AI is the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which I will examine shortly. Other governance frameworks for AI in the EU consist of U.N. Human Rights treaties, the Council of Europe conventions, and EU Member state laws, as well as domain-specific rules regulating specific applications of intelligent systems, such as the Medical Device Regulation for the healthcare domain (Cyman et al., 2021). The Charter of Fundamental Rights (European Commission, 2000a) has also been invoked in court cases concerning the harms provoked by specific AI applications, particularly Artt. 7 and 8, which are respectively dedicated the *Respect for private and family life* (including the privacy of communications) and the *Protection of personal data*, which should be processed processed fairly, only for specified purposes and on the basis of the concerned person’s consent or some other legitimate basis laid down by law, introducing a right of access and rectification as well as compliance control by an independent authority. Similarly relevant is Article 16 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union, where is claimed that “Everyone has the right to the protection of personal data concerning them.” (European Commission, 2000b)

On 5 July 2022, the European Parliament approved two new legal instruments that play a role to ensure that algorithms are safe and transparent: the Digital Services Act and the Digital Market Act. These acts create new obligations and responsibilities for online platforms in terms of their access and processing of data, to ensure that recommendation algorithms are transparent and companies are held accountable for their decisions. while promoting fair competition and fostering innovation (OECD, 2021a). Platforms and search engines totaling more than 45 million European monthly users should respect several obligations for risk management: they should undergo compulsory external audits, prevent to their best knowledge the diffusion of illegal content and content that may affect fundamental rights, allow users to block profiling-based recommendations, share their data with authorities when requested and cooperate in emergency response. Since both Act are essentially customer protection and competition legislation aimed at Big Tech (defined as *gatekeepers* in the DMA) and tech platforms such as social media, e-commerce, hosting platforms, app stores and other intermediaries offering for-profit remote services, these are outside the scope of this thesis. I will therefore focus on the General data Protection Regulation and the draft AI Regulation.

A comprehensive approach to AI regulation is in development: in April 2021, the

European Commission published a draft of its forthcoming Artificial Intelligence Act, or, more verbosely, the *Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council Laying Down Harmonised Rules on Artificial Intelligence*. This regulation is highly anticipated not only within the EU, but also internationally: this is due to the *Brussels effect* (Bradford, 2020; Cervi, 2022). This effect described the EU's unilateral power of imposing its regulations to the global marketplace. The Brussels effect is not necessarily purposeful, as it can result from a variety of independent market factors rather than the EU's explicit attempts to export its regulations. Since the European market has strong demand AI-based products that caters to multinational firms, the self-interest of multinational corporations leads them to comply with the rather strict EU regulations, and export their new EU-compliant products internationally. When multinational firms autonomously respond to EU legislation by adjusting their global conduct in compliance to EU rules, it is a *de facto* Brussels effect. When a foreign government adopts a regulation inspired by EU rules, it is a *de iure* Brussels effect. Therefore, the Brussels effect is not necessarily purposeful, as it can result from a variety of independent market factors rather than the EU's explicit attempts to export its regulations (Bradford, 2020). The most influential EU regulation to date is the GDPR, whose extensive reach led to the global diffusion of data protection laws (Bradford, 2020; Schmitt, 2022). As the EU is set to become the world's first major jurisdiction to establish a binding legal framework for AI, its future enforcement will undoubtedly have far-reaching consequences well beyond its borders (Schmitt, 2022). Ensuring that it paves the way to a human-centric and trustworthy future for AI is a matter of global importance.

3.3.1 General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

The European General Data Protection Regulation aims at creating a harmonized data protection framework across of all EU countries, where citizens are back in control of their personal data, irrespective of geographical location. They are empowered with new rights, such as right to be informed about the collection and use of their personal data (Art. 15); right to rectification of incorrect personal data concerning them (Art. 16); right to erasure, or *right to be forgotten* (Art. 17); right to restriction of processing (Art. 18); right to data portability (Art. 20); right to object to the processing of their data (Art. 21); and, importantly for the issue of Automated Decision-Making, the right not to be subject to a decision based exclusively on automatic processing, including profiling (Art. 22), and in that case the right to contest the decision and obtain human intervention (Art. 22(3)). The Regulation entered into force on May 2016, replacing the Data Protection Directive 95/46/EC; two years later, in May 2018, it became applicable to all EU member states, and violations of its provisions have since then been sanctioned. It comprises of ninety-nine articles: no matter how detailed these articles can be, they still leave out grey

areas that are up to interpretation and may need to be updated when applied in new contexts, as is the case with the fast-paced development of new technology (Floridi, 2018). While, unlike the past Data Protection Directive, the GDPR does include some Internet-related terms, it does not include neither the term ‘artificial intelligence’, nor any related concepts: even ‘big data’ and ‘machine learning’, which are characterized respectively by the collection and use of humanly inconceivable amounts of data, are absent (Sartor & Lagioia, 2020). Significant exceptions are ‘automated decision-making’ and ‘profiling’, which is governed by Article 22 and is highly relevant for this thesis as it can refer to a wide range of AI systems that process personal data (M. E. Kaminski & Malgieri, 2020). The GDPR provides some key definitions for concepts that are widely discussed in the AI domain. First of all, following Art. 4(2), data processing entails “any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or on sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction.” (European Commission, 2016) Personal data, whose use in some forms of Automated Decision-Making is contentious, is defined in article 4(1) as “any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (‘data subject’); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, from that data” (European Commission, 2016). Their processing requires a lawful basis (art. 6), such as consent, legitimate interests, performance of a contract or a task carried out in the public interest, compliance with a legal obligation, protection of the vital interests. Sensitive data, or, more precisely, *special categories of personal data*, are subject to more intense protections: this kind of data refers to highly personal characteristics pertaining to the private life of the individual and that, if revealed, could lead to discrimination. A few examples are data revealing a person’s ethnic origin, religious affiliation, genetic and biometric data, health status and sexual orientation. Instead, anonymised data (i.e. data that can no longer identify a specific person) are instead outside of the scope of the Regulation. Profiling is addressed in several Articles and Recitals, such as the definition present in Art. 4(4) (“[A]ny form of automated processing of personal data consisting of the use of personal data to evaluate certain personal aspects relating to a natural person, in particular to analyse or predict aspects concerning that natural person’s performance at work, economic situation, health, personal preferences, interests, reliability, behaviour, location or movements.”), but it is also mentioned and regulated in Recital 72 (“Profiling is subject to the rules of this Regulation governing the processing of personal data, such as the legal grounds for processing (Article 6) or data protection principles (Article 5)”), Recital 60 (“Furthermore, the data subject shall be informed of the existence of profiling and the consequences of such

profiling”), Recital 63, with the right to be informed on the consequences of profiling, and Recital 70, with the right to object to profiling (European Commission, 2016). Automated Decision-Making is referred to in Article 22, which prohibits “decision-making based solely on automated processing” (European Commission, 2016), Article 15, which entails the right of access to information about the existence of “solely” Automated Decision-Making, and Recital 71, that delineates certain exemptions to this prohibition (European Commission, 2016). To aid legislators in understanding the scope, meaning, and applicability of the articles in new contexts, such as Artificial Intelligence, the GDPR is supported by 173 Recitals that, although not legally binding, influence *de facto* the application of the Regulation. In fact, they are used by the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU) and the European Data Protection Board (EDPB), when either investigating or deliberating over compliance with the GDPR. Novel applications of data processing are also to be interpreted under the light of the main principles infused in the Regulation, such as lawfulness, fairness, transparency, purpose limitation, data minimisation and storage limitation, and data accuracy. The Regulation aims at establishing a tutelary, human-centered and market-compatible data governance framework, as expressed in its first article:

1(1) “This Regulation lays down rules relating to the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and rules relating to the free movement of personal data.”

1(2) “This Regulation protects fundamental rights and freedoms of natural persons and in particular their right to the protection of personal data”

1(3) “The free movement of personal data within the Union shall be neither restricted nor prohibited for reasons connected with the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data”

(European Commission, 2016)

As a consequence, it appears that an explicit mention of GDPR compliance can have a significant positive effect on perceived trustworthiness (Paul, Scheibe, & Nilakanta, 2020).

The Regulation applies equally to all commercial and non-commercial actors that operate in the EU, creating business certainty through a simplified regulatory environment. Foreign and domestic actors alike are required to ensure and document data protection by design and by default, clarifying accountability issues. The main innovations brought by the entry into force of the GDPR are a new set of individual rights related to data protection and the requirement of explicit consent for data processing, and the introduction of sanctions in case these are violated.

Other novelties play a key role in the domain of data security, such as compulsory breach notifications (i.e. the obligation to report a data breach within 72 hours) and the appointment of a Data Protection Officer for public organisations, or private organisations processing special categories of data. These introductions have been influential, and the GDPR has since become the prime regulation for Information and Communication Technology (Gellert, 2021), resulting in a *de facto* Brussels Effect. As noted by Siegmann & Anderljung in a recent study (2022), “58% of popular websites offer US subjects both the right to erasure (GDPR Article 17) and the right to portability (GDPR Article 20)”, and “six countries, including Japan, Argentina, and New Zealand, have already adopted similar rules”, therefore showing a *de iure* Brussels Effect.

Risk-based approach

Aside from focusing on individual rights, a fundamental feature of the GDPR is its risk-based approach, which relies on risk analysis and mitigation (M. E. Kaminski, in press) called *impact assessment*, which aims to protect “the rights and freedoms of natural persons” (European Commission, 2016) by forecasting “possible consequences of an initiative on relevant societal concerns” (Zuiderveen Borgesius et al., 2018), analyzing if a certain initiative “can present dangers to these concerns, with a view to supporting informed decision-making whether to deploy this initiative and under what conditions, ultimately constituting a means to protect these concerns.” (Zuiderveen Borgesius et al., 2018) It establishes record-keeping requirements according to the level of risk posed by the system, but provides exceptions for smaller businesses, unless their processing raises certain risks. By requiring Data Protection Impact Assessments to be conducted by data controllers, this risk-based approach strives to provide a societal foundation for better privacy policies and design (Edwards & Veale, 2017). Article 35 delineates the circumstances that make a DPIA necessary:

“Where a type of processing in particular using new technologies, and taking into account the nature, scope, context and purposes of the processing, is likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons, the controller shall, prior to the processing, carry out an assessment of the impact of the envisaged processing operations on the protection of personal data.”

(European Commission, 2016)

This means that a DPIA is required for many AI systems that make decisions that affect data subjects, and during the assessment the risk of discrimination must be thoroughly considered (Zuiderveen Borgesius et al., 2018). Another basis for the

necessity of risk assessment is found in Art. 22, which states that suitable measures are required to protect the rights of the data subject. This is also referred to as a *suitable safeguards* requirement. According to the GDPR Guidelines on Automated Individual Decision-Making and Profiling, suitable safeguards include risk mitigation tools that can be both technical and regulatory in nature. The Guidelines also suggest that businesses must assess AI risk, implement risk-mitigation strategies, and self-assess or work as a sector to determine the best way to do so. Risk mitigation should employ expert boards, internal audits and third-party auditing, as well as the development of new AI assessment systems. Rather than a one-time ex ante event, these assessments are envisioned as an iterative process, with the data controller assessing risks, mitigating risks, documenting and monitoring review, and then re-engaging in the process on a periodical basis. While companies undertake their own evaluations, these assessments are mostly co-regulatory: in fact, a subset of assessments requires pre-approval by regulators. While stakeholders should be consulted, but this might be done accomplished by a survey (A. Kaminski et al., 2020). The GDPR's impact assessments do not necessarily have to be made public, although this is strongly encouraged. Another preventive measure is the requirement of Privacy by Design and Privacy by Default in Art. 25, that was highlighted by the EDPB chair as a key instrument against the deployment and diffusion of unfair algorithms (Jelinek, 1975). These stringent provisions, if properly implemented, do not stifle the development of AI systems, albeit they may involve some additional expenditures (Sartor & Lagioia, 2020).

Applicability to AI

Many fundamental issues in AI, both practical and ethical, concern data protection (Gwagwa et al., 2020). Since a European Artificial Intelligence Regulation is still on the works, lawyers and businessmen alike have turned to the GDPR to seek legal guidance for the still unregulated domain of AI. As illustrated by European Parliament Think Tank in their study *The Impact of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) on Artificial Intelligence* (2020), "The GDPR generally provides meaningful indications for data protection in the context of AI applications." According to the European Data Protection Board, the GDPR is a "robust legal framework" capable of protecting citizens from unfair algorithms (Jelinek, 1975) as it is considered AI itself, however, challenges several GDPR provisions by enabling unforeseen ways of personal data processing (Sartor & Lagioia, 2020). The capabilities of AI and its data maximization presumption, together with the high economical value allocated to big data collecting, offer incentives for a increasing data collection and processing, even unlawfully (Jelinek, 1975). This clearly contradicts the traditional principles of data protection of purpose limitation and the limitation on automated decisions (Sartor & Lagioia, 2020). In particular, the GDPR is con-

sidered the first guarantee against unfair automated decisions and it is lauded for empowering the data subject with the a right to explanation (Ulnicane et al., 2021) as Artt. 22 and 15(h), together with Recital 71, are frequently recognized as attractive avenues for providing algorithmic remedies (Edwards & Veale, 2017). Article 15, in particular, is referred to as the 'right of access by the data subject' and is applicable to the AI domains of automated decision-making and profiling.

“The data subject shall have the right to obtain from the controller confirmation as to whether or not personal data concerning him or her are being processed, and, where that is the case, access to the personal data and the following information:

(...)

h) the existence of automated decision-making, including profiling, referred to in Article 22(1) and (4) and, at least in those cases, meaningful information about the logic involved, as well as the significance and the envisaged consequences of such processing for the data subject.”

(European Commission, 2016)

This is complemented by the 'right to object' enshrined in Article 22:

“The data subject shall have the right not to be subject to a decision based solely on automated processing, including profiling, which produces legal effects concerning him or her or similarly significantly affects him or her”

(European Commission, 2016)

However, some restrictions to these rights are present, as listed by Edwards and Veale (2017): “carve-outs for intellectual property (IP) protection and trade secrets; restriction of application to decisions that are 'solely' made by automated systems; restriction to decisions that produce 'legal' or similarly "significant" effects; the timing of such a remedy in relation to the decision being made; the authorisation of stronger aspects of these remedies by non-binding recitals rather than the GDPR's main text, leading to substantial legal uncertainty; and the practical difficulty in knowing when or how decisions are being made, particularly in relation to 'smart' environments.”

Limitations

It is unclear whether the 'right to access' of Article 15 can be interpreted as a comprehensive right of explanation of the decision, and whether it genuinely provides

a viable safeguard against the risks of automated decision-making: while the subject should be automated regarding automated decision-making, it does not appear that this encompasses the justification for every particular choice (Coeckelbergh, 2020). Article 15 is further weakened by the recent advances in complex and non-linear AI models, whose ‘black box’ nature makes it difficult to provide meaningful explanations (A. Wong, 2021). The access rights also seem to come after the processing: whether an ex-post customized knowledge about individual judgment can be ‘meaningful’ is debatable (Edwards & Veale, 2017). The restrictive provisions of the GDPR are unlikely to redress the harms of algorithmic opacity (Edwards & Veale, 2017).

Another issue is that of ‘solely automated’ Automated Decision-Making, that is prohibited under Article 22. This does not restrict ‘semi-automated’ decision-making, despite it being infamously present in many ‘algorithmic war stories’ (Edwards & Veale, 2017) such as the recidivism risk assessment software COMPAS (more on this matter in Section 4.4.1). Following Zuiderveen, Borgesius et al. (2018), “when discussing discrimination, many risks are similar for fully and partly automated decisions.” Human involvement can become ‘no involvement’ due to automation bias and algorithmic complacency, as explored in Section 1.3. Some exceptions are present for fully automated decision-making as well: following Article 22(2), the performance of a contract, explicit consent or specific legislation from the Member state can be invoked for the lawful automated processing of personal data. Public administration can also evoke Article 6(1)(e), the ‘Performance of a task carried out in the public interest’, by stating that automated data processing “is necessary for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority vested in the controller.” (European Commission, 2016) These broad-based exemptions can benefit public authorities, who can undertake automated decision-making with no hindrance by invoking the public interest exemption and adopting specific national legislation (Kang, 2020). This last issue threatens the uniform application of the Regulation in Europe. (Castets-Renard, 2020)

Finally, the GDPR presents some weaknesses in its risk approach, that focuses primarily on human rights. Human rights violations are highly contested and difficult to quantify (M. E. Kaminski, in press). The terminology of the Regulation does not help, as it does not clearly specify the scope of risk mitigation - i.e., exactly what risks should be addressed and minimized. Recital 71 (on profiling) and 75 (on the risks to the rights and freedoms of natural persons) provide some non-exhaustive guidance on this matter, mainly pointing out to inaccuracy and discrimination issues, while companies bear the burden of performing risk analysis for risks that have not yet been identified in any specificity. In this grey area, the possibility of corporate capture (Whittaker, 2021) creeps in (M. E. Kaminski, in press).

In conclusion, the GDPR allows for the creation of AI and big data solutions

that balance data protection with other societal and economic goals, but it gives no clear direction on how to do so. Its ambiguity and open-endedness can lead to uncertainties and costs, as well as sub-optimal balances between competing interests. The novelties of these technologies, their complexity and their social impacts point to the necessity of a specific regulatory framework for AI (Sartor & Lagioia, 2020). In the following section, I will discuss the Draft AI Regulation, Europe’s world-first attempt to regulate Artificial Intelligence.

3.3.2 Draft AI Regulation

The draft AI Regulation (or AI Act) is the European Union’s world-first attempt at regulating the fluid world of AI, that entails both immense economic advantages and ethical, legal and societal risks that ought to be regulated. The regulatory power of the EU known as *Brussels effect*, combined with a first-mover advantage, is likely to make this future legislation the most influential on a global level, helping shape global norms and standards according to trustworthy AI requirements that are in line with the European Union’s values and interests (European Commission, 2021a). It is therefore highly anticipated and defined as a matter “of global importance.” (Siegmann & Anderljung, 2022)

The AIA was published in April 2021 and it is awaiting being enshrined into law once the negotiations between the Council and the European Parliament lead to an agreement on a common text. The system is based at its core on European values and fundamental rights, with its ethical approach deriving from the European Ethics Guidelines proposed by the independent high-level expert group on AI set up by the European Commission (High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, 2019b).

The Act aims to formalize the high-level requirements of the EU’s trustworthy AI paradigm, which demands AI to be legally, morally, and technically sound while also respecting democratic principles, human rights, and the rule of law (Kop, 2021). This proposal was foreshadowed by the European Commission’s White Paper on AI, which called for a risk-based regulatory framework to minimize potential material and immaterial harms (De Cooman, 2022), and outlined policy options for achieving the double goal of both promoting AI adoption and addressing the risks associated with certain uses of such technology.

The draft AI regulation aspires to create a trust ecosystem by incorporating the ideas of trustworthy AI into a human-centric legal framework. This aspiration is connected to the twin goals of encouraging the use of AI systems and tackling the issues connected with such technology (Mökander, Axente, et al., 2022). It contributes to the Union’s goal of being a global leader in the development of safe, trustworthy, and ethical artificial intelligence (European Commission, 2021a). When AI is trustworthy, individuals have the confidence they need to employ AI-based solutions in their

job and daily lives, incentivizing businesses to build new, ethically compliant technologies. Trustworthy AI would be a force for good in society, ultimately improving human well-being.

Given these assumptions, it could feel counter-intuitive to discover that the legal basis for the AI Act is not human rights regulations, nor anti-discrimination law, data protection, or the like. It is instead based on Article 114 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (European Commission, 2000b), which concerns the adoption of measures towards 'the establishment and functioning of the internal market'. In fact, according to Smuha (2021a), the proposal has actually a dual aim: "safeguarding individuals' fundamental rights against AI's adverse effects, as well as harmonising member states' rules to eliminate potential obstacles to trade on the internal market." By setting harmonized rules on the development, use, and placement of AI systems, this proposal constitutes a core part of the EU digital single market strategy: it ensures that the AI systems entering or developed in the EU market are safe to use and resonate with European values.

The aims of this proposal can be best achieved by ensuring legal certainty at the Union level, in order to prevent a fragmentation of the Single Market different, and perhaps contradicting, national frameworks. This in turn could hamper the free circulation of AI-related goods (European Commission, 2021a). Therefore, a common approach to AI is presented, characterized by its high level of proportionality that only sets out bare minimum requirements to tackle the risks associated with AI. This ensures that the research and commercialization of AI is not too constrained, and does not entail unsustainable costs.

The European Commission, aiming at making this Regulation *future-proof*, did not define *Artificial Intelligence* at large, choosing instead to define *AI systems*. This reflects the technological neutrality principle already experimented with the GDPR, and provides leeway for the regulation of future and unforeseen AI system. The definition follows a hybrid approach: at Article 3 it provides a wide and vague definition, inspired by the one put forward by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development.²

“[A]rtificial intelligence system’ (AI system) means software that is developed with one or more of the techniques and approaches listed in Annex I and can, for a given set of human-defined objectives, generate outputs such as content, predictions, recommendations, or decisions

²“An AI system is a machine-based system that is capable of influencing the environment by producing an output (predictions, recommendations or decisions) for a given set of objectives. It uses machine and/or human-based data and inputs to (i) perceive real and/or virtual environments; (ii) abstract these perceptions into models through analysis in an automated manner (e.g., with machine learning), or manually; and (iii) use model inference to formulate options for outcomes. AI systems are designed to operate with varying levels of autonomy.” (OECD AI Policy Observatory, 2019)

influencing the environments they interact with.”

European Commission (2021b)

Annex I complements this article by listing all AI techniques and approaches that are in the scope of the legislation.³ This ensures a sufficient level of legal certainty, while ensuring flexibility by allowing for future adaptations by the Commission, as envisaged by Article 4.⁴

While the draft definition has been criticized for its broadness, which can create uncertainty and high costs for developers of AI systems, it should be highlighted that deploying a system with characteristics such as those described in the Regulation does not imply they will necessarily be subject to legal obligations, which will only concern systems posing high levels of risk. The most discussed example was that of Bayesian systems: when they are used as spam filters, no legal obligations arise; it is a very different case when systems relying on Bayesian statistics will be used to determine the treatment of patients (Gaumond, 2021).

The European Artificial Intelligence Board (EAIB) will monitor the implementation of this Regulation, which will be supported by national supervisors at the Member State level, similar to the GDPR’s oversight mechanism. Fines for infractions can reach 6% of worldwide turnover, or 30 million euros for private firms. Notably, the EAIB is not conceived as an autonomous body with legal personality; rather, it is considered as a coordinating organization, led by the Commission, where representatives from Member States and the Commission assemble to promote the successful implementation of the AI Act (Mökander, Axente, et al., 2022). Their supervisory function may draw from current structures, such as conformity assessment bodies or market monitoring, but it would necessitate enough technology competence as well as human and financial resources (European Commission, 2021a).

To support innovation, *regulatory sandboxes* have been designed to ensure that research is not stifled, and startups as well as small and medium enterprises have a reduced regulatory burden.

In line with recent EU legislation on digital issues (GDPR, Digital Markets Act, Digital Services Act), the Draft AI Regulation is at its core a risk-based regulation,

³“Machine learning approaches, including supervised, unsupervised and reinforcement learning, using a wide variety of methods, including deep learning; Logic- and knowledge-based approaches, including knowledge representation, inductive (logic) programming, knowledge bases, inference and deductive engines, (symbolic) reasoning and expert systems; Statistical approaches, Bayesian estimation, search and optimization methods.” (European Commission, 2021b)

⁴“The Commission is empowered to adopt delegated acts in accordance with Article 73 to amend the list of techniques and approaches listed in Annex I, in order to update that list to market and technological developments on the basis of characteristics that are similar to the techniques and approaches listed therein.” European Commission (2021b)

combining both macro-level risk regulation that tiers activities and firms by level of risk, and micro-level risk regulation that relies on impact assessments and post-market monitoring for harms M. E. Kaminski (in press). Following Gellert (2021), the word ‘risk’ is present a total of 344 times in the AIA. However, the concept of risk itself is not explicitly defined” (De Cooman, 2022). A definition can be deduced from Recital 32, dedicated to ‘high-risk’ AI systems:

“It is appropriate to classify them as high-risk if, in the light of their intended purpose, they pose a high risk of harm to the health and safety or the fundamental rights of persons, taking into account both the severity of the possible harm and its probability of occurrence and they are used in a number of specifically pre-defined areas specified in the Regulation.”

European Commission (2021b)

Therefore, the definition of risk is based on individual harm and individual rights. The protection of rights and the prevention of harms is tackled through rules that are proportionate and effective (Gellert, 2021), without unwarranted trade restrictions (European Commission, 2021a).

The main peculiarity of the AI Act’s approach to risk is its *pyramid of risk* that differentiates between AI systems that entail minimal, limited, high or unacceptable risks, each one subject to more stringent requirements the higher the level of risk they entail. Among the foreseen measures according to the level of risk we find precautionary bans, or risk assessments and post-market measures, or voluntary adoption of self-regulation principles (M. E. Kaminski, in press). Unacceptable risks are prohibited by default, as they are deemed to be in contrast with European values (Title II, Article 5). Stringent requirements apply to high-risk systems, such as transparency and human oversight, and a mandatory CE-marking procedure to enter the EU market. Systems that entail specific risks, such as those that interact with humans (i.e. chatbots) are subject to transparency requirements. Low risk systems are encouraged to adhere to voluntary ethical and technical requirements. The proposed AI Act would introduce new standards and conformity assessment requirements for “high-risk” AI products sold in the EU, estimated at 5–15% of the EU AI market (Siegmann & Anderljung, 2022). Innovation is safeguarded by the implementation of AI regulatory sandboxes that facilitate the development and testing of innovative AI systems under strict regulatory oversight.

Examples of systems that pose unacceptable risks are social scoring performed by public authorities, dark-pattern AI, manipulation, exploitation of children or mentally challenged persons, and real-time biometric identification systems. The use of RBI has specific exceptions, such as searching “for victims of crime”, in case of “threat to life or physical integrity or of terrorism” (European Commission, 2021b).

In this case, an “ex-ante authorisation by a judicial authority or independent administrative body” is required. However, real-time and ex-post Remote Biometric Identification systems can be put on the market, provided they undergo an “ex-ante third-party conformity assessment”, they comply with “enhanced logging requirements” and existing data protection rules (*ibid.*).

A step lower in the pyramid of risk, we find high risk systems. These systems are permitted on the EU market insofar they comply with specific trustworthiness requirements and they undergo an ex-ante conformity assessment. A system can be classified as high-risk not only because of its function, but also for its specific purpose and modalities of use (European Commission, 2021a). Following Chapter 1 of Title III, there are two types of high-risk systems: the first type indicates the safety components of regulated products, like medical devices and machinery. These ought to undergo a third-party assessment according to the relevant sectoral legislation. The second type indicated certain stand-alone AI systems that are deployed in high risk fields: critical infrastructures, education or vocational training, safety components of products, employment, essential services - both private and public, law enforcement, border control management, administration of justice and democratic processes, and surveillance systems (European Commission, 2021b).

In Chapter 2 are presented the data and data governance requirements that high-risk AI systems ought to comply with, including “documentation and recording keeping, transparency and provision of information to users, human oversight, robustness, accuracy and security.” (European Commission, 2021a)

The requirements for High-risk AI are to use high-quality data for training, validation and testing. This data should be relevant, representative, accurate, complete and free of errors. These requirements are unrealistic in practice: recognizing that, datasets are only required to meet these standards *sufficiently*, according to the system’s intended purpose. Other data governance requirements are to “establish documentation and design logging features” to allow “traceability and auditability”, to “ensure an “appropriate... degree of transparency and provide users with information on how to use the system” and human oversight, “built into the system” or “to be implemented by users”. Finally, they should “ensure robustness, accuracy and cybersecurity” (European Commission, 2021b). The overarching aim is to “establish and implement” a comprehensive “risk management process” whose characteristics are delineated in Article 9(2):

“The risk management system shall consist of a continuous iterative process run throughout the entire lifecycle of a high-risk AI system, requiring regular systematic updating. It shall comprise the following steps: (a) identification and analysis of the known and foreseeable risks associated with each high-risk AI system; (b) estimation and evaluation of the risks that may emerge when the high-risk AI system is used in ac-

cordance with its intended purpose and under conditions of reasonably foreseeable misuse; (c) evaluation of other possibly arising risks based on the analysis of data gathered from the post-market monitoring system referred to in Article 61; (d) adoption of suitable risk management measures in accordance with the provisions of the following paragraphs.”

European Commission (2021b)

The purpose of this risk management system is the minimisation of risk associated with the AI system, until the likelihood and extent of harm is deemed acceptable. This minimisation of risk is achieved through design solutions and adequate development. In case risks cannot be eliminated, suitable monitoring and mitigation measures should be in place, and users should be trained.

The proposal deserves praise for establishing a framework for public supervision of high-risk AI uses (Smuha, 2021a). The proposal closes a significant gap in protection, by moving the duty of compliance from individuals to independent national regulatory agencies, for example through the inclusion of bans and ex ante requirements for high-risk AI systems, the references made to independent audits, and the prospect of substantial. Furthermore, the European Commission will build a publicly accessible EU database of stand-alone high-risk AI systems, which will boost public transparency (*ibid.*).

Concerning transparency mechanisms, the AI Act only contains a few explicit references to auditing, most of which are found in the annexes. However, it has been received as a proposal to create a Europe-wide ecosystem for AI auditing (Mökan-der, Axente, et al., 2022). This is especially true if we define auditing broadly, as structured processes through which an entity’s current or previous behavior is examined for adherence with pertinent principles, rules, legislation, or norms (*ibid.*) As such, auditing covers several enforcement mechanisms envisaged by the AI Act, such as conformity assessments (Article 43) that high-risk AI systems must undergo, and post-market monitoring plans (Article 61) through which providers must continuously document and analyze the performance and compliance of high-risk AI systems for its whole life cycle (*ibid.*)

Following this short oversight on the basics of the proposed AI Act, I will conclude by exposing some of its limitations.

The risk-based approach, far from being ‘clearly defined’, leaves question unanswered on basic issues like its aim, logic and boundaries, indicating that the proposed risk-based approach may not be as rigorous as it appears (Gellert, 2021). Its scope, rather than managing and minimising AI risks at large (an arduous task due to the already-mentioned *Collindrige’s dilemma*), could actually be that of determining which AI systems should actually be regulated, as an antidote for the potential for

over-broad regulation of AI systems entailed by the vague and extensive definition of AI provided by the proposal (Gellert, 2021).

The EU, by providing a world-first framework on AI, aims at providing sufficient legal certainty to reduce the regulatory costs of operating AI systems in the Union. It appears, however, that at the present stage the AI could entail some heavy costs. (Siegmann & Anderljung, 2022) Through an impact assessment on the proposed regulation, (CEPS, Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology (European Commission), ICF, Wavestone, 2021) the Commission estimated that the AI Act could entail at most rise of 6-10% in regulatory costs for investments in developing high-risk AI systems. These costs are the sum of the foreseen expenditures for meeting the requirements (compliance costs) and to provide adequate documentation of compliance (verification costs). These estimates are probably overstated, as they assume that no requirements are complied with by the system in question to begin with. Still, any rise in regulatory cost suggests that prices for EU products could rise by the same amount, possibly lowering the competitiveness of domestic AI systems compared to non-EU competitors (Siegmann & Anderljung, 2022). The Commission's estimates are called into question also by the study it commissioned before the draft AI Act was released, where regulatory costs were shown to possibly increase up to 17% of the high-risk systems' total costs of development. (*ibid.*)

The most problematic limitation of the proposed AIA is its individual-based conception of harm, following its definition of high-risk AI systems as posing "significant risks to the health and safety or fundamental rights of persons." (European Commission, 2021b) The contentiousness of the individual harm requirement was already exposed in Section 3, following the arguments of Van der Sloot (2017) that refer to the difficulty in understanding the functioning and evaluating the fairness of decisions of black-box algorithms. This preserves the status quo even in case of manipulative AI systems, which can thrive unchallenged as long as someone can demonstrate direct harm. Moreover, in case of an AI system that with adverse societal consequences, those who wish to challenge it will still need to prove individual harm, and civil society organization as well as citizens are not granted the right of filing a complaint in case of suspected non-compliance of a system. The role of society is marginalized in favor of national authorities (Smuha, 2021a). The issue of societal risk is not tackled in the compulsory risk assessments, which prove inadequate due to their testing the system *in labo*, isolated from its context of use, rather than *in vivo*, where possible incremental and long-term negative consequences can be appreciated (*ibid.*). Surprisingly, to the individual-based conception of harm does not follow any granting of specific individual rights for those impacted by the system. Following M. E. Kaminski (in press), "Its focus is not on the individual impacted 'data subject,' nor on impacted communities or neighborhoods. Instead,

its focus is on the development and use of AI.” (M. E. Kaminski, in press)

The draft AI act may also be limited in its principal aim, that of market harmonization. Risk of fragmentation is present in the provisions for national-level enforcement, delegating a substantial amount of power to national supervisory authorities. These could apply different protection standards due to the lack of uniform implementation standards of proposed requirements such as human oversight, or they could even lack sufficient resources to satisfactorily fulfil their tasks. As a consequence, different protection levels could be accorded to European citizens according to their location (Smuha, 2021a).

3.4 Industry self-regulation

Out of the 160 sets of AI ethical principles and guideline papers collected by AlgorithmWatch in 2020,⁵ the bulk of binding agreements and voluntary pledges were presented by the business sector. This is hardly unexpected given the importance of corporations in AI research, development, and deployment: in 2018, corporate-affiliated researchers published more AI research papers than academics in the United States (Cihon, Schuett, & Baum, 2021).

This can be read as a movement for self-regulation and the construction of a distinct Silicon Valley corporate narrative according to which self-regulation is the best approach to ensure technological innovation and its beneficial influence on economic growth. This liberal doctrine of free market is generally well-received in the United States, which is a champion in soft-law approaches and self-regulation for AI (Castets-Renard, 2020).

These soft-law methods to AI governance, i.e. non-binding standards, are often ineffective. The voluntary character of self-regulation projects cannot guarantee that the defined principles will always be followed, especially as they are not necessarily subject to standardized enforcement standards (Taeihagh, 2021). Despite this, or perhaps exactly for this reason, industry bodies have released voluntary standards, guidelines, and codes of conduct. Industry self-regulation has been the main strategy to respond to AI-enabled technical and ethical transformations at the global level (Floridi, 2021; Ulicane et al., 2021), with companies like Google, Microsoft, and IBM publishing their own ethical principles for AI.

For example, Google endorses the principles of “providing social benefit, avoiding creating or reinforcing unfair bias, enforcing safety, maintaining accountability, maintaining privacy design, promoting scientific excellence, and limiting potentially harmful or abusive applications such as weapons or technologies that violate principles of international law and human rights”. (Coeckelbergh, 2020) Similarly, Microsoft promotes *AI for Good* and endorses the principles of fairness, reliability and

⁵<https://inventory.algorithmwatch.org/>

safety, privacy and security, inclusiveness, transparency, and accountability. In these corporate documents, the unspoken emphasis is on self-regulation. (Coeckelbergh, 2020)

Self-regulation emerged as a solution for coping with the ethical debate with the advent of the commercial Web in 2004, when the common belief was that the digital industry was capable of developing its own ethical codes and standards, without external oversight needed for enforcement and compliance (Floridi, 2021). Self-regulation matured roughly ten years later, when Google established an Advisory Council in 2014 to address the repercussions of the European Union's Court of Justice judgement on the *right to be forgotten*. At that point, ethical stands were elaborated also within companies themselves. When, in 2019, the Pentagon announced that it would cooperate with Google in the development of drones to seek and track enemy soldiers, almost 3,000 Google signed a letter of complaint, leading the company to terminate the contract. Right after, Google started outlining its own AI principles, pledging not to cooperate in the development of weapons and other technologies aimed at provoking injury and worse, or surveillance technologies that contravene globally accepted ethical standards. Eventually, the 2018 Cambridge Analytica scandal engulfed Facebook, proving how difficult and eventually ineffective self-regulation could be (Floridi, 2021). Guidelines are easily amended and can adapt quickly to technological change, especially compared to black-letter law: therefore, a guidelines-based approach to governance can be adopted in response to previous emerging technologies and can promote ethical, fair, and non-discriminatory practices in AI design, provided that all three elements of regulatory governance are present: standard-setting, external monitoring, and enforcement mechanisms (Taeihagh, 2021; Yeung, 2019). By themselves, important ethical and legal reasons are frequently insufficient to offset worries about the impact of justice or equality considerations on earnings, business models, and other interests (Wachter, 2021). Instead, the fundamental purpose of business ethics has been to limit public and regulatory scrutiny by creating an external façade of ethical behavior, which is intrinsically immoral (G. Wood & Rimmer, 2003). Ethics codes boost corporate reputation and profit by establishing universal moral assertions that are enormously significant as claims but exceedingly ambiguous as regulations: in the field of informatics, these guidelines have remarkable for their absence of specific moral requirements for computer workers (Abbott, 1983). As a result, companies may wind up interpreting ethics arbitrarily and without supervision, a practice known as *ethics-washing*.

3.4.1 The risk of *ethics-washing*

The corporate sector is increasingly committing to *Ethics for AI*, derived from guidelines, codes, frameworks and other ethical standards (Castets-Renard, 2020). These laudable efforts, however, are increasingly identified with technology companies' self-

regulatory efforts and with shallow appearances of ethical behavior (Bietti, 2021), where an ethical language is embraced as a disguise to avoid criticism and governmental oversight (Green, 2021a). This *ethics-washing* is aimed at scrutinizing audiences, who are shown a carefully crafted façade of ethical behavior (Green, 2021a). This mechanism allows companies to set the standard of what counts as ethical behavior (K. Crawford et al., 2016), creating a “market of principles and values” (Castets-Renard, 2020) where private and public actors can choose and outwardly commit to the ethical standards that are best aligned with their current behaviors, rather than adapting to any independent and comprehensive benchmark (*ibid.*). This way, companies are “learning to speak and perform ethics rather than make the structural changes necessary to achieve the social values underpinning the ethical fault lines that exist”. (Metcalf et al., 2019)

Business logic is unchallenged by these iterations of tech ethics (Green, 2021a), that act as a form of virtue signalling. The issue of social acceptability and social impacts of AI is removed from the domain of politics to that of *techno-solutionism*: complex issues such as disparate impacts of algorithms are addressed with routinized, checklist approaches (Bietti, 2021) and without putting into question the effective usefulness of automated approaches. An example would be trying to solve these discriminatory outcomes by striving solely for higher algorithmic accuracy, with no concern of underlying structural injustice (Bietti, 2021; B. D. Mittelstadt et al., 2016).

Unethical practices, rather than being avoided for the sake of societal well-being, are disguised to avoid costly backlash. Companies aim at “performing, or even showing off, the seriousness with which a company takes ethics becomes a more important sign of ethical practices than real changes to a product.” (Metcalf et al., 2019) Digital ethics is therefore captured by business strategy, and is useful insofar it ensures market success, and discarded otherwise (Green, 2021a). This makes most tech business models incompatible with genuine ethical preoccupation, due to their reliance on exploitative and extractive practices: examples abound of companies that have undersigned non-binding ethical frameworks, just to keep developing profitable, yet ethically dubious products. (Green, 2021a) Green (2021a) mentions the case of Microsoft that, after releasing its ethical principles and pledged to protect safety, inclusiveness and privacy (Microsoft, 2018), as well as pledging not to “deploy facial recognition technology in scenarios that we believe will put democratic freedoms at risk” (Smith, 2018), they invested in the Israeli facial recognition company *AnyVision*, which works in concert with the military to aid in the surveillance of Palestinians in the West Bank (Solon, 2019).

Another facet of ethics-washing is that of ethical lobbying, that aims at precluding or tailoring legislation. The adoption of self-regulatory guidelines, while positive *prima facie*, can actually serve the aim of avoiding legislative intervention (Castets-

Renard, 2020; Floridi, 2021), offering the appearance of a perfectly self-sustained digital ecosystem where private platforms successfully act as lawmakers, exerting their governance on delicate issues such as fairness and free speech (Castets-Renard, 2020). An example of this, as described by Castets-Renard (2020), is Mark Zuckerberg's submission of a white paper on online content regulation (Bickert, 2020) to European legislators, and the establishment of Facebook's Oversight Board in May 2020. Through this oversight board, Facebook exercises its judgment over the most problematic content shared on the platform. As Facebook defines its own rules on what counts as hate speech, threats, fake news and nudity (in this case, often censoring artworks), social media platforms are entrusted with an essential role in ensuring free speech and curtailing discrimination with no public oversight nor transparency over their decision-making process (Castets-Renard, 2020).

A tactic employed by business aiming at performing ethics-washing is the hiring of moral philosophers, who join the company ranks with great expectations that are met with little power to actually shape internal and external company policies (Bietti, 2021). The role of philosophers in Big Tech is, unfortunately, mainly that of a mere façade, useful for deflecting legitimate concern over company practices (*ibid.*). Several scandals demonstrate that, once the in-house philosopher dares to raise their own remonstrances over certain practices, firing comes soon after. A high-profile case was the firing of the researcher Timnit Gebru and Meg Mitchell (Hao, 2020), co-leads of Google's Ethical AI team, targeted after writing a paper about limitations and possible harms of Large Language Models (LLMs) (Bender, Gebru, McMillan-Major, & Shmitchell, 2021). As LLMs represent a core business activity of Google, the company resisted the publication and attempted to force the authors to retract it. Externally, Google advertised its ethical approach to business; internally, any form of ethical inquiry was curtailed if threatening to its business interests (Green, 2021a). Gebru and Mitchell's ordeal prompted several other Google employees to resign.

Tech companies such as Google seem unable to raise to their self-entrusted role of human rights defendant. The involvement of affected communities and the political process is necessary for a truly inclusive definition of what constitutes algorithmic harm (Selbst, Boyd, Friedler, Venkatasubramanian, & Vertesi, 2019). A greater scrutiny should be accorded to AI ethics frameworks, in particular regarding the level of civil, political, and academic involvement in its formulation (Daly et al., 2019). Due to gender imbalances skewed in favor of male employees in Big Tech Hagendorff (2020), has pointed out how lack of gender diversity can negatively affect the formulation and achievement of ethical goals. This one of the factors why the setting of ethical standards for AI system necessitates democratic participation, representative of the diverse body of possible affected subjects, and oversight by independent authorities. The responsibility of establishing such participatory and

oversight mechanisms should fall on the state, rather than on private actors (Yeung, 2019). This is especially relevant as Big Tech prepares to set its foot onto the domain of *digital governance*.

Chapter 4

AI and the public administration of justice

In public administration, there is a push to data-driven decision-making (Rieder & Simon, 2016). Governments utilize algorithms for a variety of purposes, including administration, service delivery, welfare benefit allocation, population control and security (Katzenbach & Ulbricht, 2019).

AI, like bureaucracy, is a goal-oriented rational paradigm that claims neutrality and objectivity via detached abstraction (McQuillan, 2020), supporting process rationalisation and monitoring (Panagiotopoulos & Rodrigues, 2021). Algorithms are becoming authoritative as a type of rule, serving as an antidote to subjective decision-making in massive and complex systems (Caplan & Boyd, 2018).

This *algorithmic governance*, which will be explored in Section 4, has its origin and justification on a long history of government data collection and statistical analysis (Levy et al., 2021; Salsburg, 2001). It implies a structural and functional reorganisation of the public sector and its services through a digital transformation that spans the design and delivery of public services, including enforcement and control, and builds on gradual transformation waves from the analogue government towards the digital government (Panagiotopoulos & Rodrigues, 2021). This has been a key item on the governmental agenda for over the past three decades, since the early computing developments in the 1950, with the digitisation of census studies and health records in the '60s as its first step (Panagiotopoulos & Rodrigues, 2021).

As governments become the “developer, procurer, and applier” of AI solutions (Panagiotopoulos & Rodrigues, 2021), they heighten their capacity to elaborate increasing amounts of information for forecasting and prediction, aiming for evidence-based decisions and policy-making (*ibid.*). AI supports operational efficiency and relieves the government from time-consuming and burdensome tasks by automating physical and digital tasks, enabling more cost-efficient investments and the allocation of more resources on high-level tasks (*ibid.*).

The use of data has a long history also in the domain of criminal justice (Brayne,

2017), as the first attested use of the expression *preventive justice* dates back to the late eighteenth century (McSherry, 2020). In his *Commentaries on the Laws of England in Four Books* (1753), Blackstone makes reference to legislation aimed at preventing future crime by acting where there was a “probable suspicion, that some crime is intended or likely to happen.” (Blackstone, 1753) Almost two centuries later, in 1928, Ernest Burgess of the Chicago School created an actuarial model that projected the likelihood of parolees reoffending (Harcourt, 2008; Oleson, VanBenschoten, Robinson, & Lowenkamp, 2011) and this tendency towards quantification was over time in legal processes in the 1970s and 1980s through sentencing standards (Espeland & Vannebo, 2007). Since then, the criminal justice system seems to have turned toward *actuarial justice* (Harcourt, 2008), which is focused on a merely statistical approach to crime prediction and minimization, with little to no focus on understanding the root causes of crime and addressing them through social and economic policies (O’Brien & Yar, 2008; Reiner, 2006). As a consequence, criminal justice practice is dictated by statistical models and aggregate probability scores, rather than the practitioner’s experience and knowledge, implying a shift in decision-making where the risk model has more influence than the judge’s expertise (O’Brien & Yar, 2008; E. Silver & Miller, 2002). While actuarial approaches have been used in jails and the courts for nearly a century, data-driven decision-making has only recently been systematically incorporated into law enforcement processes (Brayne, 2017).

As predictive machine learning algorithms have recently been used to guide judicial decision-making, including sentencing (McSherry, 2020), judges and attorneys may be tempted to significantly depend on algorithmic predictions, which may appear to be sounder and more accurate at first glance thanks to their capacity to make available and elaborate vast amounts of data, retrieve the entire jurisprudence relevant to the case, and the absence of emotional factors influencing decision-making (Caianiello, 2021). These elements that can improve the system’s quality and efficiency, to the point where judges may be prone to underestimating the limitations and flaws of AI predictions, such as highlighted bias effects emerging from elaborated data (Caianiello, 2021). Rather than being an additional information source adjunct onto a stable practice, AI interacts with the behavior of human decision-makers by possibly introducing new sources of bias (Cabitza & Natali, 2022a) and influencing the distribution of benefits and liabilities across the population. (Gabriel, 2022)

Using predictive justice and predictive policing systems may delegate portions of decision-making, as well as responsibility and accountability for the choice itself (Bennett Moses & Chan, 2018) since the machine could be blamed for any undesirable outcome (Sprick, 2019) while the judicial or police bodies avoids accountability. Allocating praise and blame presupposes transparency about the methodology of the prediction and its impact on the corresponding decision (Sprick, 2019) and sufficient

technological expertise to understand the AI output (Ferguson, 2016).

This possible accountability gap would be problematic especially since the choice to predict arrest and assess the risk of reoffending (two of the main applications of predictive policing and predictive justice, as investigated in Sections 4.4.1 and 4.4.2) has far-reaching implications for societal fairness (Mayson, 2018), especially in the domain of racial discrimination. Arrest rates have been racially uneven for decades: therefore, an AI system trained on these data is likely to replicate this racial disparity in arrest and risk predictions. (Mayson, 2018) Such data biases can be hard to detect, and may arise from subtle choices such as the selection of the training dataset, what data to exclude or include, what AI models to use, the construction of prediction parameters and what information to highlight or deemphasize, the choice of fairness metrics (Abiodun & Lekan, 2020; Ugwudike, 2022). While seemingly innocuous, some of these choices allow creators of predictive algorithms to infuse AI systems with their own values, choices and preferences (Ugwudike, 2022), and may result in disparate impacts (Barocas & Selbst, 2016) across social groups (Abiodun & Lekan, 2020), shifting social and political power dynamics by *automating justice* through consistently more favorable automated decisions for certain groups over others. (Abiodun & Lekan, 2020)

These are just a few of the issues that digitization and AI-based innovation could pose to the public sector if a suitable governance framework is not in place (Panagiotopoulos & Rodrigues, 2021). Given these premises, it is perhaps fortunate that the level of use of AI technologies in the justice field is relatively low: according to the European Commission and Directorate-General for Justice and Consumers (2020a) study on the use of innovative technologies in the justice field, as of 2018 only 7% of respondents indicated that some form of AI technologies was in use in their organization (European Commission and Directorate-General for Justice and Consumers, 2020a). There four primary factors that are now limiting the application of AI in the public sector are technology, laws, ethics, and social considerations (van Noordt et al., 2020).

For example, the creation and application of AI technology requires resources that are often lacking in governments: high levels of data quality and integration, and specialized employees to create and implement AI solutions (van Noordt et al., 2020). However, 82% of respondents to the European Commission and Directorate-General for Justice and Consumers questionnaire stated that AI technologies should be deployed in the justice domain, or that their possibilities should be studied, because they could improve data security, data exchanges, access to information, and processing (European Commission and Directorate-General for Justice and Consumers, 2020a). This viewpoint should be addressed with caution in order to avoid falling into the trap of technological solutionism: the belief that technology can fix all social issues (Morozov, 2014). Digital technology solutions to social problems

have been shown not only failing to offer the promised remedies, but at times even exacerbating the problems they are meant to cure (Green, 2021a).

Many of the benefits attributed to AI for the public sector are often based on assumptions, rather than real data (van Noordt & Misuraca, 2022). Validation of their projected positive impact has been limited, due to the slow adoption of AI in public administrations and the lack of comprehensive impact assessments that highlight the consequences of AI after their effective deployment (van Noordt & Misuraca, 2022). As two-thirds of humanity lack meaningful access to justice (OECD, 2019a), AI can make justice faster, cheaper and more intelligible (Spinney, 2022), democratize access to legal information and support users in resolving their own legal issues or connecting them with professionals who can (Simshaw, 2022). This does not take into account the case of proprietary and for-profit predictive softwares, through which litigants willing to pay for such services can be consulted on the best ways to win their case by anticipating the court judgment based on advanced data analysis on past judicial behavior, giving them an unfair edge (Abiodun & Lekan, 2020; Stewart & Stuhmcke, 2020). Predictive court analytics may become a tactic used by plaintiffs with access to advanced data analytics tools, therefore those with more financial resources (Stewart & Stuhmcke, 2020).

As anticipated, in this chapter I will go over the concept of algorithmic governance in Section 4.1, emphasizing in Section 4.1.1 the role that profiling and prediction play in the increasing rationalisation of public administration. I will then focus on the concepts of predictive justice (section 4.2) and predictive policing (section 4.3), also reporting three notable case studies of algorithmic injustice: the racial bias demonstrated by the risk assessment tool COMPAS (section 4.4.1) and the discriminatory assumptions and surveillance in SyRI (section 4.4.2).

4.1 Algorithmic governance

The era of algorithmic governance has arrived. The Special Rapporteur on Extreme Poverty and Human Rights dedicated his Report A/74/493 to the digital transformation of government service provision, in particular the welfare state, which is “gradually disappearing behind a webpage and an algorithm” (Special Rapporteur on Extreme Poverty and Human Rights Philip Alston, 2019b). Among other affected and emerging areas we find electronic voting, technology-driven surveillance through facial recognition programs and predictive policing, the digitization of justice, and many other forms of virtual interactions between citizens and various levels of government. This is becoming the norm in high- and middle-income countries (Special Rapporteur on Extreme Poverty and Human Rights Philip Alston, 2019b).

In a recently published white paper on AI (2020), the European Commission devotes a specific section to promoting AI adoption by the public sector, deeming it

essential that AI products and services are embedded in activities of public interest, e.g. in administrative, sanitary, financial and transportation domains (Commission, 2020). Ahn and Chen (2020) present what they called *AI-augmented bureaucracy*, that aims at a detailed understanding of the citizens' needs and forecasting optimal solutions, providing customizable service. These activities could be properly understood as *smart government* (Ahn & Chen, 2020; Medaglia et al., 2021).

AI is an attractive tool for use in the public sector, since environmental conditions are continually changing and no sort of preprogramming could account for all probable scenarios (Medaglia et al., 2021). This is the main rationale behind the idea of algorithms as an instrument for making policy more adaptive policy, always up-to-date thanks to its autonomous learning capabilities. (Levy et al., 2021; Mormann, 2021) This sets algorithms apart from traditional automation technologies relying on pre-programmed *if-then* logic for decision-making, where the same input instructions create identical results (Medaglia et al., 2021). To effectively function and learn autonomously, however, AI requires adequate and readily available data: if these conditions are not met, AI may not be the ideal solution for automated decision making (*ibid.*).

The public sector's push for algorithm adoption is a product of the post-World War II rush to formalize, rationalize, and automate government (Levy et al., 2021). The goal of systematized, quantified government decision-making stems from operations research, which aims to provide neutral, scientific, and objective approaches for analyzing events and finding optimal courses of action (Harcourt, 2018; Levy et al., 2021). The commitment to automated decision-making that characterizes algorithmic governance makes algorithms the determinants of a new social order, where procedures are affected by their intrinsic mathematical logic and statistical practices (Katzenbach & Ulbricht, 2019; Srivastava, 2021). As a result, discussions concerning algorithmic governance frequently overlaps with those about *datafication* (Mejias & Couldry, 2019) and AI (Katzenbach & Ulbricht, 2019).

Datafication, which refers to “the quantification of human life through digital information” (Mejias & Couldry, 2019) benefits from the *data deluge* (Andrews, 2012), a surge in the volume and variety of data acquired through by increasingly sophisticated infrastructures that allow for more and quicker data processing, as well as societal standards that facilitate quantification, classification, and surveillance (Katzenbach & Ulbricht, 2019; Rieder & Simon, 2016). Algorithmic governance encompasses a diverse set of socio-technical practices that range from predictive policing to labor management and content moderation. In this sense, algorithmic rule aims to anticipate and mitigate agency, spontaneity, and risk: by mapping various futures before they occur, unwanted ones are actively avoided and acceptable ones are pursued (Andrejevic, 2019a).

Algorithmic governance can have disruptive impacts on government decision-

making and administrative efficiency as well as citizen participation, by providing services that better reflect their needs and expectations (Medaglia et al., 2021; Reis, Santo, & Melão, 2019). Relying on data for policy-making is also perceived as an antidote to subjective factors (Richardson et al., 2019), and evidence shows that data-driven governance is especially welcome in countries that display higher perceived levels of corruption, perhaps due to people's widespread expectation of AI as a neutral instrument (Medaglia et al., 2021).

Algorithmic governance, when based on evidence-based policing and increased data access for accountability purposes, can provide opportunities for heightened governmental transparency and more careful design of policies (Levy et al., 2021). To realize this potential, a data ecosystem with a competent workforce, resources that can be mobilized quickly, meaningful control over AI systems, incentives for innovation, and, most importantly, an adequate regulatory and ethical framework is required (Levy et al., 2021; Medaglia et al., 2021).

Algorithmic governance could be the most inclusive and responsive system of government we have known of; or it could be the most coercive and invasive (Katzenbach & Ulbricht, 2019). Among the risks of algorithm governance we find bias and discrimination, (Srivastava, 2021) increasing social division (Medaglia et al., 2021) and exclusion (Valle-Cruz, Alejandro Ruvalcaba-Gomez, Sandoval-Almazan, & Ignacio Criado, 2019), lowered accountability of decision-makers behind opaque algorithms and increased analysis complexity, (Medaglia et al., 2021; Monteiro, 2022; Valle-Cruz et al., 2019) cybersecurity risks, (Henman, 2020) job loss, (Valle-Cruz et al., 2019) loss of control of AI systems and blind obedience to their outputs, paternalism and loss of privacy (Henman, 2020; Medaglia et al., 2021; Wirtz & Müller, 2019).

Another issue is the reliance (or even dependence) on Big Tech to realize new AI solutions for algorithmic governance (Balkin, 2017; K. Crawford, 2021; Srivastava, 2021), developing proprietary and closed-source software (Christian, 2020) whose opaque functioning could undermine the accountability required for institutional legitimacy in representative liberal democracies (American Civil Liberties Union, 2022; M. B. Crawford, 2021; Monteiro, 2022), resulting in unchecked authority that is difficult to challenge (Monteiro, 2022).

Social media companies, too, can represent a rich and pervasive source of citizen data: as revealed in 2013 by Edward Snowden. Facebook and Google were sharing user data with secret services in the US, the UK, Australia, New Zealand, and Canada (Srivastava, 2021). This behavioral data is collected in a systematic manner to train and improve machine learning: to perform better (that is, to provide more accurate predictions about complex social issues), algorithmic governance is vulnerable to a strong pull towards continuous monitoring in order to extract increased and more diverse data (Srivastava, 2021).

Closer scrutiny and continuous auditing should be applied to the practices underpinning the creation, gathering and processing of data by governments (Richardson et al., 2019) with a focus on public participation in the creation of digital technologies, transparency about how they work, and intelligible, publicly available regulatory and redress systems (Floridi, 2018). In fact, public acceptance and use of digital technology in government will occur only if the advantages are perceived to be real and the hazards to be prospective, but avoidable, or at the very least something against which one may be safeguarded (Floridi, 2018).

Rather than focusing solely on strictly quantifiable, market-driven notions of efficiency and attempting a punitive and paternalistic standardization of citizen behavior, the focus of algorithmic governance should be on how government capacities can be enhanced through technology to ensure a better quality of life for society's most vulnerable and disadvantaged members (Special Rapporteur on Extreme Poverty and Human Rights Philip Alston, 2019b).

4.1.1 Profiling and prediction

Profiling and prediction are two sides of the same coin. They are the main way in which data can support the automation of public services (Burr, 2021): when combined, they can generate knowledge systems for social management that inform and execute decisions (Srivastava, 2021; Yeung, 2018a), such as *Social Credit Systems* (Creemers, 2018), whose general framework and key mechanisms have first been established and refined in China between 2014 and 2020, as outlined by the State Council's *Planning Outline for the Construction of a Social Credit System (2014-2020)* (Chinese State Council, 2014; Creemers, 2018; Drinhausen & Brussee, 2021).

China's Social Credit System is a digitised and data-driven system (Drinhausen & Brussee, 2021) that elaborates a multitude of information from a variety of sources - including who their friends are, their online spending behavior, and social media posts (Creemers, 2018) - aiming at assessing the trustworthiness of individuals and corporations to improve their adherence to ideal legal and ethical behaviors (Y. Chen & Cheung, 2017; Sprick, 2019) and providing rewards or sanctions accordingly. (Creemers, 2018; Monteiro, 2022) For example, these systems have been shown to affect people's ability to travel, land a job, receive loans and mortgages, and even their relationships with family and friends (Creemers, 2018). By "scoring and predicting citizen behaviour, preference and opinion", (Katzenbach & Ulbricht, 2019) social benefits are distributed, and national security and policing are enforced. These ambitious aims rely on new forms of population surveillance and profiling that are achieved in concert by state and corporate actors (Bennett Moses & Chan, 2018). This incentive mechanism aims at fostering *social harmony* - as explicitly mentioned in (Chinese State Council, 2014) - which should be interpreted as absolute conformity to the Party's will (Monteiro, 2022).

Similar predictive and profiling systems are only conceivable because of AI technology and its ability to enhance and expand state surveillance. AI-enabled monitoring, rewarding, and repression become tools to shape the ideal citizen (Monteiro, 2022). AI technology can become the central feature of an oppression system that is more efficient and less costly in casting its net of surveillance and intimidation, by automating various functions that were previously by dense networks of surveillance agents and removing human error (Monteiro, 2022). The pervasive and ever-present algorithms are gradually internalized by the subject, who will censor themselves at every step. The awareness of constant surveillance results in a *chilling effect* that inhibits a citizen from acting freely (White & Zimbardo, 1975) with strong repercussions on freedom of speech and freedom of assembly (Katzenbach & Ulbricht, 2019), fostering a strictly compliant behavior and eroding the exercise of individual rights and freedoms, thus eroding the foundations for a democratic society itself (Yeung, 2018a). This proactive aspect of social management creates a society that nearly does not need to be controlled (Monteiro, 2022).

Profiling, in its most basic sense, does not have a negative connotation *per se*. Article 4(4) of the European General Data Protection Regulation defines it as “[A]ny form of automated processing of personal data consisting of the use of personal data to evaluate certain personal aspects relating to a natural person, in particular to analyse or predict aspects concerning that natural person’s performance at work, economic situation, health, personal preferences, interests, reliability, behaviour, location or movements.” (European Commission, 2016) Target 16.9 of the UN Sustainable Development Goals (United Nations, 2015) calls for a global effort to establishing every person’s legal identity by 2030; digitising this identification and enriching it with other demographic and socioeconomic attributes may facilitate the targeting and delivery of services and resources to better address specific social challenges. This *datafication* of legal identity could also reduce the risk of duplication and fraud (Special Rapporteur on Extreme Poverty and Human Rights Philip Alston, 2019b), but it introduces new risk, such as the exposure of sensitive information due to data breaches, which, if not properly addressed, may have adverse effects on individuals whose data have been compromised, ranging from identity theft to economic and mental hardship or even bodily harm (Leslie, 2019). For the purpose of this thesis, I will focus instead on the grave unintended consequences that may arise when sensitive information is processed by classification algorithms.

Classification refers to process of assigning an object or person to a specific group. (Burr, 2021) Classification algorithms identify objects and assign them to categories by using either unsupervised or semi-supervised Machine Learning techniques on extensive databases (Srivastava, 2021). These categories can be predefined, or they can emerge over time when the algorithm detects new, unexpected patterns. The more criteria that are considered and the more information that is obtained, the more

complex and specific the categories become: the use of Machine Learning techniques enables the construction of profiles that are fluid, relational, and implicit, instead of categorical (Edwards & Veale, 2017).

Profiling is an ongoing process that takes place over an indefinite period of time: even though individuals may be assigned to a category following the internal logic of a system, this classification is not static. Profiles are instantly updated and constantly re-defined by the algorithm (Zarsky, 2013) when new information about them becomes available (Floridi & Taddeo, 2016). This information is gathered either directly, when a person leaves ‘data breadcrumbs’ by interacting with a specific technology, or indirectly, as new information is inferred from automatically assembled groups of individuals that share similarities with the targeted person, for example in terms of demographic features or behavioral patterns (Floridi & Taddeo, 2016).

These dehumanized ‘data doubles’ inferred from group statistics allow for the fast, automatized construction of detailed profiles about individuals (Katzenbach & Ulbricht, 2019) where seemingly innocuous data, when intensively mined and processed, can reveal highly personal characteristics, facilitating the discrimination and manipulation of the people by the hand of State actors (Katzenbach & Ulbricht, 2019; Yeung, 2019). This type of relational profiling has little conscious and deliberate input on the part of the affected individual, who is singled out on the basis of connections that they cannot control nor foresee. (Yeung, 2019) It is a form of *de-individualisation*, namely the “tendency of judging and treating people on the basis of group characteristics instead of on their own individual characteristics and merit.” (Van Wel & Royakkers, 2004) No matter the intensity of the correlations found, we have to mind the gap between information concerning populations, and resulting actions directed instead at individuals (B. D. Mittelstadt et al., 2016). This has strong implications for self-determination and free will, and implies the systematic and automated treatment of persons as objects with a fixed and pre-determined destiny, instead of moral actors (Yeung, 2019).

According to the *Guidelines on Automated individual decision-making and Profiling for the purposes of Regulation 2016/679* by the European Commission’s Article 29 Data Protection Working Party (2018),

“Profiling can perpetuate existing stereotypes and social segregation. It can also lock a person into a specific category and restrict them to their suggested preferences. This can undermine their freedom to choose, for example, certain products or services such as books, music or news-feeds. In some cases, profiling can lead to inaccurate predictions. In other cases it can lead to denial of services and goods and unjustified discrimination.”

(Article 29 Data Protection Working Party, 2018)

Predicting future trends for a category of people on the basis of correlations reveals how profiling is the enabler of predictions (Burr, 2021), and both require extensive surveillance for the collection of granular data. (Yeung, 2019) Surveillance describes “purposeful, routine, systematic and focused attention paid to personal details, for the sake of control, entitlement, management, influence or protection.” (D. M. Wood, Ball, Lyon, Norris, & Raab, 2006) It implies an asymmetric power relationship between the surveilled and the surveillant (Andrejevic, 2019b), where possible harms go beyond the domain of individual privacy, including for example issues of discrimination (Mantelero, 2018).

Some predictions can be a force for good in informing evidence-based policy-making, where the use of accurate and extensive data can help in avoiding irresponsible or biased choices (Burr, 2021). The issue of data quality is crucial, and decisions should not be based on *dirty data* - “missing data, wrong data, and non-standard representations of the same data.” (Richardson et al., 2019) This includes data that is distorted by historical patterns of discrimination and bias at the societal and individual level (*ibid.*). Relying on this type of data for policy-making carries the risk of creating negative feedback loops: any forecast based on historical data will produce discriminatory results if the target variable occurs disproportionately across demographic groups, as such biased patterns in past data are presented as predictions of future events (Mayson, 2018). At the individual level, past mistakes can permanently tarnish one’s “algorithmic reputation”, as the actuarial logic of algorithmic justice is largely blind to the fact that can rely on experience to avoid repeating mistakes, rather than perpetrating them (Falletti, 2022). Higher rates of arrest in a disadvantaged segment of population due to circumstantial issues becomes a manifest destiny once it is magnified by prediction: past inequalities are projected forward (Mayson, 2018) and the socioeconomic status quo is crystallized by predictions that present themselves as telescopes, but are actually mirrors.

It is clear, then, that prediction and classification are not an exact science (Burr, 2021) and they disparately impact the poorest strata of the population, who are subject to increased rates of surveillance and negative feedback loops (Eubanks, 2018; Sprick, 2019). Yet, the reliance on algorithmic categories to describe a person and the assessments they produce has the irresistible appeal of signaling objectivity and certainty (Ananny, 2016; Korff & Brown, 2013), despite the opaque nature of their internal logic. As algorithms will inevitably generate errors that State actors may be unable or unwilling to explain, it will be increasingly harder to seek redress and ensure accountability for decisions that significantly affect citizens (Korff & Brown, 2013). Because of this, the application of prediction and profiling in the public sector, and in the justice sector in particular, is especially problematic. The two following sections will investigate the issues of predictive justice and predictive policing.

4.2 Predictive justice

The minimization of human discretion and human error is one of the main tenets of algorithmic governance, as discussed in Section 4.1. As shown by Danziger, Levav, and Avnaim-Pesso (2011), the work of judges can be affected by extraneous factors such as the time of the hearing, whether or not they had a pause before, and whether they had lunch. In the rationalizing process of algorithmic governance, justice strives towards predictability and standardization - or, according to Licoppe and Dumoulin (2019), its ‘robotisation’. While AI and ML systems are extremely relevant for these aims (Caianiello, 2021), the pursuit of techniques to forecast justice court outcomes has been ongoing since before their inception (Queudot & Meurs, 2018).

Already in 1963, Loevinger established a new discipline called *Jurimetrics*, aiming at “the formulation of a calculus of legal predictability” (Loevinger, 1963). In the same year, Lawlor affirmed that technology would one day analyse and anticipate judicial decisions (Lawlor, 1963). Today, breakthroughs in Natural Language Processing and Machine Learning provide us with the ability to analyze legal texts automatically in order to create successful prediction models of judicial outcomes (Aletras, Tsarapatsanis, Preotiuc-Pietro, & Lampos, 2016; Tromans, 2017). This is defined as *predictive justice*, “Software anticipating a judicial decision based on the analysis of a large quantity of case law” (Abiodun & Lekan, 2020), or *Judicial analytics*, which is “the use of data to monitor, understand and predict judicial behaviour.” (Stewart & Stuhmcke, 2020) This predictive ability, which formalizes previously anecdotal knowledge (Stewart & Stuhmcke, 2020), requires access to extensive and high quality data sets on case law (Queudot & Meurs, 2018) and is based on linguistic analysis and the retrieval of arguments in legal texts through Natural Language Processing (Abiodun & Lekan, 2020; Aletras et al., 2016).

Predictions can have significant effect for the work of lawyers and the effort of litigants, helping them defining their tactics and perhaps drop the cases that would result hopeless, in turn reducing congestion in courts (Queudot & Meurs, 2018; Stewart & Stuhmcke, 2020). Over time, these subtle influences can shape the approach of lawyers to the legal doctrine and the legal principle itself, as claims are withdrawn or settled following predictions, generating more self-sustaining data crystallizing this tendency (Stewart & Stuhmcke, 2020) In fact, even in systems different from the Anglo-Saxon case law framework, legal decision-making is strongly guided by influential precedents, that can offer to the judge examples of successful legal reasoning or statements of facts to help them in framing their reasoning for an order or a judgment. (Queudot & Meurs, 2018)

Academic interest in predictive justice has resulted in groundbreaking research, such as Aletras et al.’s (2016) predictions of judicial decisions on cases heard by the European Court of Human Rights, based purely on textual content. Previous published judgments served as the training set of a text-based analysis, as the authors

did not have access to other material such as lodged applications or briefs. Since the structure of judgments of the European Court of Human Rights is sufficiently standardized, this material is particularly apt of an automated text-based analysis. The point of the authors is: “if there is enough similarity between the chunks of text of published judgments that we analyzed and that of lodged applications and briefs, then our approach can be fruitfully used to predict outcomes with these other kinds of texts.” (Aletras et al., 2016)

Similar applications of legal knowledge-based tools are starting to support lawyers: intelligent search tool and predictive technologies can accelerate the workflow of legal professionals, as the manual searching of related case journals is replaced by an automated, precise and customized extraction of information (Abiodun & Lekan, 2020). Some examples of AI tools for lawyers is IBM’s *ROSS Intelligence*, based on the company’s cognitive computer *Watson* and first ‘employed’ in 2016 by law firms in the United States (Abiodun & Lekan, 2020; Liberatore, 2016). ROSS can communicate with lawyers using natural language and is specialized in bankruptcy consulting (*ibid.*). In France, *Predictive* estimates the rate of success of prospective court cases by reportedly analyzing one million judicial decisions per second (Abiodun & Lekan, 2020). Zambrano (2015) provides an analysis of several other legal-tech start-ups concerned with the prediction of outcomes of court cases, such as Juristat, Lex Predict and Lex Machina. Companies such as Solomonic and Gavelytics, respectively based in the United Kingdom and in the United States, are instead based on mining judicial data to consult lawyers on strategies to litigate more successfully. In particular, Gavelytics exploits the looser American privacy laws to assess and present the behavioral patterns of judges, attorneys, law firms and litigants, providing a strategic advantage to its clients (Spinney, 2022). Solomonic is specialized in out-of-court settlements, extracting general trends on how many cases with similar characteristics to the one at hand were successfully privately settled, also giving insights on the time it took to reach the agreement. As the more informed litigants are, the more likely they are to opt for out-of-court settlements: the use of softwares like Solomonic can therefore make the process cheaper and faster, while easing the congestion of courts (*ibid.*).

This shows how data literacy and analytics are becoming sought-after and increasingly crucial skills and tools for lawyers, also because data analysis of judicial performance has the potential to ‘disrupt’ the legal profession by shedding light on metrics of success (Stewart & Stuhmcke, 2020). This last factor can explain some of the grievances against the disclosure of statistics on judge performance and rulings, which in France is punished by up to five years in jail (Spinney, 2022). On the opposite, the move was welcome in China, where judicial data is said to have improved public trust in the judiciary (*ibid.*).

The public has an interest in the efficient and fair operation of state institutions,

and public trust in the administration of justice is essential to the rule of law (Stewart & Stuhmcke, 2020). The internet has opened new avenues for public oversight and participation in judicial proceedings (Peng & Xiang, 2019). As such, a form of court digitalization can improve the capacity, efficiency, openness, trustworthiness and positive public perception of courts and judges (Peng & Xiang, 2019). This push for *e-Justice* may have begun in the United States in the 1970s, when information collected through computers was allowed in court hearings (Shi, Sourdin, & Li, 2021), but it has only lately gained momentum. The COVID-19 pandemic hastened a transition towards virtual platforms and a growing use of artificial intelligence, as most countries allowed for online hearings and welcomed e-filings of legal papers (Spinney, 2022). Some digitalization initiatives, such as e-filing, e-conferencing and, to a lesser extent, prediction systems, are making inroads in Canada, the United Kingdom, Ireland and even the in European Court of Justice. (Arias, 2020) Although China did not accept electronic evidence in court until 2012, the country has now eagerly endorsed all aspects of e-justice at all levels of its judiciary system, up to the Supreme People's Court (Spinney, 2022).

Artificial Intelligence is mostly employed to save time on tedious and repetitive tasks like transcription, but it is increasingly used also for more delicate and complex tasks such as mining data on instructive trends, for example on crimes being committed or regularities in judicial rulings (De Sanctis, 2021; Spinney, 2022). Artificial Intelligence can even play a more central advisory and even determinative role, in what is called the *Smart Court* system (Shi et al., 2021). The smart court system integrated legal Artificial Intelligence with big data use and blockchain formation (*ibid.*). For the scope of this thesis, I will focus on Artificial Intelligence.

A few Internet courts have already been established in China, notably in the cities of Hanzhou, Guangzhou and in Beijing (Abiodun & Lekan, 2020). This automatization of the judicial system has China at the forefront (Abiodun & Lekan, 2020), mainly because of specific judicial capacity issues: there is a high discrepancy between the relatively small number of Chinese judges and the increasing reliance of people on the law to solve their disputes thanks to the fast social and economic development (Peng & Xiang, 2019). The smart court system is seen as the definitive solution to further promote access to justice and ease the workloads of judges, while enabling a faster and more efficient dispute resolution. This, in turn, saves costs through cheaper online proceedings and ensured a better enforcement of judgments (Shi et al., 2021).

Of course, the smart court system presents some downsides. These concerns are related to data privacy, the quality of legal big data, algorithmic opacity, and the erosion of judicial independence due to datafied scrutiny of their work and their possible over-reliance on (or even substitution by) automated judgments (Greenhouse, 2021; Shi et al., 2021). The possible automation of judgment is the most contentious

application of legal AI. It is debatable whether an algorithm should be permitted to decide autonomously about high-stakes decisions that severely impact the lives of human beings (European Commission and Directorate-General for Justice and Consumers, 2020b). Some examples are automated calculation of bail amount, recidivism risk assessment, or fully-fledged AI court rulings (*ibid.*). This reliance on AI in judicial decisions could inappropriately hand over the discretionary sentencing power to non-judicial agents (Hillman, 2019).

Risk assessments generated by algorithms have been repeatedly shown to be biased (European Commission and Directorate-General for Justice and Consumers, 2020b), and yet they are presented to the court as if they were a factual and objective measurement (Hillman, 2019). Predictive technology acts as another witness against the defendant, who in most cases will lack the resources to understand and challenge it (*ibid.*). This is because the data, assumptions, and even underlying prejudices of the AI model's reasoning are shrouded in the secrecy of an often proprietary black box (*ibid.*).

It is therefore important for judges and lawyers to be educated in the level of trust that they should accord to legal AI, teaching them how to responsibly use these algorithms in their practice (European Commission and Directorate-General for Justice and Consumers, 2020b). A risk that emerges from the adoption of algorithmic solutions is that of algorithmic bias defined in section 1.3.1. To ensure that judges are not as tempted to follow the AI advice uncritically, and ensuring judicial autonomy and flexibility, van Dijck (2022) points out three possible *Human-AI Collaboration Protocols* (Cabitza & Natali, 2022a) to combine human judgment with the outputs of AI in the legal domain: an optional approach, a benchmark approach, or a feedback approach. In the optional approach, the decision whether to consult (or, if consulted, to accept) the AI judgment is left to the judge, reintroducing a level of arbitrariness to the court, whether positive or negative (van Dijck, 2022). In the benchmark approach, the AI output represents a “first-step” in the decision-making process, and it serves the aim of offering to the judge a baseline overview of the case from which to build their legal reasoning and draw their conclusions. This can entail an anchoring effect (Englich, Mussweiler, & Strack, 2006; D. Wang, Yang, Abdul, & Lim, 2019) or automation bias (Goddard, Roudsari, & Wyatt, 2012), whereby the decision-maker tends not to deviate much from the AI output, or even uncritically accept it. The final approach is the feedback approach: the human judgment comes first, and it is then compared to the AI prediction. The decision maker can then adjust their own judgment or leave it unchanged, or even decide to either fully adopt AI's output (van Dijck, 2022) .

These calls for a greater autonomy of judges from algorithmic predictions are motivated by the centrality of human intuition, experience and soft skills to the sentencing process, that “when done correctly... is more art than science.” (Hillman,

2019) The same judicial discretion that algorithmic justice wants to minimise can be the antidote to the strictness and context-blindness of contemporary algorithms. As in the case of the Dutch *Toeslagen affaire*, a child benefit scandal that costed thousand of innocent families their livelihoods (NJCM et al. v The Dutch State, 2020; Special Rapporteur on Extreme Poverty and Human Rights Philip Alston, 2019a; Toh, 2019), blameless irregularities in benefit applications are automatically classified as ‘fraud’ and attenuating circumstances are not evaluated with human sensitivity. After all, following the words of the mythologist Joseph Campbell, “Computers are like Old Testament Gods; lots of rules and no mercy.” (Campbell, 1988)

4.3 Predictive policing

The terrorist attacks of 9/11 had an indelible impact on the datafication of policing, leading to the development of ‘intelligence-led policing’. (Ratcliffe, 2003) Local law enforcement agencies engaged in the domestic war of terror as front line actors, receiving in turn increased funding to gather, analyze, exchange and use data. Today, police departments are deploying predictive policing systems, defined as “the collection and analysis of data about previous crimes for identification and statistical prediction of individuals or geospatial areas with an increased probability of criminal activity to help to develop policing intervention and prevention strategies and tactics.” (Meijer & Wessels, 2019)

Oswald et al. (2018) pinpoint three main purposes for the application of Artificial Intelligence in the context of policing. The first case is a macro-level aid to planning, prioritisation and forecasting; then the generation and evaluation of networks, for aims such as crime reduction; finally, algorithms can inform decision-making or risk-assessments pertaining to individuals (Oswald et al., 2018). The forecast of criminal activity (Perry, 2013) informs police intervention (Leslie et al., 2022) and allows for a more efficient allocation of limited resources (National Institute of Justice (NIJ), 2014; Richardson et al., 2019). As highlighted by Meijer and Wessels (2019), the predictions generated by these systems can be either place-based or person-based. Place-based predictions, based on the idea of *crime hotspots* (Chainey, Tompson, & Uhlig, 2008; Hart & Zandbergen, 2012), provide a possible time-frame and location of future crimes (Perry, 2013; Richardson et al., 2019), while person-based predictions generate networks that single out individuals who are likely to be involved in criminal activity, either as a victim or perpetrator (Braga, Hureau, & Papachristos, 2014; Richardson et al., 2019). Typical responses to forecasted high levels of risk are the deployment of an increased police presence to the hotspot in question, or the surveillance of the potential perpetrator, or giving a warning to the possible victim (Katzenbach & Ulbricht, 2019).

This technological upgrading of law enforcement has a high publicity value (Fer-

guson, 2016), boosting the legitimacy of the public security apparatus, as algorithmic solutions are perceived as unbiased and incorruptible (Sprick, 2019) and can shield organizations from criticism over discriminatory practices, as data-driven policing is presented as an accountability mechanism (Brayne, 2017). It is the case of Chinese law enforcement, in the cadre of the AI-enhanced and automated prevention of any form of deviant behavior, such as the aforementioned Social Credit System (Sprick, 2019). Between March and December 2017 alone, Chinese police apprehended 43.000 fugitives thanks to the use of data technology (G. Chen, 2019). At the local level, since 2014, Suzhou Municipality has used the Suzhou Public Security Crime Prediction System to forecast the locations and times of theft (Henman, 2020). Instead, predictive policing has so far yielded inconclusive results in terms of efficacy in the United States (Bennett Moses & Chan, 2018), owing to a considerable potential to be corrupted by self-fulfilling predictions (Ferguson, 2017), or *confirmation feedback loops*. (Richardson et al., 2019)

Increasing police presence and surveillance in vulnerable communities can promote unfounded prejudices and arrest rates. These confirmation feedback loops can instigate responses that perpetuate discrimination (Richardson et al., 2019), such as the issue of US police disproportionately stopping and questioning Black owing to what is jokingly referred to as the offense of ‘driving while black’ (Harris, 1996).

As already explored in Section 4.1.1 on prediction and profiling, present decisions are informed by hypothetical futures (Andrejevic, 2019a) based on patterns that are shaped by past data (Monteiro, 2022) collected from a variety of sources (Katzenbach & Ulbricht, 2019). It is implied that, the more data is available, the more accurate these predictions will be; a failure in criminal prediction is attributed to incomplete information, and the purported solution is to gather more data, with direct implications for mass surveillance (Andrejevic, 2019a). But more is not always better. As observed for negative feedback loops, increasing surveillance (and therefore data gathering) in specific areas can increase an unevenly high rate of crime detection which, rather than a result of higher criminality, could be the result of a more intense and strict scrutiny over everyday occurrences.

The notion that police data reflects actual criminal behavior is a fallacy: police data reflects rates of arrest (Mayson, 2018). Not every crime is reported, and for those that are, some are reported falsely; others are left unsolved, perhaps until a scapegoat from a marginalized community is apprehended. Arrest rates can therefore be racially biased and can be further distorted by possible corruption and other unlawful practices (Richardson et al., 2019). In this sense, we can speak of ‘dirty data’, which nevertheless represent the main data sources analyzed by police authorities (Richardson et al., 2019). Predictive policing vendors have so far provided little assurance that their systems are not based on dirty data: if that is the case, biased policing practices of the past will inevitably influence predictions that will

become self-affirming, since “a racially unequal past will necessarily produce racially unequal outputs.” (Bennett Moses & Chan, 2018; Mayson, 2018; Richardson et al., 2019)

Another source of potential bias is the use of Facial Recognition Technology (FRT). It is based on the automatic recognition of facial features via Machine Learning, identifying specific individual on their basis of this biometric data. Biometric data is defined in the Article 4(14) of the GDPR as “personal data resulting from specific technical processing relating to the physical, physiological or behavioural characteristics of a natural person, which allow or confirm the unique identification of that natural person, such as facial images or dactyloscopic data” (European Commission, 2016). It represents a special category of data, but it can be processed by the police according to the principles of necessity and proportionality (Roussi, 2020). It is debatable whether proportionality can be evoked for solutions that put into constant surveillance thousands, or even millions of people to catch a single criminal; yet, by 2019, already 64 countries and hundreds of municipalities were using FRT, sometimes as part of ‘smart city’ programs where AI cameras are sold as the definitive solution to tackle crime (*ibid.*). As FRT becomes widespread, researchers, legal scholars and civil society advocates are exposing its harms and immaturity, as the technology still presents grave issues of inaccuracy and racial bias (*ibid.*). Despite this rising awareness, FRT based on biased datasets is still being developed and used in circumstances where individual security is at stake, (Leslie, 2019) causing great concern also for its deployment by governments that could use it as an instrument to target opposition and limit freedom.

Buolamwini and Gebru are the authors of an influential paper on racial bias in FRT: they demonstrated that these systems have disparate accuracy according to gender and skin tone of individuals, performing worst on the task of recognizing dark-skinned women. In general, the system performed best on males compared to females, and on light-skinned people compared to dark-skinned people (Buolamwini & Gebru, 2018) and, in general, compared to those with non-western features (Akhtar, 2019). Other studies have pointed to a worrying rate of misidentification also in the case of trans and gender-nonconforming people (Leslie et al., 2022). The issues generated by misidentification are straightforward, as an innocent person may be wrongly accused of a crime they did not commit. Since FRT error disproportionately targets vulnerable strata of the population, it is a case of structural injustice (Buolamwini & Gebru, 2018).

The challenges of accountability, accuracy, and prejudice in predictive policing investigated in this section demonstrate the need for rigorous assessment procedures capable of resolving these issues for AI-informed police activity (Sprick, 2019). This has been identified by Sprick 2019 as “the single most important issue stressed in many publications on predictive policing”.

A final issue is that of transparency by the developers of the predictive policing software, which should be evaluated from two standpoints: transparency towards the public, and transparency towards the organisation that deploys it (Katzenbach & Ulbricht, 2019). While the data sources can be in part transparent to the police organisation in case of shared efforts in data collection (Egbert, 2019), the internal logic of the software are mostly inscrutable for anyone but the developers, with no predictive policing system being transparent to the public as how it operates, what data is used, and what accountability measures are in place to redress potential injustice (Katzenbach & Ulbricht, 2019; Richardson et al., 2019). This unwillingness to provide transparency on the side of developers and law enforcement is justified on the grounds that giving information about how the software works would make the it ineffective, allowing ill-intentioned people to ‘game the system’ to escape punishment (Katzenbach & Ulbricht, 2019). This justification was used also in the *Toeslagen affaire* scandal, as the government refused to disclose the functioning of their fraud-detection system *SyRI* even during court hearings (NJCM et al. v The Dutch State, 2020). This egregious case of algorithmic injustice will be explored in the following section, along with the risk assessment tool COMPAS.

In conclusion, the issues displayed by predictive policing systems could lead us to rethink the punitive and actuarial logic of law enforcement as a whole. In Machine Learning algorithms aiming at reducing crime, fairness concerns do not represents insightful opportunities, but rather constraints on the efficiency-driven, short-term logic that suggests to widely resort to incarceration, since individuals in prison cannot offend (Bao et al., 2021). This calls for what Virginia Dignum (2022) defined as a *relational* approach to AI, as opposed to the prevalent rational approach. Under the rational approach, human decision-making is directed by algorithms, irrespective of human insights, involvement, and even emotions, culminating in bias and exclusion. The relational approach, on the other hand, acknowledges that objective and rational reasoning may not always give rise to the correct course of action, because correctness is dependent on the dynamics of the environment where the choice is made. Rather than solving ethical problems, the focus of AI design and use should be on asking ethical questions: instead of asking for more complete police data for more accurate predictions, implying more pervasive surveillance, we should ask ourselves what are the sources of this almost ineludible source of bias, resulting in an approach to policing that analyses the causes of crime and addresses them through assistive interventions, rather than choosing a punitive approach (European Commission and Directorate-General for Justice and Consumers, 2020b).

4.4 Case studies on algorithmic (in)justice

This section presents three notable case studies of ‘algorithmic injustice’, which is defined as the harmful effects of algorithms, especially their automation of historically discriminatory patterns disproportionately affecting the most vulnerable strata of society (Birhane, 2021; Marjanovic, Cecez-Kecmanovic, & Vidgen, 2022; Mbadiwe, 2018). I will focus on the American recidivism risk assessment algorithm *COMPAS* and the Dutch welfare fraud detection system *SyRI*. My choice to present these two cases was determined on the one hand by the role that algorithmic auditing had in unveiling the injustice, as in the case of ProPublica’s assessment of COMPAS; on the other, on the measures adopted to ensure that similar injustice would not happen again, since one response to the political scandal resulting from SyRI was the development of a new algorithmic auditing framework, FRAIA.

4.4.1 USA’s COMPAS

Correctional Offender Management Profiling for Alternative Sanctions (COMPAS) is a commercially available software, owned by the for-profit company Equivant, previously Northpointe. It has been used by US courts in Wisconsin, Florida, Michigan, in the majority of New York counties, and in the most populated county of New Mexico (Brenner et al., 2020) to assess a defendant’s likelihood of committing another crime (Mehrabi, Morstatter, Saxena, Lerman, & Galstyan, 2021), also known as recidivism risk assessment. This assessment is useful to inform decisions on pretrial detention and release (Mehrabi et al., 2021), such as whether an individual should be granted parole (Coeckelbergh, 2020).

This evaluation is a survey questionnaire based on 137 questions, among which we can find age, gender, and criminal history, while race is omitted for fairness reasons (Christin, Rosenblat, & Boyd, 2015). These can be answered by the defendant, or they can be directly pulled from criminal records (Angwin & Larson, 2016). Some questions probe the personality and beliefs of the assessed individual, such as their agreement with the statement “A hungry person has a right to steal”. Other questions, instead, investigate the personal relationships of the defendant, whose risk score will be increased if they answer positively to factors that go beyond their control such as “Was one of your parents ever sent to jail or prison”, or because of the living situation of who they associate with, as in “How many of your friends/acquaintances are taking drugs illegally?” (Angwin & Larson, 2016) The answers are sent to Equivant, to be processed through its proprietary model (Brenner et al., 2020). This generates a risk score ranging from 1 to 10 along a ‘High/Low’ continuum (Brenner et al., 2020), indicating how likely the defendant is to reoffend. The risk score has significant ramifications for the person undergoing assessment, as those who receive a medium or high risk score (between 5 and 10) are likely to be

held while awaiting trial compared to defendants with a lower risk (Feller, Pierson, Corbett-Davies, & Goel, 2016).

The stakes associated with to these scores are dramatically high, but their levels of predictive power appears to be inadequate (Angwin, Larson, Mattu, & Kirchner, 2016). Rather unsurprisingly, the internal validation studies performed by Equivant demonstrated good accuracy, and this was corroborated by at least one third-party research. However, many others have questioned COMPAS's predictivity (Angwin & Larson, 2016; Brenner et al., 2020; Dressel & Farid, 2018; Mayson, 2018; Mehrabi et al., 2021). Dressel and Farid (2018) observed that the predictions made by COMPAS were as accurate as those of non-specialists in criminal justice. Moreover, a linear classifier based on just two features (age and criminal record) proved to be as effective as COMPAS (Dressel & Farid, 2018).

COMPAS's ingerence into the private life of defendants, with its collection of 137 sensitive responses, seems unjustified not only on ethical grounds, but also for matters of effectiveness. A study by ProPublica 2016 demonstrated the lack of reliability of the system, since "only 20 percent of the people predicted to commit violent crimes actually went on to do so." Numerous jurisdictions adopted COMPAS without thoroughly evaluating its efficacy first. Moreover, since the software is proprietary, its data and algorithms are not transparent to the jurisdictions that chose to deploy it, as well as to the suspect and the court (van Dijck, 2022). The State of New York, for example, began using the tool for a trial project in 2001, and then extended it to the rest of the state by 2010 (with the exception of New York City). Not until 2012 did the state provide a detailed statistical review of the instrument. While the study revealed a 71% accuracy, it did not take into account racial differences (Angwin et al., 2016). This missing element is crucial: as shown by ProPublica 2016 significant racial disparity is present, as black defendants are twice more likely to be mislabeled as high risk than their white counterparts, who received lower average risk scores with several cases of 'false negatives' (i.e. being classified as low risk but actually reoffending within two years). In fact, in recidivism prediction, the algorithmic error rates between these two demographics were roughly the same, but in opposite directions (Mehrabi et al., 2021).

Mayson (2018) defines a risk assessment algorithm as racially biased "if it systematically over- or understates the average risk of one racial group relative to another." Since false positives were overwhelmingly black, and false negatives were overwhelmingly white, critics contended that the system displays an evident bias against black defendants (Coeckelbergh, 2020). Even when statistical studies isolated the effect of race from other factors like age and sex, and even criminal history and recidivism, this bias persisted. Black defendants were 77% more likely to be mislabeled by the algorithm as having a higher likelihood of committing a violent crime in the future, and 45% more likely to be predicted to reoffend in general (Angwin et al., 2016). A

possible reason is that, among the 137 factors analyzed by COMPAS (which, it is important to remind, did not include race) some were compounded into a proxy for race (Brenner et al., 2020; Christin et al., 2015). Possible candidate proxy variables are socio-economic status, personal beliefs, zip codes and prior arrest (Brenner et al., 2020; Christin et al., 2015).

Independent researchers do not have access to the data on which the model is built since COMPAS uses a proprietary algorithm that cannot be reviewed. It is impossible to pinpoint the specific reason of the racially disparate effect without access to the data or model details (Brenner et al., 2020). Although Northpointe provided ProPublica with the basics of their algorithm's inner workings, it refused to release the specific computations, claiming that they are a trade secret (Angwin & Larson, 2016).

Northpointe/Equivant's argued that ProPublica's study 2016 actually demonstrated that the algorithm was race neutral, given that reoffending rates were roughly the same at each level of the COMPAS scale, irrespective of race: around 60% of arrests for any crime, and 20% of arrests for violent crimes, therefore respecting predictive parity (Mayson, 2018). According to ProPublica, this is not enough: for defendants that did not actually reoffend (and therefore should have been labeled as zero risk), the algorithm subjected black defendants to a more severe treatment, as they almost twice more likely to be mislabeled as being medium or high risk compared to white defendants (P.-H. Wong, 2020). In terms of false negatives, a low-risk white defendant would be rearrested 47.7% of the time, whereas a black defendant would reoffend only 28% of the time in the same circumstance (Mayson, 2018).

This disagreement is because of different understandings of the concept of fairness: disparate treatment and disparate impact. In disparate treatment, decision-making includes protected features and final decisions are noticeably affected by them. When there is disparate impact, decisions disproportionately affect the protected groups (P.-H. Wong, 2020). However, excluding the impossible case of perfect predictions, it is mathematically impossible to achieve predictive parity, parity in false positives, and parity in false negatives at the same time when the base rate of the predicted outcome (reoffending) is not the same across racial groups. It is therefore necessary to make a conscious and value-laden choice as to which metrics to prioritize at the expense of others (Mayson, 2018).

4.4.2 The Netherlands' SyRI

Between 2013 and 2019, an automated decision system deployed by the Dutch Tax and Customs Administration to detect welfare fraud wrongly flagged around 26,000 innocent parents as child benefit fraudsters in the infamous *Toeslagenaffaire* ('child benefit scandal'), causing them significant financial and psychological distress, dis-

proportionately targeting immigrants living in impoverished areas (NJCM et al. v The Dutch State, 2020).

The controversial system, called SyRI (System Risk Indication), is a risk calculation model (or ‘welfare surveillance system’, according to Leslie 2022) devised by the Ministry of Social Affairs and Employment to estimate an individual’s likelihood of participating in benefits and tax fraud, and in labor laws transgressions (Toh, 2019). SyRI used data from numerous sources, including work and education, housing, and debt history, to generate its forecasts (Leslie, 2019).

SyRI programs are carried out in two stages, where first a risk model and comparison algorithm are applied to the dataset, and then a Ministry inquiry starts (NJCM et al. v The Dutch State, 2020). The operations start with the Information Bureau pseudonymizing the dataset, i.e. using a secret key to replace identifying information with a code. This is the ‘source file’, that is then algorithmically compared with several undisclosed risk indicators from a risk model (van Bekkum & Borgesius, 2021). While there is no publicly available information about this algorithms, there are some hypotheses concerning these risk factors taken into consideration, such as suspiciously low levels of water use; couples living together despite reportedly residing at different addresses; an individual having multiple garages and vehicles; a sharp increase in bank account balance in the last year (NJCM et al. v The Dutch State, 2020). This process singles out the pseudonyms that showed an alleged higher likelihood of committing fraud, and then their identifying information is then retrieved (Meuwese, 2020). In the following and last step, the Ministry evaluates the suspicious cases. This method of examination involves drawing “relational connections between potential hits” (van Bekkum & Borgesius, 2021), but its logic is kept secret.

SyRI came to international attention in late 2019 and early 2020, following the intervention by one of the UN’s top human rights experts, the UN Special Rapporteur on extreme poverty and human rights Philip Alston, in a high-profile court case in The Hague (Ó Fathaigh & Appelman, 2020). Alston described the case as the first legal challenge he was aware of that “fundamentally and comprehensively” contested the use of an ADM system in the welfare state on human rights grounds (Special Rapporteur on Extreme Poverty and Human Rights Philip Alston, 2019a). On 29 October 2019, the District Court of the Hague held hearings on the legality of the automated fraud-detection system (Toh, 2019). In NJCM cs/ De Staat der Nederlanden (NJCM vs the Netherlands), also known as the SyRI case (Privacy International, 2020), the Court declared declared SyRI to be in violation of Article 8 of the European Convention of Human Rights (NJCM et al. v The Dutch State, 2020), being the first ruling where a court condemned a welfare fraud detection system on the basis of the right to privacy (van Bekkum & Borgesius, 2021). The court also found that the Dutch government had failed to strike a balance between the right to

privacy and the public interest in detecting welfare fraud, and that the use of SyRI was disproportionate to the aim it sought to achieve. (Privacy International, 2020) It also affirmed that governments have a ‘special responsibility’ to safeguard human rights when implementing new technologies such as these automated profiling systems (NJCM et al. v The Dutch State, 2020).

One of the biggest faults highlighted in the SyRI judgment was a serious lack of transparency (Ó Fathaigh & Appelman, 2020), as the Court noted that the government deliberately chose not to provide any verifiable information on the nature and functioning of SyRI (Ó Fathaigh & Appelman, 2020). The reasoning of the government behind the choice not to disclose how SyRI works lies in the fear that it would make the system useless, helping fraudsters to ‘game the system’ (Katzenbach & Ulbricht, 2019). SyRI is not properly defined even by the legislation supporting it: only in a following explanatory memorandum to the legislation is present a short description, which however has been judged as too open-ended (van Bekkum & Borgesius, 2021). It did not clarify whether SyRI is a centralized or decentralized system, as it is only defined as an ‘infrastructure’ that may or may not include the second-phase analysis of the Ministry (*ibid.*). This leads to a high degree of confusion over what SyRI even is; the six NGOs that brought the government to court claim that SyRI presents features of Deep Learning and makes use of Big Data. The State contended that SyRI is instead a simple decision tree, only using data from preexisting data sets of government bodies (Meuwese, 2020). Moreover, as previously mentioned, there is no information on the risk model used or the algorithm performing the comparison calculations. The relational connections drawn between potential fraudsters are, too, derived from an unknown method (van Bekkum & Borgesius, 2021). All this considered, the court did not attach a specific technical label to SyRI, claiming it was impossible to “assess the correctness of the position of the State of the precise nature of SyRI because the State has not disclosed the risk model and the indicators of which the risk model is composed or may be composed” (NJCM et al. v The Dutch State, 2020).

This lack of transparency has clear consequences for welfare beneficiaries who were investigated and/or whose benefits were suspended, since, in Court hearings, the government disclosed that the system generated false positives, flagging innocent individuals as at-risk for fraud. While the government claimed that it made good use of these false positives, using them to increase the accuracy in its risk model, these claims cannot be substantiated (Toh, 2019) and it is doubtful that the flagged beneficiaries would have had the capacity to redress such wrongful claims. Since the risk factors to be put under welfare fraud investigation are unknown, beneficiaries have no way of anticipating whether they will lose the benefits they rely on (*ibid.*).

Claims of ethnic profiling against SyRI are sustained by the perplexing idea of including double citizenship as a risk factor, as well as the choice to selectively deploy

the system in low-income neighborhoods, creating a surveillance regime targeting poorer citizens for more intensive scrutiny at a disproportionate rate (Toh, 2019). This is unfortunately in accordance with Eubanks's (2018) findings on the increased state surveillance on the poor. SyRI was implemented in Rotterdam, the Dutch city with the highest poverty rate, along with Haarlem and Eindhoven. During the hearing, the government explicitly admitted that SyRI targeted neighborhoods showing higher rates of residents relying on welfare, even though there is no clear evidence that these neighborhoods actually show higher rates of fraud (Toh, 2019).

This led the court to assess “whether the SyRI legislation meets the requirements of necessity, proportionality and subsidiarity pursuant to Article 8 paragraph 2 ECHR”, therefore whether the purpose of SyRI is relevant enough for the community as a whole to strike a fair balance capable of justifying their invasion of private life (NJCM et al. v The Dutch State, 2020). As noted by the UN Special Rapporteur on Extreme Poverty and Human Rights (2019b), beneficiaries of social security benefits and other forms of state assistance are at risk of having to renounce to their right to privacy and data protection in order to receive the assistance they are entitled to. It is unsurprising, then, that the amount of data gathered by SyRI is astounding. As emerged during the hearings, 17 data categories were considered by the system, each encompassing a large amount of structured data sets from many different sources (NJCM et al. v The Dutch State, 2020). As such, rather than a proportionate approach, SyRI constituted an untargeted dragnet of personal data collection (NJCM et al. v The Dutch State, 2020). It is therefore a reasonable choice, for the court, to decide to interpret the Article 8 of the ECHR (the right to a private life) in the light of the principles delineated in the European General Data Protection Regulation: “[t]he court will take into account the (...) general principles of data protection from the Charter [of Fundamental Rights of the European Union] and the GDPR in its consideration of whether the SyRI legislation meets the requirements of Article 8 ECHR.” (NJCM et al. v The Dutch State, 2020; van Bekkum & Borgesius, 2021)

The court ruled that SyRI was unlawful due to its lack of proportionality between the interest in fraud detection and the level of surveillance that it subjected welfare beneficiaries to, therefore eroding the human right to privacy as operationalized by the GDPR, therefore stopping the use of digital welfare technologies on human rights grounds. The government chose not to appeal to the ruling and discontinued SyRI. While an important victory for privacy right advocates, the end of the SyRI program did not seem like a great loss for the government: as reported by a Dutch newspaper (Huisman, 2019) in and endorsed by Meuwese (2020), as of 2019 SyRI had not yet revealed even a single substantiated case of fraud. The true loss for the government was actually in terms of reputation.

The case triggered a debate over the use Automated Decision Making systems

and algorithms by governments (Ó Fathaigh & Appelman, 2020). It emerged that the government overlooked the criticism leveled against SyRI by the Dutch Council of State and the Dutch Data Protection Authority before its implementation, notably its lack of significant limitations on the amount of personal data it could collect and process. The SyRI legislation was adopted by the Parliament, without debate and without having it undergo any risk assessment (van Bekkum & Borgesius, 2021).

As a political scandal ensued, leading to resignation of the government in January 2021, the momentary discomfort of undergoing an auditing process proved to be less dramatic than the threat of being held accountable by the public for unintended consequences of AI systems. To prepare for a new regime of ongoing algorithm risk impact assessments, in 2021 the Netherlands Court of Audit created an evaluation methodology in conjunction with numerous government organizations.

In an effort to avoid past mistakes, on July 2021 the Dutch government created and launched the Fundamental Rights and Algorithms Impact Assessment (FRAIA) framework (Netherlands Court of Audit, 2022b), in collaboration with the University of Utrecht, which I will analyze in the following chapter among other algorithmic impact assessments.

SyRI is not an isolated case: it fits in within a global trend of welfare state digitalization (Special Rapporteur on Extreme Poverty and Human Rights Philip Alston, 2019b). Many governments seek to employ algorithmic solutions to reduce benefit fraud, while making their services more cost-effective. The United States, the United Kingdom, Australia, and India have all been highlighted as examples of countries that have deployed digital technology to ostensibly enhance their public welfare programs (Leslie, 2019). However, the implementation of such system has resulted in several negative consequences, among which the erosion of people's right to privacy (Leslie, 2019; van Bekkum & Borgesius, 2021). These technologies are routinely implemented without substantial engagement with the general public and welfare recipients in particular (Toh, 2019). This lack of transparency is aggravated by the challenges that sometimes arise in understanding and appealing the automated choices (Leslie, 2019). With the broad rise of digital welfare states, universal guidelines are necessary to investigate both the potential of these innovative solutions and their legitimate constraints (Bekker, 2021).

Chapter 5

Auditing for AI systems

“Digital technologies in general, and especially those central to the digital welfare state, are often presented as being both unavoidable and irresistible. (...) However, quite apart from the choices that citizens and Governments might make if they were fully informed and adequately consulted, the reality is that such decisions are all too often taken in the absence of sophisticated cost-benefit analyses. When such analyses are undertaken, they consist of financial balance sheets that ignore what might be termed the fiscally invisible intangibles that underpin human rights. Values such as dignity, choice, self-respect, autonomy, self-determination and privacy are all traded off without being factored into the overall equation, all but guaranteeing that insufficient steps will be taken to ensure their role in the new digital systems”

Special Rapporteur on Extreme Poverty and Human Rights Philip Alston (2019b)

In his *Report of the Special Rapporteur on Extreme Poverty and Human Rights*, Philip Alston drew the attention to the failures of public administrations in ensuring that the AI systems they adopted pose no large-scale risk to the population (K. Crawford & Schultz, 2019; Raji & Buolamwini, 2019; Special Rapporteur on Extreme Poverty and Human Rights Philip Alston, 2019b). Government agencies frequently fail to audit their riskiest projects until later phases of deployment, due to poor monitoring, no auditing, and unclear regulation. As governments worldwide increase their investments in AI, they should in turn increase their capacity to audit these technologies, to prevent ethical concerns from materializing. It is necessary to establish a systematized procedure for promptly assessing whether initiatives in governmental and corporate portfolios are most concerning. The implementation of an agile risk assessment checklist can ensure monitoring and stringent auditing processes are in place to decrease the risk score of the system (Kennedy, Coates, & Lindquist, 2020).

This chapter provides an oversight over the methods and rationale of algorithmic auditing and algorithmic impact assessment. These two terms, although often used interchangeably, present a slight conceptual difference: *audit* is most used in case of systems that have already been deployed; in case of early-stage interventions, aimed at providing information on the possible social and ethical impacts of the system, the expression *impact assessment* is used (Selbst, 2021). With Algorithm Impact Assessment (AIA), I will refer to both concepts, as they can both help identify and redress errors and mitigate risks at any stage of development. The life cycle of algorithms has been divided in five distinct phases by Floridi et al. (2022): design, development, evaluation, operation, and retirement. During the early phases, AIAs can consist of risk assessment analysis; in the later stages, the auditors can analyze the real-world impact of the system (Eticas Foundation, 2021). AIAs constitute a toolkit to ensure the ethical and legal compliance and algorithms (Guszcza, Rahwan, Bible, Cebrian, & Katyal, 2018), and are most effective when performed in a “timely, well-planned and periodic” manner (Panagiotopoulos & Rodrigues, 2021), in an environment of clear legal obligations and transparency.

AIAs aim at gaining additional information over the environment over which the system will be deployed, as well as the environment that characterized its development (Eticas Foundation, 2021). The assessment of regulatory compliance, accuracy, replicability, robustness, transparency, explainability, usefulness and desirability of a system is useful for a wide range of stakeholders beyond system developers: it can help regulators in assessing which AI systems are in compliance or in breach with legal standards, it can help deployers in avoid the reputational risk resulting from the use of discriminatory algorithms, and it provides the means to the general public to make informed decisions on their engagement with specific products or companies (Brown et al., 2021). In short, AIAs are especially useful as accountability mechanisms (Metcalf, Moss, Watkins, Singh, & Elish, 2021).

Risk assessments of AI systems involve moral imagination: they involve the formulation of use cases and fictional case studies of various AI applications under a mixture of different settings, available data, AI models, inputs and outputs (Sibal, 2021). These use cases are analyzed through a collaborative, multi-disciplinary approach (Ezeani et al., 2021; Kloza, Van Dijk, Casiraghi, Maymir, & Tanas, 2021) drawing technical and conceptual inputs from legal professions, academia and across different organizational functions in industry, involving “product developers, programmers, engineers, data scientists, compliance, ethics, human resources, IT infrastructure/security, operations, sales, marketing and legal teams” (Ezeani et al., 2021). From IT professionals comes a basic understanding of the technology; operation teams can provide insight into the organizational processes and business structure under which the system was developed; ethicists can clarify the import of the AI ethics codes adopted by the industry and their connection to accountability

problems and potential ethical blind spots (Hagendorff, 2021; Selbst, 2021).

The main benefit of AIAs is that they contribute to informed decision-making, while also mitigating societal concerns. In particular, informed decision-making can not only provide benefits for effective public procurement of ethical AI systems, but it also enhances entrepreneurial anticipatory thinking. Organizations and companies can better consider the implications of their planned activities, minimizing potential negative consequences in advance, resulting in higher cost-efficiency and public trust gains (Ada Lovelace Institute, AI Now Institute and Open Government Partnership, 2021). Impact assessment may also help with compliance with legal and regulatory obligations; they can also serve as proof of due diligence, even reducing legal liability. If conducted transparently, AIAs can increase public trust by demonstrating that an organization or company is socially responsible (Kloza et al., 2021). Eventually AIAs can be part of a larger cultural movement toward responsibility within the technological industry (Selbst, 2021), shifting the market in an ethical direction that will benefit society as a whole (Calo, 2017).

Given the ethically and commercially beneficial considerations connected with AI auditing, consulting companies are starting to develop their own auditing frameworks to ensure the ethical and legal compliance of their clients' AI projects. *ReD Open*, a participated spin-off of University of Milano-Bicocca, is a company that consults businesses on ethical innovation, digital transformation, and responsible adoption of AI solutions. Through its Center for Responsible Innovation, ReD Open is investing in the development of an algorithmic auditing checklist to ensure the ethical and legal compliance of its clients' AI projects. During my ongoing research internship in ReD Open, I have been part of the group of professionals and academics that developed of a tool for AI risk impact assessment, elaborating from a checklist first ideated by Valentina Cavosi in her Master's thesis (Cavosi, 2021). The development process of this framework is illustrated in Section 5.5, while a work-in-progress checklist is presented in full in Annex I.

5.1 Defining the audit methodology

The risks connected to the deployment of new AI systems are characterized by their complexity, uncertainty and ambiguity, whereby potential benefits and potential risks interconnect (International Risk Governance Center, 2017). Impact assessments are a powerful tool at the disposal of legislators and civil society when facing projects whose societal impacts that are yet unknown and difficult to measure unknown and hard-to-measure. It is the case when AI developers have the knowledge and expertise to evaluate these effects, but lack adequate incentives to generate the required information (Selbst, 2021) . We are now exactly in this situation with respect to algorithmic harms: there is a general awareness concerning the potential

harms that may be engendered by algorithmic systems, but little public expertise on how to address them, making assessments crucial for disclosing information (Selbst, 2021).

There is not yet a agreed-upon blueprint for conducting Algorithmic Impact Assessments (Eticas Foundation, 2021). The ethical research and consulting organization *Eticas* released a guide to algorithm auditing (2021) where they provided to a wider public insight into their auditing methodology. The auditing plan entails first and foremost specifying some key issues, such as the parts of the system to be audited, the main variables to take into consideration, possible intersections between variables, the groups to be monitored and their relevant variables; then, methodological questions are tackled. AIAs can be both quantitative and qualitative: in case of quantitative analysis, metrics and techniques (such as surveys, statistics) ought to be specified. In case of qualitative analysis, relevant research techniques are interviews, focus groups, ethnographic analysis, and participant or non-participant observation, among others. Both for qualitative and quantitative studies, parameters of interpretation for the results should be set, generally in terms of minimum and maximum acceptable values for accuracy, acceptability, and so on. Then, it is necessary to identify the relevant stakeholders that will participate to the study, both from inside and outside the organization whose algorithms are being audited. A first draft of the steps to be followed in the audit is discussed, including the estimated duration of the assessment procedure and the related schedule to be followed (Eticas Foundation, 2021).

At each of these critical junctures, AIAs can take a different shape: risk assessment models can vary widely according to several characteristics, such as their criteria of assessment, the party performing the assessment, whether they are mandatory or voluntarily adopted, and their scale of evaluation (Yeung, 2019). In terms of criteria of assessment, Human Rights Impact Assessment (HRIA) are focused on the evaluation of impacts upon on human rights at large, while Data Protection Impact Assessments (DPIA) mandated by the GDPR are instead concerned with the evaluation of the impact of a proposed system on data quality and security. Another difference between HRIA and DPIA regards their scale of evaluation, that is rather narrow for DPIA, which is limited to a single data processing activity, while HRIA concerns the human rights conformity of a considerable range of business operations (Yeung, 2019).

No matter whether internal or external, the audit process must always involve proactive collaboration on the side of organizational staff. In general, external audits are more objective, especially when performed by highly trained and certified auditors following a solid methodology. (Eticas Foundation, 2021) It must be taken into account, however, that the degree of cooperation of the assessed entity with the auditing staff varies, and there always exist a potential incentive to provide to

the auditors overly optimistic information that does not reflect the reality of the deployed algorithm. The aims of AIAs vary according to the body they are performed by: in case of civil society organization, the target may be enhancing public accountability and investigating negative impacts on the people they advocate for; in case of consulting firms, the auditing process is a needed step to provide to the client information on how to ameliorate their system to avoid reputational risk; an internal audit, instead, serves as a risk self-assessment that informs managerial decision-making (Eticas Foundation, 2021).

AIAs can also vary according to their timing with respect to the system's life cycle: they can be *ex-ante* or *ex-post* the system deployment. Ex-ante auditing is endorsed by the Draft AI regulation (European Commission, 2021b) for high-risk systems and is therefore likely to become an increasingly common practice. Ex-post auditing serves the role of market monitoring.

The final distinguishing feature of AIA methodology I will focus on is that of qualitative *versus* quantitative auditing. Quantitative auditing is usually delivered in the form of a questionnaire that automatically generates an impact score, while qualitative auditing often involves open-ended questions or sets of principles (Cavosi, 2022b). Quantitative and qualitative auditing present striking differences in their evaluation of complex issues such as bias.

Quantitative bias analysis is based on four steps. First, a data-based clustering is performed, paying special attention to clusters derived from the processing of protected attributes. Second, vulnerable groups are identified. Third, analysis criteria and metrics are defined, to analyze potential differences in algorithm equity across different groups. Finally, specific fairness metrics are applied to group analysis, such as impact ratio and the rates of false positives and false negatives.

Some helpful tools to perform quantitative bias assessment are the AI Fairness 360 Open Source Toolkit¹, the Aequitas Bias and Fairness Audit Toolkit², or the Algorithmic Equity Toolkit³.

The qualitative approach to bias auditing is based on a nuanced understanding of who and how is affected by its creation and use through first-hand information collected from affected persons, groups and organizations, to understand their level of acceptance and satisfaction relative to the use of AI to tackle a specific problem (Eticas Foundation, 2021).

An example of qualitative audit is Eticas's external audit of *VioGén* (2022a), a system that assesses a woman's risk of becoming victim of intimate partner violence. Interviews with women who underwent the *VioGén* assessment after reporting their aggressor to the police revealed a systematic reduction of risk level (and therefore level of protection) for those without children.

¹<https://aif360.mybluemix.net/>

²<http://www.datasciencepublicpolicy.org/projects/aequitas/>

³<https://aekit.pubpub.org/>

Figure 5.1: The five phases of AIAs. Image created by (Cavosi, 2022a)

As described by Cavosi (2022a), algorithmic assessments generally involve five phases. The first is the system description phase. This includes a report of the project the system is deployed for: its aims, expected use and benefits. The model should be described in terms of its defined characteristics, its inputs, outputs, and level of autonomy. The origin of training and use data should be specified, as well as the relevant stakeholders. The second phase is that of risk assessment, that differs according to the method and scope of the AIA: taking again the example of HRIA and DPIA, the metrics used to evaluate the risk in terms of either human rights impacts or data security. To evaluate risk, checklists may be used: in terms of quantitative risk assessments, multiple choice questions about system risk can be assigned specific scores, and total final score indicates the level of risk assigned to the system. Other types of checklists, instead, may simply present a list of risky system characteristics: if the system displays one or more of the mentioned issues, then the system may be considered high risk. It is the case of the draft AI regulation (European Commission, 2021b) and its *ladder* approach to risk.

The third phase is impact evaluation, that can include human, social, and environmental impact. Central questions are whether the system will affect human autonomy, dignity and privacy, but also on societal values such as social cohesion and sustainability. Assessing the impact also entails more technical considerations on the system's robustness and safety, and the consideration of transparency and accountability mechanisms put in place by the organisation.

The fourth phase is concerned with risk mitigation: once the possible future harms of the AI system are discovered, the algorithmic auditing should lead to actionable insight on how to implement adequate measures to avoid negative consequences. However, this element is the least commonly featured in algorithmic auditing checklists (Cavosi, 2022a), probably because it requires a level of fine-tuning to the assessed organization's environment and system that is problematic to perform in the predetermined fashion of checklists, requiring instead the hands-on involvement of consultants.

Finally, the system should be revised periodically, since several long-term and incremental impacts can only be detected some time after the large-scale implementation of AI systems. If new risks are identified, the risk mitigation procedure should

be performed again.

The Eticas guideline to risk auditing, too, identifies five stages to algorithmic auditing, but there is no substantial overlapping with Cavosi's (2022a) framework. These five stages are the *Preliminary study*, *Mapping*, *Analysis plan*, *Analysis*, and *Analysis report*

At any phase of the auditing process, the analysis may come to a halt due to unforeseen circumstances. In these cases, the auditing team should be in a position to stop the assessment while issues are being dealt with, therefore rethinking or readjusting the analysis plan that had guided the auditing process thus far (Eticas Foundation, 2021).

As audits are based on gathering information of an algorithm's behavior when it is applied in a specific setting, (Brown et al., 2021) different AIAs have different targets. The central targets in the assessment of Automated Decision-Making systems are those of bias, privacy, and general human rights considerations.

The International Risk Governance Center identified key questions for the effective governance of such algorithms: "With what kind of data/datasets DMLAs work and how to handle privacy and biases while pursuing accuracy; what is the learning context and what kind of learning takes place and where; and to what extent can and should algorithms explain or account for their decisions." (International Risk Governance Center, 2018) In particular, information should be collected on the underlying decision-making process of the algorithm, the level of human control, the domain of deployment and its key issues, and the purpose of the algorithmic decision-making (*ibid.*).

5.2 Human Rights, Ethical and Social Impact Assessment (HRESIA)

Drawing from Panagiotopoulos and Rodrigues (2021), legal compliance, ethical alignment, and social responsibility are critical components to ensuring that AI deployment and use are beneficial. Legal compliance refers to technology-specific legislation, data protection and intellectual property, but also human rights regulations. This is the domain of impact assessments and conformity assessments.

Ethical alignment addresses ethical challenges early on, using strategies such as ethics by design, ethical impact assessments, and the application of ethical guidelines. Such ethical considerations cannot replace regulation, but they do encourage the reflection and incorporation of ethical considerations and public perceptions into corporate strategy and public policy-making. (Panagiotopoulos & Rodrigues, 2021)

Social responsibility encompasses the minimisation of harm and the maximization well-being at the societal level. Performing a similar calculus is complex due to not easily quantifiable harms and benefits arising from AI systems. Therefore, rather

than relying on approximate and dehumanizing balancing acts between benefit and damage, initiatives such as Human Rights Impact Assessments (HRIA), public involvement and public disclosure aim at addressing in advance these issues embedding social considerations such as human rights and public opinion. (Panagiotopoulos & Rodrigues, 2021)

AI ethical failure is far more widespread than previously imagined, with the majority of incidents occurring in the last five years. This demonstrates the urgent need for new governance structures capable of guaranteeing that AI systems are legally compliant, technically robust, and conform to ethical standards and principles (Floridi et al., 2022).

Using a value-oriented approach, the evaluation should concentrate on the social effect of AI systems. This includes the impacts on a number of human rights and ethical values (Mantelero, 2018).

Several scholars and organizations have proposed various forms of algorithmic impact assessment to identify the human rights, ethical, and social implications of AI systems and try to alleviate those concerns in the design and operation of algorithmic systems *ex ante* (Yeung, 2019) .

A Socio-economic Impact Assessment (SIA), for example, is “a structured way of showing a proposal’s advantages and disadvantages for society as a whole and for various parties.” (Panagiotopoulos & Rodrigues, 2021) An example of an auditing question in a SIA checklist would be:

“Are there provisions to assess and alleviate specific impacts on vulnerable groups (e.g., children, migrants, homeless, those accessing welfare services) that may experience socio-economic disadvantage from the AI deployment and use?”

Panagiotopoulos and Rodrigues (2021)

On the other hand, Ethics-Based Auditing (EBA) is “a process of judging the ethical impacts of research and innovation activities, outcomes and technologies that incorporates both means for a contextual identification and evaluation of these ethical impacts and development of a set of guidelines or recommendations for remedial actions aiming at mitigating ethical risks and enhancing ethical benefits, typically in consultation with stakeholders.” (Panagiotopoulos & Rodrigues, 2021)

This process involves systematic moral considerations about the ethical value of a particular initiative (Casiraghi et al., 2021). Rather than codifying ethics, EBA is a tool for auditors to detect, visualize, and explain whatever normative values are inscribed in a specific system. (Mökander & Floridi, 2021)

While standards for EBA are not yet established, there exists a variety of well-established techniques to draw from . For example, functionality audits assess the

logic underlying an algorithmic decision. Code audits involve the analysis of the source code, and impact audits evaluate the repercussions of an algorithm’s deployment (Mökander & Floridi, 2021). These interdisciplinary methodologies demonstrate that ethics may be useful in an integrated impact assessment process, not as a replacement for a technical and legal evaluation based on industry norms and basic rights, but rather as an “argumentative support” (Casiraghi et al., 2021). Another advantage of EBA is that, by requiring that ethical principles and standards of conduct be explicitly expressed and publicly disclosed, it assures that organizational actions are open to more scrutiny, which may reduce the phenomena of ethics shopping (as described in section 3.4.1) (Floridi et al., 2022).

While EBA is a value-based approach, rights-based alternatives show promise as well. In contrast to ethical and social frameworks, which involve a contested theoretical inputs, proliferation of standards, and the potential of ethics-washing, human rights provide “a well-defined benchmark” (Mantelero, 2018).

Human Rights Impact Assessment (HRIA) is defined as “a process to discover, measure and/or map human rights impacts and risks.” (Panagiotopoulos & Rodrigues, 2021) This should be done before the development of the system and should include an assessment of whether risks to human rights can be mitigated or successfully justified. Furthermore, measures for receiving external input on AI systems that may infringe on basic rights should be put in place (High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, 2019b).

Possible questions for a HRIA, as taken from Panagiotopoulos and Rodrigues’s *Framework for Regulating AI in the Public Sector 2021* are:

1. “Is there a requirement/are public authorities encouraged to carry out human rights impact assessments (HRIAs) on AI systems acquired, developed and/or deployed by them?”
2. “Is there a legal framework to set out the procedure for carrying out HRIAs?”
3. “Does the assessment evaluate the potential impact of the AI system on human rights taking into account the nature, context, scope, and purpose of the system?”
4. “Where a public authority has not yet procured or developed an AI system, is this assessment carried out prior to the acquisition and/or development of that system?”
5. “Do the HRIAs include a meaningful external review of AI systems, either by an independent oversight body, e.g., National Human Rights Structures (NHRs) or an external researcher/auditor with relevant expertise?”

The human rights impact assessment procedure is meant to address the entirety of human rights at once: doing so, each individual right are not accorded the same attention that they would be given if assessed individually (as is the case of the right of privacy in DPIA) (Kloza et al., 2021). Another issue with HRIA is that human rights are generally protected as individual rights, yet the dangers from Big Data and AI are predominantly social in nature (Mantelero, 2018). Following Yeung (2019), “the inability of rights to provide a comprehensive response to the threats posed by AI technologies is more deeply rooted in the inherent limitations of rights-based approaches effectively to address systematic harms that are experienced primarily at a collective, societal level, rather than at the level of the individual right-holder.”

As proposed by Mantelero (2018), “the Human Rights Impact Assessment in data protection should evolve into a more complete Human Rights, Ethical and Social Impact Assessment (HRESIA).”

The HRESIA focuses on social concerns and the public dimension through public involvement, individual and group empowerment, and non-discrimination and equitable participation throughout the evaluation process. These features remain instead unaddressed by data protection regulations. Recital 75 of the GDPR mentions the danger of “significant economic or social disadvantage” as a result of data processing, and yet neither the GDPR nor the DPIA models go into detail on societal considerations of data processing (Mantelero, 2018). HRESIA, instead, puts into action the EU legislator’s objective to defend both the right to the personal data protection, but also the “fundamental rights and freedoms of natural persons”, as stated among the main aims of the Regulation and the specific provisions on risk management.” (*ibid.*)

5.3 Drawbacks and challenges

Impact assessments, like other governance processes, have limits. They may, for example, fail to recognize particular harms, or they can turn ethical considerations into a simple tick-box exercise (Mökander & Floridi, 2022). AIAs need robust institutional support and a conducive atmosphere to ignite ethical debate and provide verifiable documentation (Kloza et al., 2021). In particular, AIAs require guidance and technical support from regulators, in the form of sufficient training, guidelines, explanations, and advice, as well as fostering a spirit of collaboration between stakeholders, both external and internal (*ibid.*)

Audit integrity concerns, such as the efficacy of the process itself, can become problematic in the absence of enforced auditing standards (B. Mittelstadt, 2019). This is a structural issue that hinders algorithmic accountability, together with the absence of suitable laws to ensure compliance with audit recommendations. A legislative framework can provide appropriate standards for audit integrity and for

implementing audit results into practice (Ugwudike, 2022).

Without strong incentives or regulation, many algorithms may be not auditable, and those developing and deploying them may be unwilling to make a change towards more transparency. There are numerous causes behind limited auditability, which could be linked to the nature of the algorithm itself, its context of deployment as well as trade secrets and national security (Eticas Foundation, 2021). Concerning the perception and acceptability of audits in organizational contexts, there is always a possibility of adversarial behaviour: the organization or AI systems being audited may try to deceive the auditor by withholding information or temporarily altering their behavior (Floridi et al., 2022). This can happen because assessments are performed on the basis of information that only those who are responsible for the project may have access to. A system that relies on the private sector's good faith for participation risks being undercut by its incentives and institutional rationale (Selbst, 2021). Furthermore, even when audits show problems in AI systems, power imbalances may prevent remedial actions from being performed (Floridi et al., 2022).

Critics of AIAs claim that they burden organizations excessively, generating additional cost and delays in decision-making, or even stalling the deployment of the system in question. Instead of being quick, simple, and inexpensive, the AIA process is complex in practice and of low applicability to real-world scenarios (Kloza et al., 2021). To be effective, AIA regulation must foresee how such procedures would be mediated via the private sector institutional framework (Selbst, 2021).

Because most AI systems in use or development today are proprietary, firms have insufficient incentives for opening up their systems to external examination, even in case it anticipates potential societal repercussions and offers way to minimize them (Calo, 2017; Selbst, 2021). Given the extent to which an AIA regulation would rely on good faith participation by regulated enterprises, AIAs must function in tandem with the field rather than in opposition to it. As a result, regulators must better understand the AI industry, including technology, organizational culture, and state-of-the-art documentation standards (Selbst, 2021).

In sum, while AIAs may be a sensible regulatory policy in theory, they pose practical difficulties when we consider that they will inevitably be implemented by the very corporations that are behind the development of AI technology. Because the knowledge and information inherent inside the sector itself is required for successful risk assessment, the industry will have a stake in its own governance (Selbst, 2021).

Aside from the legal and corporate context, AIAs present some difficulties in and of themselves. For example, when analyzing the effects of algorithmic decision support on human autonomy, the deskilling of human decision-makers supported by AI may need to be studied over an extensive period of time. Because of their ability to continuously learn and evolve, ML algorithms add uncertainty into how and why decisions are made, and the challenges associated with opacity and the allocation

of responsibility will only rise in the future, as technical complexity increases. The resulting gap between the design and operation of algorithms on the one hand, and our knowledge of their ethical implication on the other hand, can lead potential harm to go undetected (B. D. Mittelstadt et al., 2016).

Although ethics-based AIAs like HRESIA can help ensure the ethical alignment of AI systems, they are far from being a sufficient solution. It is still impossible to predict the totality of long-term and indirect effects of the functioning of an AI system. While HRESIA can be a tool for organisations in ensuring the compliance of AI systems to ethical guidelines, the dilemma of how to prioritize amongst incompatible values remains inherently political (Floridi et al., 2022).

5.4 A selection of AI auditing frameworks

In this section, I will go over three different AI auditing frameworks, each displaying unique characteristics.

The *Canada AIA* was the first algorithmic impact assessment model developed and made available by a national government already in 2019. Its completion is mandated by law for all public agencies making procurement decisions. Just like the auditing framework developed by the ReD Open / MUDI Lab team, the Canada AIA is an interactive, web-based checklist where numerical scores are assigned to each answer to provide a specific risk classification at the end of the assessment.

capAI, developed by Floridi et al. in 2022, is based in full on the High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence’s *Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI* (2019b) and the European draft AI act (2021b), of which it represents a state-of-the-art compliance framework. It is an example of value-based framework.

The Fundamental Rights and Algorithm Impact Assessment, also known as *FRAIA*, is a checklist developed by the Dutch Court of Audit. It was ideated to guide AI procurement and deployment choices in the public sector, providing to the prospective users all necessary information to understand the implications and risk connected to a specific AI system. Other than being a right-based framework, *FRAIA* is especially interesting as it assumes that the checklist will be filled by a multidisciplinary team, indicating for each question which type of professionals should be consulted to answer.

5.4.1 Canada AIA

The Canadian AIA⁴ was instituted by Canada’s Treasury Board to instruct other agencies on responsible procurement of AI-based systems. Its development in 2019

⁴<https://www.canada.ca/en/government/system/digital-government/digital-governmentinnovations/responsible-use-ai/algorithmic-impact-assessment.html>

Risk Profile

Is the project within an area of intense public scrutiny (e.g. because of privacy concerns) and/or frequent litigation?

- Yes
- No

Are clients in this line of business particularly vulnerable?

- Yes
- No

Are stakes of the decisions very high?

- Yes
- No

Will this project have major impacts on staff, either in terms of their numbers or their roles?

- Yes
- No

Figure 5.2: Screenshot from the Canada AIA website showing a series of closed-ended questions

was prompted by the entry into law of Canada's *Directive on Automated Decision-Making*, that mandates ex-ante assessments for all government agencies intending to acquire and deploy an AI decision-making system and requires that the audit reports be made public. In general, its aim is to ensure that AI systems are implemented in a way that reduces risks and results in more efficient, accurate, coherent, and interpretable decisions. The AIA consists of a total of 77 questions: 44 questions aim at evaluating the risk of the system, and 33 aim at evaluating its current risk mitigation strategies. Closed-ended questions can be answered on either a dichotomous scale, a Likert scale, or a nominal, multiple-choice scale. For open-ended questions, a blank box is present.

The questions aiming at evaluating risk, for example, concern the typology of the system, its impact on dimensions such as human rights, the environment and the economy, as well as the use of data and its source, and the type of automated decision that will result from the system. To assess risk mitigation strategies, questions entail the consultation and inclusion of stakeholders and experts, the decision-making and data governance procedures. Each answer corresponds to a specific score that, at the

The impacts that the decision will have on the rights or freedoms of individuals will likely be:

High impact ▾

Please describe why the impacts resulting from the decision are (as per selected option above).

The impacts that the decision will have on the health and well-being of individuals will likely be:

Choose... ▾

Choose...

Little to no impact

Moderate impact

High impact

Very high impact

Figure 5.3: Screenshot from the Canada AIA website showing both closed-ended questions on a Likert scale, and open-ended questions

end of the questionnaire, will indicate the level of impact of the system. Other than the system risk score, the AIA provides additional information on possible revisions to be made to the AI system.

Critics of the Canadian AIA point to the limits of its closed-ended questions, that are perceived as rigid and as hindering autonomous reflection on the system at hand. Still, the framework displays several strengths: it is easy to perform, it is fast (requiring only around 35 minutes to complete), it responsively suggests risk mitigation procedures, and it enables public oversight over the audits.

5.4.2 capAI

capAI stands for *conformity assessment procedure for AI systems*. It is an algorithmic impact assessment described by its authors as “a procedure for conducting conformity assessment of AI systems in line with the EU Artificial Intelligence Act”. (Floridi et al., 2022) It provides an independent and quantifiable assessment of AI systems in accordance with the proposed draft AI regulation, and gives to its users guidance on the translation of high-level ethical principles into a structured process than can determine a more ethical design, development, deployment and use of AI.

Unlike the Canadian AIA, which is only applicable *ex ante*, capAI has been designed to be useful at each of the five steps of AI life cycle (design, development, evaluation, operation, retirement). It comprises of three documents: an internal review protocol, that provides organizations with a tool for risk management and quality assurance; a summary datasheet, that could one day be submitted to a future EU public database of high-risk systems; an external scorecard, to communicate the results of the audit to customers and stakeholders.

The procedural blueprint of AI can be summarized as follows:

1. “Describe the purpose of the AI systems”
2. “Define the standards or verifiable criteria based on which the AI systems should be assessed”
3. “Disclose the process, including a full account of the data, data use and parties involved”
4. “Assess the impact the AI systems have on humans and the environment”
5. “Evaluate whether the benefits and mitigated risks justify the use of AI systems”
6. “Determine the extent to which the system is reliable and transparent”
7. “Document the results and considerations”

8. “Reflect and evaluate, i.e., create a feedback loop”

capAI is a tool for organisations to ensure that their AI system is in compliance with specific ethical principles, and as such is a form of Ethics-Based Auditing. It was designed to be holistic, traceable, accountable, strategic, dialectic, continuous, and driving re-design. Following research on the most common ethical failures of AI, which involved 106 case studies, capAI provides the wisdom to avoid repeating those mistakes.

5.4.3 FRAIA

The Fundamental Rights and Algorithm Impact Assessment (FRAIA)⁵ is a rights-based framework that assesses the level of risk posed by an AI system, proposing in turn mitigating measures. It was created in collaboration with the University of Utrecht, and launched in March 2022.

FRAIA is a useful tool for fostering dialogue both between developers and users and AI, and within the stakeholders in the system implementation. This prevents the use of potentially dangerous algorithms. FRAIA is fine-tuned as a tool for government organizations wishing to deploy a given algorithm, and as such is designed to ensure that potential issues are addressed early and in a systematic fashion. This way, it is ensured that algorithms would not be adopted in a haste, without first examining their accuracy, efficacy, and risks. The mechanism proposed by the FRAIA to attain this goal includes a step-by-step evaluation of all key processes involved in the use of an algorithm, i.e. its preparation (Part 1), input and throughput (Part 2), output (Part 3), and a final comprehensive overview (Part 4).

The FRAIA consists of a large number of questions regarding the main the issues that should be discussed whenever a government organizations is considering the use of an algorithm. These discussions should take place within a multidisciplinary team, with people of different backgrounds and organizational roles. Once completed, with all answers and key considerations noted down, the FRAIA can serve as a ‘reference material’ to inform the decision-making process surrounding the design and implementation of the system, and to refer back to at any critical juncture.

Part 1 of the FRAIA clarifies the rationale, the underlying motives, and desired outcomes of the use of a specific algorithm. The reasoning behind its procurement (or development) and deployment is evaluated in terms of the values underlying it, which are pinpointed through a multidisciplinary group reflection. Only then it makes sense to answer questions about potential impacts on human rights. As for each step, the answers provided here are useful for answering to the ones presented in the following parts.

⁵<https://www.government.nl/documents/reports/2021/07/31/impact-assessment-fundamental-rights-and-algorithms>

Figure 5.4: Flow chart of the topics covered in Part 1. Image from Netherlands Court of Audit (2022b)

An example question in this section is, “*What is the objective that the use of the algorithm needs to achieve? What is the main objective here, and what are secondary objectives?*” (Netherlands Court of Audit, 2022b)

Part 2 of this FRAIA concerns the ‘What?’ of the project. This part is divided into two sub-parts, 2A and 2B, respectively concerned with the input of the algorithm and the algorithm itself.

Investigating the input of the algorithm entails questioning what data is used, as in Question 2.A.2.1: “*What type of data is going to be used as input for the algorithm and from which sources has the data been taken?*”

Investigating the algorithm itself means asking questions about the type of algorithm used, its ownership and control mechanisms, its accuracy, and transparency and explainability levels.

Part 3 is about the *implementation, use and supervision* of the algorithm, which are the critical junctures during which algorithmic biases can emerge. as decisions are made “about (handling) the algorithm’s output, about the question which output the algorithm generates, how that may play a role in policy or decision-making, and how that can be supervised” (Netherlands Court of Audit, 2022b).

The fourth and final part of the FRAIA provides guidance on assessing algorithmic impact through a ‘fundamental rights roadmap’, which aids both in the identification of potential negative effects on human rights, and in the discussion on prevention and mitigation of these harms.

At the end of step 4, if necessary, mitigating measures should be applied. Then, the process should be repeated until the FRAIA has been completed successfully, that is, all questions have been answered in a comprehensive manner, and the fun-

Figure 5.5: Flow chart of the topics covered in Part 2. Image from Netherlands Court of Audit (2022b)

Figure 5.6: Flow chart of the topics covered in Part 3. Image from Netherlands Court of Audit (2022b)

Figure 5.7: Flow chart of the topics covered in Part 4. Image from Netherlands Court of Audit (2022b)

damental rights assessment in Part 4 has a positive result.

5.5 Devising an AI auditing checklist with MUDI Lab and ReD Open

The current scenario in the regulation of AI, characterized by the global growing importance of the GDPR and the influence already exerted by the draft AI Act, points to a future where algorithmic impact assessments could become compulsory for high risk systems. AIAs are tools that help developers, deployers and users of AI in gaining awareness on the risks that AI systems may entail, evaluating their impact on ethical and legal aspects. Impact assessments are particularly useful and desirable in the development phase as they can point out to possible ethical risks before they occur, leading to mitigation procedures. However, all phases of the development, deployment, use (and even discontinuing) of the systems, when done responsibly, call for ongoing assessment of risk. The existence of autonomous learning capabilities on behalf of the system suggest that possible ethical risks are always changing and may unexpectedly appear over time, for example if the system starts to display biased decision-making patterns.

These numerous benefits led to public and private funding being provided for the

development of new assessment strategies. I was involved in a hybrid research group between the ethical design company ReD Open SRL and the Bicocca MUDI Lab. My direct colleagues for the elaboration of the AI auditing checklist were Valentina Cavosi and Riccardo Angius, and our work was carried out under the oversight and guidance of the CEO Massimo Manzari and the Scientific Coordinator Prof. Eng. Federico Cabitza. Together, we performed literature review and collected assessment frameworks to explore the variety of methods adopted. The impact assessments taken into consideration made reference not only to the European context, but also extra-European frameworks.

The checklist I present in Annex I draws from the Algorithmic Impact Assessment checklist developed by Valentina Cavosi at the *Modelling Uncertainty, Decision and Interaction* (MUDI) laboratory at the University of Milano-Bicocca in 2020, under the supervision of Prof. Eng. Cabitza (Cavosi, 2021). It is a web-based questionnaire, hosted on the platform *LimeSurvey*.⁶

For the purpose of this thesis, I translated the AIA checklist from Italian to English and extended it. This entailed performing a gap analysis compared to the new auditing frameworks developed in the meantime by organizations, institutions and companies in this field, therefore updating it to the latest standards. This extension was both *vertical* (i.e., adding new response options to the preexisting items, defining new criteria of conditional routing and of evaluation) and *horizontal* (i.e., adding new items or item groups, as to cover issues that were only marginally considered in the original AIA).

The tool is organized following the guidelines for a Trustworthy AI defined by the European Commission's High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, 2019b). A trustworthy AI system is defined as the one possessing the requirements of *Human agency and oversight; Technical robustness and safety; Privacy and data governance; Transparency; Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness*, and *Societal and environmental well-being*. As such, the AIA performs an analysis of the impact of the system on each of these seven requirements, classifying the system as either *Low Risk*, *Medium Risk* or *High Risk*. This reflects the risk-based approach proposed in the draft AI regulation (European Commission, 2021b).

The tool comprises of four sections:

1. The description of the system
2. The risk evaluation and classification of the system
3. The self-assessment of the seven requirements defined by the European Commission in the *Ethical Guidelines for Trustworthy AI* (2019b)

⁶<https://www.limesurvey.org/>

4. The survey feedback

The result is an Algorithmic Impact Assessment checklist that can be used internationally to help the developers, providers and those who want to adopt AI-based systems understand the risks that these systems may involve. This tool evaluates the system's impact on legal and ethical dimensions, with the goal of assisting in the reduction of any potential risks connected to its deployment.

Conclusion

The introduction of AI ethical considerations into public policy is relatively new (Ada Lovelace Institute, AI Now Institute and Open Government Partnership, 2021), but it is gaining momentum. According to an analysis of AI Ethics publications (Morley, Elhalal, et al., 2021), by 2021, more than 80% of all documents had been published less than four years before, indicating a rapid increase of interest for this discipline. This popularization has a beneficial spillover effect, and I suggest that the field of algorithmic justice could be the arena for the development of new ethical approaches to automated decision-making. This is because the domain of justice is distinguished by the tension between principles, especially the principle of prevention of harm and the principles of privacy or human autonomy (High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, 2019b), which are put at the center of the debate on the acceptability of predictive policing and its associated surveillance activities. Value-based assessment tries to ensure that such tensions (Whittlestone et al., 2019) do not result in a zero-sum game: a poor benchmark score might spark out-of-the-box thinking on behalf of the system developer to find unexplored solutions, to minimize risk and maximize societal gain all while respecting the basic values examined.

Similarly, the cautionary tale of the Dutch *Toeslagenaffaire* mentioned in the Introduction and explored in Section 4.4.2 may have a silver lining. As a political scandal ensued, leading to resignation of the government, the temporary discomfort of undergoing an auditing process proved to be less dramatic than the threat of being held accountable by the public for unintended consequences of AI systems. To prepare for a new regime of ongoing algorithm risk impact assessments, in 2021 the Netherlands Court of Audit created an evaluation methodology in conjunction with numerous government organizations. On May 18, 2022, the Court issued a report (Netherlands Court of Audit, 2022) evaluating the algorithms adopted by the Ministry of Justice, the National Office for Identity Data, the Security Directorate-General for Migration, and the police. Six out of nine were unable to achieve the standards outlined in the auditing framework for *Governance and accountability, Data and model, Privacy* and *IT general controls*. The findings forced the Dutch State Secretary for Digitisation to take urgent measures to rectify the flaws discovered and restore faith in the governance of algorithmic systems.

The relevance of risk impact assessments appears to be also an issue of political

legitimacy, which is compromised if the justice system fails to safeguard the citizens it is entrusted to serve and protect. That is why, rather than investigating potential failures in AI systems only after they have caused harm, this thesis advocates and offers the means for a benchmark and risk impact assessment analysis to be performed before the deployment of algorithms and throughout their lifespan, through the impact assessment checklist presented in Annex I.

Stringent social acceptability requirements for AI systems, to be met *ex-ante*, raise concerns about stifling innovation: promising but imperfect algorithms may be rejected repeatedly, discouraging developers. However, a precautionary approach promotes sustainable innovation, which is the constant creation and improvement of solutions that will change our lives for the better. The proposed AI Ethics auditing ensures that the ‘promising, but imperfect’ solutions may turn into promising and socially valuable systems thanks to actionable recommendations.

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Annex I. Checklist Prototype

Foreword

What is the purpose of the Artificial Intelligence impact evaluation tool?

This self-assessment tool was designed to aid developers, providers and those who want to use systems based on artificial intelligence (AI) to be aware of the risks that these systems can entail. This tool allows for the evaluation of the impact of the system on legal and ethical dimensions, with the aim of assisting in the mitigation of potential risks associated with its deployment.

The tool is organized following the guidelines for a Trustworthy AI defined by the European Commission's High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence. (High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, 2019b) A trustworthy AI system is defined as the one possessing the following requirements:

1. Human agency and oversight
Including fundamental rights, human agency, and human oversight
2. Technical robustness and safety
Including resilience to attack and security, fall back plan and general safety, accuracy, reliability, and reproducibility
3. Privacy and data governance
Including respect for privacy, quality and integrity of data, and access to data
4. Transparency
Including traceability, explainability and communication
5. Diversity, non-discrimination, and fairness
Including the avoidance of unfair bias, accessibility and universal design, and stakeholder participation
6. Societal and environmental well-being
Including sustainability and environmental friendliness, social impact, society, and democracy

7. Accountability

Including auditability, minimisation and reporting of negative impact, trade-offs, and redress

When is it advised to perform an impact evaluation of one's AI system?

Performing an impact evaluation of AI is important during the development of the system, before its distribution (to avoid potentially costly errors) and periodically (after deployment) to evaluate the system's long-term consequences. It is important to evaluate how AI develops over time and influences the environment in which it is used. It is possible to establish a time interval for repeated evaluation (e.g., once every six months, once every year...), but there are also specific situations calling for a reevaluation of the system, such as the introduction of new datasets, or when the system is applied to a different aim from the one it was developed for.

How does the tool work?

The tool comprises of the following sections/four sections:

1. The first section is dedicated to the description of the system
2. The second section is dedicated to the risk evaluation and classification of the system
3. The third section is dedicated to the self-assessment of the 7 requirements defined by the European Commission in the ethical guidelines for trustworthy AI: Human agency and oversight; Technical robustness and safety; Privacy and Data Governance; Transparency; Diversity, non-discrimination, and fairness; Societal and environmental well-being; Accountability.
4. The fourth section is dedicated to feedback: once the questionnaire is completed, the user will be shown a summary page including:
 - a. The level of risk posed by the AI system
 - b. The impact of the AI system on each of the 7 requirements (so that it will be straightforward to self-assess which aspects of the system will have to undergo revision)
 - c. A summary of requirements
 - d. The possibility to download the feedback provided by the tool

Section 1. Description of the AI System

1.1 Name of the organisation:

1.2 Title of the project:

1.3 Phase of the project:

- Analysis
- Design
- Development
- Deployment
- Operation

1.4 Provide a description of the project:

- Provide an overview of the system and its aim. Describe its design in its entirety, the data used and, in case of automated learning, the way the system is trained. Moreover, describe which stakeholders are affected and how they interact with the system.

1.5 Which advantages does the use of the AI system offer?

? Choose all options that apply

- Enhancement of decision quality (the system is more precise)
- Cost efficiency
- Time efficiency
- The system is safer
- The system is more objective and unbiased
- The system performs tasks that human being would not be able to perform in a reasonable time
- The system allows for a service that would otherwise be impossible
- The system contributes to the achievement of individual or societal wellbeing
- Optimal resource management (better environmental sustainability)
- Other

Section 2. Risk Assessment of the AI System

What is your level of agreement with the following statements? (1 = Totally disagree, 6 = Totally agree)

*2.1 The AI system is used in a new social domain

? Reference: "Is the AI used in a new (social) domain?" [5]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*2.2 The AI system acts within a sensitive social field (for example access to goods, benefits and services, financial domain, safety, health, surveillance, right/intellectual property etc.)

? Adapted from: "Does the application take place on a sensitive subject?" [5], "Is the solution intended for use in an area of public interest?" [16], "Is the projects within an area of intense public scrutiny (e.g. privacy concerns) and/or frequent litigation?" [10] and "Risk Type: access to goods, benefits and services.." [2]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*2.3 A new type of AI technology is used

Reference: "Is a new for of AI technology used?" [5]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*2.4 The AI system has a high degree of autonomy

Reference: "Does the AI have a high degree of autonomy?" [5]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*2.5 The system will substitute a decision that would otherwise be made by a human

Reference: "Will the system be replacing a decision that would otherwise be made by a human?" [5]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*2.6 The AI system makes complex decisions

Reference: "Does the AI make complex decisions?" [5]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*2.7 The AI system is used in a complex environment

Reference: "Is the AI used in a complex environment?" [5]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*2.8 The data used or generated by the system entail, at least in part, the personal data of the affected subject

References: "Are sensitive personal data used?" [5], "Does the data used or generated by the solution contain any biographical or sensitive information?" [16] and "Does the decision deal with special categories of data, as defined by applicable legal norms?" [13]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*2.9 The AI system makes decisions that have a significant impact on people or legal entities, entailing legal consequences for them

🔍 Reference: "Does the AI make decision that have a significant impact on people or entities or have legal consequences for them?" [5], "Will this project have major impact on staff, either in terms of their numbers or their roles?" [10] and "In the cases where the application of an automated decision-making system is likely to result in a high risk to people's rights and freedom, the user shall carry out an automated decision impact assessment prior to the deployment." [1]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*2.10 The outputs of the AI system are no longer understandable by the developer

🔍 Reference: "Are the results of the AI application no longer (fully) understandable?" [5]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*2.11 The deployment of the AI system can cause physical or psychological harm to a subject

1 2 3 4 5 6

*2.12 The use of the AI system can cause damage to property

1 2 3 4 5 6

*2.13 The system is used by a different organizational branch from the one that designed it

🔍 Reference: "Is the system used by a different part of the organization than the one who developed it?" [5]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*2.14 The deployment of the AI system can entail unjust results (decisions) or discrimination (according to age, gender, income, sexual orientation, race, disability etc.) towards some subjects, for example on the workplace or in accessing services

Reference: "An automated decision impact assessment referred to in paragraph 2 shall in any case be required in case of: potential unfair bias or discrimination towards subjects, including price and employment discrimination or unfair differential access to services" [1]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*2.15 The use of the AI system may result in a loss of control by the subject

Reference: "An automated decision impact assessment referred to in paragraph 2 shall in any case be required in case of: potential loss of control or agency for the subject, including economic or psychological manipulation." [1]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*2.16 The AI system acts on a large scale and makes decisions that can affect communities or society as a whole

Reference: "An automated decision impact assessment referred to in paragraph 2 shall in any case be required in case of: large scale application of automated decision-making, including profiling and systematic monitoring, that may affect communities or the society as a whole." [1]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*2.17 There is not yet a legal basis that explicitly and clearly allows for the use of an algorithm equivalent to the one being assessed

Reference: "Answering this question involves finding out whether there is a legal basis that explicitly and clearly allows for the use of an algorithm and renders this use sufficiently foreseeable" [15]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*2.18 The model is not continuously updated to ensure its compliance with current legislation

Reference: "Is the model updated at regular intervals to bring it into line with current legislation?" [14]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*2.19 An 'exit strategy' is not available in case the algorithm is no longer desired/feasible/ relevant

Reference: "If it should become clear in future that the algorithm is no longer desired/feasible/ relevant, is there an exit strategy?" [14]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*2.20 The risks of decommissioning the AI system have not been predicted

Reference: "The risks of decommissioning the AI system have been addressed" [9]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*2.21 The activities of the AI system entail facial recognition

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*2.21.1 The facial recognition system has not been trained and tested on a great diversity of skin tones and facial features, leaving groups of people vulnerable to underrepresentation and bias.

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*2.21.2 The facial recognition system is deployed in a public space.

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*2.21.3 The facial recognition system processes data in real time.

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*2.22 The activities of the AI system entail emotion recognition

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*2.23 The activities of the AI system entail social credits/citizen scoring systems

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

Section 3. Human Agency and Oversight

What is your level of agreement with the following statements? (1 = Totally disagree, 6 = Totally agree)

*3.1 The AI system does not affect human autonomy by generating an excessive reliance on the system by end-users

📌 References: "How might the implementation of your AI system impact the abilities of affected stakeholders to make free, independent, and well-informed decisions about their lives? How might it enhance or diminish their autonomy?" [12] and "Could the AI system affect human autonomy by generating over-reliance by end-users?" [6]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*3.1.1 Procedures have been put in place as to avoid that end users will rely too much on the AI system

📌 Reference: "Did you put in place procedures to avoid that end-users over-rely on the AI system?" [6]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*3.2 The AI system does not influence nor limit human autonomy by interfering with the decisional process of end users

📌 Reference: "Could the AI system affect human autonomy by interfering with the end-user's decision-making process in any other unintended and undesirable way?" [6]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*3.2.1 Measures have been implemented as to prevent the AI system from involuntarily affecting human autonomy

📌 Adattata da: "Could the AI system affect human autonomy by interfering with the end-user's decision-making process in any other unintended and undesirable way?" [6]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*3.3 The AI system does not address nor influence the user in a direction desired by the organization (i.e., nudging)

Reference: "To what extent does the AI direct the user in a direction desired by the organisation (nudging)?" [5]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*3.4 End-users are not incentivized to follow the automated decisions

Reference: "Is there a strong incentive for people to follow the automated decisions?" [5]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*3.5 The AI system does not entail the risk of creating an overreliance by users, stimulating a behavior of dependence, or manipulating the end users' behavior

Reference: "Does the AI system risk creating human attachment, stimulating addictive behaviour, or manipulating user behaviour?" [6]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*3.5.1 In case end users developed a disproportionate attachment to the AI system, the system manipulated their behavior, or behaviors of dependence occurred, measures to avoid possible negative consequences have been considered and adopted.

Reference: "Did you take measures to deal with possible negative consequences for end-users or subjects in case they develop a disproportionate attachment to the AI system? Did you take measures to minimise the risk of addiction? Did you take measures to mitigate the risk of manipulation?" [6]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*3.6 The end user is informed on which data will be collected about them and which conclusions will be drawn from them

Adattata da: "Are end-users capable of determining which data of / about them are collected and which conclusions are drawn from them?" [5]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*3.6.1 When the end user is informed on the decisions that the AI systems will make, the index does not comprise limited options (non-exhaustive index) or options that may influence the judgments and choices of the end user themselves.

Reference: "When informing an individual about significant choices they will make, the AI system does not unreasonably restrict the available options or otherwise attempt to influence their value judgement without the explicit and informed consent of the individual in question?" [16]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*3.7 The end user has the capability of easily requesting explanations about the AI system

Reference: "Affected individuals are made aware of their ability to request explanations" [16]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*3.8 The end user is aware of the existing or potential risks of the use of the AI system

Reference: "Did you inform end-users and subjects of existing or potential risks?" [6]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*3.9 The end user has the capability of deleting the data and the conclusions drawn about them by the system either through clear instructions, or automatically by sunset clause

References: "Can the user delete his data from the system?" [5]; "Ease to deactivate/remove: either through clear instructions or automatically by sunset clause" [4]; "Is it made clear whether individuals have the option to withdraw their data and opt out from inferences being made about them? If yes, what is the withdrawal procedure?" [17]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*3.10 Some end users may have difficulty in using the system correctly and effectively

1 2 3 4 5 6

*3.11 Easily accessible help sections or tutorials have been included in the system

Reference: "Ensure that users are informed and capable of using the system correctly, including e.g. in-system help" [17]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*3.12 The AI system does not simulate human interaction with, or between, end users or subjects

Reference: "Does the AI system simulate social interaction with or between end-users or subjects?" [6]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*3.12.1 When the AI system persuasively mimics the behavior of a human being, it only does so after informing the user that it is an AI system

Reference: "If the system can convincingly impersonate a human being, it does so only after notifying the user that it is an AI system." [16]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*3.12.2 In case of interactive AI systems (e.g., chatbots), the subject clearly knows they are interacting with an AI system and not with a human being

Reference: "In cases of interactive AI systems (e.g., chatbots, robo-lawyers), do you communicate to users that they are interacting with an AI system instead of a human?" [6]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*3.13 People are not objectified or dehumanized by the use of the AI system

Reference: "Are people objectified and possibly dehumanized by the deployment of the system?" [5]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*3.14 The system is not implemented to substitute or integrate public services

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*3.14.1 It is possible to access those services also without using the AI systems

🔍 Riferimento: "In case of AI system aimed to replace or complement public services, full non system alternatives(2), partial(1), none(0)." [4]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*3.15 It is possible to take over the decision-making process of the AI system (human oversight)

🔍 Reference: "Can people take over the automated decision-making process?" [5]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*3.16 A 'stop button' is ensured, or a similar procedure to safely interrupt an operation when necessary

🔍 Riferimento: "Did you ensure a 'stop button' or procedure to safely abort an operation when needed?" [6]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*3.17 A functionality has been made available to ensure that, if necessary, the subject can influence the decision-making process of the AI system

🔍 Reference: "Is there a time when the individual can influence decision making by the AI? Should this functionality be made available?" [5]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*3.18 Human-in-the-Loop, Human-on-the-Loop, Human-in-Command or other equivalent oversight measures are built into the system

🔍 Reference: "What measures did you take to ensure that the system can be effectively controlled or overseen by humans?" and "Is it controlled or overseen by a Human-in-the-Loop, Human-on-the-Loop or Human-in-Command?" [8]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*3.19 The humans who oversee the system have been given specific training on how to exercise oversight

📌 Reference: "In particular, have the humans who oversee the system been given specific training on how to exercise oversight?" [8]

1 2 3 4 5 6

Section 4. Privacy and Data Protection

What is your level of agreement with the following statements? (1 = Totally disagree, 6 = Totally agree)

*4.1 The data collection process complies with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

1 2 3 4 5 6

*4.2 A data protection impact assessment (DPIA) was performed

1 2 3 4 5 6

*4.3 A Data Protection Officer (DPO) has been nominated, and they are involved in the phases of development, acquisition, or use of the AI system.

1 2 3 4 5 6

*4.4 Supervision mechanism for data processing have been established

1 2 3 4 5 6

*4.5 Mechanisms have been put in place to report privacy problems concerning the AI system

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*4.6 The AI system only collects and elaborates strictly necessary data

Reference: "Does the application only collect and process the data necessary for the application?" [5]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*4.7 Usage data are retained and stored

Reference: "Identify if usage data from service operations is retained and stored." [18]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*4.8 During the development of the AI system, a mechanism for implementing the right to withdraw consent, the right to object, and the right to be forgotten was considered

References: "Did you implement the right to withdraw consent, the right to object and the right to be forgotten into the development of the AI system?" [6] and "Can the user delete his data from the system?" [5]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*4.9 The implications for privacy and the protection of data collected, generated, or processed during the AI system lifecycle have been explored

Reference: "Did you consider the privacy and data protection implications of the data collected, generated or processed over the course of the AI system's life cycle?" [6]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*4.10 The AI system is aligned with appropriate standards (ISO, IEEE) or protocols adopted for the management and (daily) governance of data

Reference: "Did you align the AI system with relevant standards (e.g. ISO25, IEEE26) or widely adopted protocols for (daily) data management and governance?" [6]

1 2 3 4 5 6

Section 5. Technical Robustness and Safety

What is your level of agreement with the following statements? (1 = Totally disagree, 6 = Totally agree)

*5.1 Techniques, security processes and consolidated standards for data protection are implemented (e.g., cryptography, anonymization)

Reference: "Does the supplier deploy well-established techniques, security processes and standards to protect the data, for example encryption and anonymization, where appropriate and feasible?" [18]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*5.2 Measures have been put in place to guarantee that data (including tracking data) used to develop the AI system are always updated, high quality, complete and representative of the environment in which the system was implemented

Reference: "Did you put in place measures to ensure that the data (including training data) used to develop the AI system is up-to-date, of high quality, complete and representative of the environment the system will be deployed into?" [6]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*5.3 The possibility that the AI system may invalidate the data or the hypotheses on which it had been trained has been considered, and possible consequences have been evaluated

References: "Did you consider whether the AI system's operation can invalidate the data or assumptions it was trained on, and how this might lead to adversarial effects?" [3] and "Did you consider whether the system's operation can invalidate the data or assumptions it was trained on, and how this might lead to adverse effects?" [8]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*5.4 The AI system obtained cybersecurity certifications (e.g., the certification scheme created by the Cybersecurity Act in Europe), or it is in compliance with specific security standards

Reference: "Is the AI system certified for cybersecurity (e.g. the certification scheme created by Cybersecurity Act in Europe= or is it compliant with specific security standards?" [6]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*5.5 Potential types of attacks to which the AI system might be vulnerable have been identified

Reference: "Did you assess potential forms of attacks to which the AI system could be vulnerable?" [6]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*5.6 A plan has been adopted to verify the policies of robustness, integrity and security from the identified cyber-attacks

References: "Explain how robustness policies will be checked and the type of attacks considered." [18] and "Did you put measures in place to ensure the integrity, robustness and overall security of the AI system against potential attacks over its lifecycle?" [6]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*5.7 Malicious parties could achieve substantial financial gain by hacking the system system

Reference: "May malicious parties have especially strong motives to hack the system? Can they easily achieve substantial financial gain— including by means of blackmailing—or can a hacked system be used to achieve political goals (including expressing political opposition against the system)?" [13]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*5.8 Malicious parties could achieve political goals by hacking the system

Reference: "May malicious parties have especially strong motives to hack the system? Can they easily achieve substantial financial gain— including by means of blackmailing—or can a hacked system be used to achieve political goals (including expressing political opposition against the system)?" [13]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*5.9 Malicious parties may have other strong motives to hack the system

Reference: "May malicious parties have especially strong motives to hack the system? Can they easily achieve substantial financial gain— including by means of blackmailing—or can a hacked system be used to achieve political goals (including expressing political opposition against the system)?" [13]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*5.10 It is possible to explain how robustness is checked against adversarial attacks, even once the system has been integrated/implemented on a large scale

Reference: "Describe how the service checked for robustness against adversarial attacks, including once it is integrated/deployed at scale." [18]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*5.11 Processes have been put in place to continuously measure and evaluate risks

Reference: "Did you put in place a process to continuously measure and assess risks?" [6]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*5.12 The risk of a possible malicious or inappropriate use of the AI system has been evaluated

1 2 3 4 5 6

*5.13 The actions performed to maintain the accuracy of the AI system are monitored and documented

Reference: "Did you assess the risk of possible malicious use, misuse or inappropriate use of the AI system?" [6]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*5.14 It is possible to describe how AI systems will be monitored and checked to highlight potential manipulation (both internal and external)

Reference: "Does the supplier provide evidence that the AI system has been tested and that AI domain experts were involved in the development, testing and deployment?" [18]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*5.15 The AI system was developed, tested, and implemented by experts in the domain of Artificial Intelligence

Reference: "Does the supplier provide evidence that the AI system has been tested and that AI domain experts were involved in the development, testing and deployment?" [18]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*5.16 Input-output checks have been performed to safeguard the accuracy and completeness of data processing

Reference: "Which input-output checks have been performed to safeguard the accuracy and completeness of data processing?" [14]

1 2 3 4 5 6

Section 6. Transparency

What is your level of agreement with the following statements? (1 = Totally disagree, 6 = Totally agree)

*6.1 The source code is open source or available upon request

Reference: "Source code is available, either freely or upon request (for non-sensitive applications)." [16]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*6.2 Affected stakeholders can gain access to the types of algorithms used

Reference: "Affected individuals are able to access the types of algorithms employed." [16]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*6.3 Considering efficiency and accuracy, the simplest and most intelligible system was chosen

Reference: "Taking into account efficiency and accuracy, has the simplest and most intelligible model been used?" [11]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*6.4 The logic of the AI decision-making process is clear and publicly available

Reference: "Is the functioning of the AI (the logic decision making) clear/public?" [5]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*6.5 In the instance of an AI system suggesting or making an erroneous decision, the error can be diagnosed by tracing back to the key factors that led to the conclusion

References: "It is possible to retrospectively walk through the 'decision journey' of a specific decision so as to diagnose the point at which it went wrong." [16], "Can you trace back which AI model or rules led to the decision(s) or recommendation(s) of the AI system?" [6] and "In the case that the AI system suggests or makes a wrong decision, is it possible to trace the key factors leading to any specific decision and diagnose the error?" [16]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*6.6 Measures dealing with the traceability of the AI system throughout its whole lifecycle have been implemented

Reference: "Did you put in place measures that address the traceability of the AI system during its entire lifecycle?" [6]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*6.7 The documentation relative to the development and support of the AI system was considered (e.g. reports, registers, quality criteria)

Reference: "Is the supplier able to provide documentation related to the development and support of the AI system, for example test, reports, logs and quality criteria?" [18]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*6.8 It is possible to make the used datasets public

🔍 References: "Can the used datasets be made public?" [5] and "AI operator organisations could consider providing affected AI subjects with a high level explanation of how their AI system works" [16]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*6.9 It is possible to make the sources of used data public

🔍 Reference: "Can the sources of used data be made public?" [5]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*6.10 The documentation relative to training data, methods of collection, data processing and the measures adopted to maintain the continuous accuracy of data, has been stored

🔍 References: "Is the data's origin documented?" [11], "Documentation is kept about the provenance of the training data, the methods of collection and treatment, how the data was moved and the measures taken to maintain its accuracy over time" [16] and "Can the supplier provide access to all the AI-model(s) training data and, when this is not feasible, to explain the process for providing a representative sample?" [18]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*6.11 The training data resemble the context of use

🔍 Reference: "Does training data resemble the context of use?" [3]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*6.12 Access is provided to all the input data of the AI model, included third-party data and open-source data, as well as the mechanisms for controlling the flow of data

🔍 Reference: "Does the supplier provide access to the AI model(s) input data, including third party or open source data including mechanisms for controlling the flow of data?" [18]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*6.13 It is possible to trace back to which data was used by the AI system to make one or more decisions

🔗 Reference: "Are the training data set's characteristics documented and disclosed? Are the corresponding data sheets comprehensive?" [11] and "Can you trace back which data was used by the AI system to make a certain decision(s) or recommendation(s)?" [6]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*6.14 Specific measures have been implemented to continuously assess the quality of input data

🔗 Reference: "Did you put in place measures to continuously assess the quality of the input data to the AI system?" [6]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*6.15 The advantages of the use of AI systems are explained to the affected subjects

🔗 Reference: "Did you communicate the benefits of the AI system to users?" [6]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*6.16 The consequences of the use of the AI system are explained to the affected subjects

🔗 Reference: "Is it clear to end users (and other relevant actors) what are the consequences of decision making by the AI?" [5]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*6.17 The rationale behind the decision on which data are used by the system, and on whom it will draw its conclusions, are explained

🔗 Reference: "Can the supplier articulate how it was decided which data to use or about whom to make inferences?" [18]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*6.18 The subject is informed that the decisions made about them are the result of a decision taken by the AI system

Reference: "Users are informed when a significant decision about them was made or assisted by AI." [16]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*6.19 The subject is notified that their data is being gathered and how inferences are made about them

Reference: "Is it clear that data subjects know their data is being used or that inferences are being made about them?" [18]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*6.19.1 The procedures through which the subject is informed on the gathering of their personal data, the kind of consent that is required on their behalf, and the procedures of consent collection, are explained

Reference: "Does the supplier provide information on what individuals were told, when they were made aware, what kind of consent was needed from them and what the procedures for gathering consent were?" [17]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*6.20 It is possible to explain the functioning of the AI system to the affected subjects (high-level explanation)

References: "Is the operating principle comprehensible and interpretable?" [11], "To which extent can the operation of the application/the algorithm be explained to end users and those involved?" [5] and "A high-level summary of the system's working is provided in clear, non-technical language in an easily accessible location" [16]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*6.21 The affected subject can receive clear directions and explanations on how the results provided by the AI system should be interpreted

Reference: "Affected individuals are able to access the most important factors driving the outcome of decisions" [18]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*6.22 During the whole process, it is explained how the rights of those who provided their data were safeguarded

Reference: "Does the supplier describe how the rights of individuals who provided the data were safeguarded throughout the process?" [18]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*6.23 Affected persons are periodically surveyed to assess whether they understand the system decisions

Reference: "Do you continuously survey the persons concerned to determine whether they understand the decision(s) of the system?" [8]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*6.24 Efforts have been made to ensure developers, deployers, end-users and the public have realistic expectations about the capabilities and limitations of AI systems

Reference: "Communicate, in a clear and proactive manner, information to stakeholders about the AI system's capabilities and limitations, enabling realistic expectation setting, and about the manner in which the requirements are implemented" [6]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*6.25 If multiple parties are involved in the development/use/maintenance of the algorithm, the parties and their roles can be made explicit

Reference: "If multiple parties are involved in the development/use/maintenance of the algorithm: can the parties and their roles be rendered explicit?" [15]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*6.26 Measures have been put in place to ensure the system's reproducibility

Reference: "Did you put in place measures to evaluate and ensure the system's reliability and reproducibility?" [8]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*6.27 Third parties such as suppliers, persons concerned, vendors, civil society organisations, can report potential vulnerabilities, risks or biases to the system via a specific process to be addressed and re-dressed

Reference: "Have you considered introducing benchmarking procedures to compare the performance and risks of the system's output with human-made decisions in the same areas?" [8]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

Section 7. Diversity, Non-Discrimination and Fairness

What is your level of agreement with the following statements? (1 = Totally disagree, 6 = Totally agree)

*7.1 There are specific groups that are favored or put at a disadvantage in the context in which the AI system is used

References: "How might the implementation of your AI system adversely affect each stakeholder's fair and equal treatment under the law? Are there any aspects of the project that expose vulnerable communities to possible discriminatory harm?" [12] and "Are there specific groups that are favoured or disadvantaged in the context where the AI application is used?" [5]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*7.2 It has been taken into consideration that biases may emerge when several groups are subject to several decision-making processes

Reference: "Consideration has been given to biases that might arise when different groups are subjected to different decision-making processes." [16]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*7.3 Mitigating measures have been adopted to guarantee that individuals in similar circumstances receive similar treatments

Reference: "Mitigating measures have been pursued to ensure individuals in the same circumstances receive equal treatment." [16]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*7.4 In collecting data, the diversity and representativity of stakeholders has been considered

Reference: "Where relevant, did you consider diversity and representativeness of end-users and or subjects in the data?" [5]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*7.5 Measures have been implemented as to avoid that the system is trained with inaccurate data (e.g., omitted or not up to date)

Reference: "Decision has been made to refrain from training the AI system on inaccurate data, whether that be due to age, omission, method of collection or other factor." [16]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*7.6 The potential discrimination impact has been assessed

Reference: "Assessments on potential discrimination impact has been conducted." [16]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*7.7 Efforts have been made to consult, during the development process, people coming from demographic contexts appropriate to the context of use

Reference: "Efforts have been made to consult, during the development process, people from appropriate demographic backgrounds." [16]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*7.8 Efforts have been made to consult, during the development process, people coming from a diverse demographic background, including disadvantaged and underrepresented groups

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*7.9 Tests have been performed for specific, vulnerable target groups or problematic use cases

Reference: "Did you test for specific target groups or problematic use cases?" [8]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*7.10 A comparative assessment has been made among public values that may conflict as a result of using the algorithm.

Reference: "If public values conflict as a result of using the algorithm, a comparative assessment must be made between them and a balancing exercise may need to be conducted" [15]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*7.11 It is possible to describe how employees are trained in understanding and accepting that all individuals have unconscious prejudices, and that they are responsible of guaranteeing that these biases do not affect the functioning of the AI system

Reference: "Can the supplier describe how they educate their staff to understand and accept that individuals have unconscious bias and understand their responsibility in ensuring it doesn't affect the operation of the AI system?" [18]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*7.12 It is possible to describe if and where there are missing or low-quality data, identifying potential risks and finding solutions

References: "Can the supplier describe where they have missing or poor quality data?" [18] and "Are they able to identify potential risks of missing or poor data and can they articulate how they are mitigating these risks?" [18]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*7.13 A strategy (or a series of procedures) was established to avoid the creation or reinforcement of unfair biases in the AI system, both for what concerns the use of input data and for the algorithm design

Reference: "Did you establish a strategy or a set of procedures to avoid creating or reinforcing unfair bias in the AI system, both regarding the use of input data as well as for the algorithm design?" [3]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*7.14 The user interface of the AI system is usable by people with special needs or disability, or by people at risk of exclusion

References: "Did you assess whether the AI system's user interface is usable by those with special needs or disabilities or those at risk of exclusion?" [6] and "Accessibility: possibility to be used by all regardless of demographics, language, disability, digital literacy and financial accessibility. All these requirements should be fulfilled, whereas addressing them only partially or not at all are not adequate." [4]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*7.15 The information and user interface of the AI system are accessible and usable also by the users of assistive technology (e.g., screen readers)

Reference: "Did you ensure that information about the AI system, and the AI system's user interface, is accessible and usable also to users of assistive technologies (such as screen readers)?" [6]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*7.16 End-users that use assistive technologies have been involved and consulted during the phase of design and development of the AI system

References: "Did you involve or consult with end-users or subjects in need of assistive technology during the planning and development phase of the AI system?" [6] and "Did you involve or consult with persons concerned in need of assistive technology during the planning and development phase of the system?" [8]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*7.17 Universal Design principles and accessibility standards have been considered during every step of the planning and development process

Reference: "Did you ensure that Universal Design Principles and accessibility standards are considered during every step of the planning and development process, if applicable?" [8]

Universal Design Principles: www.cen.eu/news/brief-news/Pages/NEWS-2019-014.aspx

1 2 3 4 5 6

*7.18 Does the AI system make decisions whose outcomes are punitive (e.g., incarceration)?

1 2 3 4 5 6

*7.18.1 Has the dataset been assessed for a false positive parity across groups? Are the results satisfactory?

Reference: "False positive parity: Desirable when your interventions are punitive" [17]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*7.19 Does the AI system make decisions whose outcomes are assistive (e.g., granting benefits)?

1 2 3 4 5 6

*7.19.1 Has the dataset been assessed for a false negative parity across groups? Are the results satisfactory?

Reference: "False negative parity: Desirable when your interventions are assistive/preventative" [17]

1 2 3 4 5 6

Section 8. Societal and Environmental well-being

What is your level of agreement with the following statements? (1 = Totally disagree, 6 = Totally agree)

*8.1 The negative impacts that the AI system can have on the environment have been accounted for

Reference: "Are the potential negative impacts of the AI system on the environment?" [6]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*8.1.1 Mechanisms have been established as to evaluate the environmental impact during the development, deployment, and use of the AI system (e.g., the quantity of energy used and the corresponding carbon emissions)

Reference: "Where possible, did you establish mechanisms to evaluate the environmental impact of the AI system's development, deployment and/or use (for example, the amount of energy used and carbon emissions)?" [6]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*8.1.2 Measures have been defined to lower the environmental impact of the AI system throughout its lifecycle

Reference: "Did you define measures to reduce the environmental impact of the AI system throughout its lifecycle?" [6]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*8.2 Affected subjects were adequately informed and consulted before the AI system was implemented

Reference: "Did you ensure that workers understand how the AI system operates, which capabilities it does or doesn't have?" [6]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*8.3 Tutorials or Help sections were provided to make sure that stakeholders are capable of correctly using the system

Reference: "Ensure that users are informed and capable of using the system correctly, including e.g. in-system help, or external material e.g. website. Absence is not adequate" [4]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*8.4 The AI system does not entail a risk of labor force deskilling

Reference: "Could the AI system create the risk of de-skilling of the workforce?" [3]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*8.4.1 Measures have been implemented to counteract the risk of labor force deskilling

References: "Did you take measures to counteract the de-skilling risks?" [6] and "Could the system create the risk of de-skilling your staff? Did you take measures to counteract de-skilling risks?" [8]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*8.4.2 Training courses and learning materials were provided to enhance the skills of employees

References: "Did you provide training opportunities and materials for re- and up-skilling?" [6] and "Does the system promote or require new (digital) skills? Did you provide training opportunities and materials for re- and upskilling?" [8]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*8.5 Mechanisms were established to evaluate the social impact of the use of the AI system (e.g., on indirectly affected sectors of society)

Reference: "Did you assess the societal impact of the AI system's use beyond the end-user and subject, such as potentially indirectly affected stakeholders or the society at large?" [6]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*8.6 Measures have been defined to guarantee that the AI system does not have a negative impact on democracy

Reference: "Did you take measures to ensure that the AI system does no negatively impact democracy?" [6]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*8.7 Measures have been defined to guarantee that the AI system does not have a negative impact on the life of future generations

Reference: "How might it affect their capacities to flourish and to fully develop themselves?" [12]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*8.8 Decisions made by this system do not have an impact on the affected party's livelihood (loss of opportunities, loss of benefits)

1 2 3 4 5 6

*8.9 Decisions made by this system do not have an impact on the affected party's freedom (incarceration, surveillance)

1 2 3 4 5 6

*8.10 The person about whom a decision is taken by the AI system can prove the wrongness of the decision without going to court

Reference: "Can the person about whom a decision is taken with the help of the relevant tool prove the wrongness of the decision without going to court?" [13]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*8.11 The harm of a wrong decision is fully reversible

Reference: "Is the harm of a wrong decision fully reversible?" [13]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*8.12 It is possible to compensate the individual or family fully and adequately for the harm of a wrong decision

Reference: "Is it possible to compensate the individual or family fully and adequately for the harm of a wrong decision, when it is ascertained that the decision was wrong and cannot be reversed?" [13]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

Section 9. Accountability

What is your level of agreement with the following statements? (1 = Totally disagree, 6 = Totally agree)

*9.1 Potential losses and damages due to erroneous decisions, misuse or malfunctioning of the AI system have been taken into consideration

Reference: "The potential loss, harm and damage resulting from incorrect decisions, misdeployment or malfunction of the AI system has been assessed." [16]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*9.1.1 There is an employee responsible for investigating, dealing with, and redressing eventual losses and damages

Reference: "Who is responsible for investigating, addressing and (where appropriate) rectifying any loss, harm or damage that occurs?" [16]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*9.2 The impact of possible erroneous decisions made by the AI system has been evaluated

Reference: "The impact of incorrect decisions informed by AI systems has been assessed." [16]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*9.2.1 There are employees responsible for evaluating the impact of the AI system (including social impact)

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*9.2.2 Employees responsible for evaluating the impact of the AI system have developed control plans

Reference: "Employees responsible for impact (including social impact) of the AI system have been identified and they have developed relevant control plans." [16]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*9.3 The continuous accuracy of the input data is guaranteed through time (including the completeness and the timely updating of data)

Reference: "Plans are in place to ensure the continuing accuracy of the input data over time, including the completeness of the data and the timely update of the data." [16]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

*9.3.1 The parameters of the AI systems are periodically optimized to ensure that the system remains accurate and fair

Reference: "Parameters of the AI system are periodically tuned to ensure the system remains accurate and fair" [16]

- 1 2 3 4 5 6

* 9.3.2 The developer and the service provider cooperate to maintain the continuous accuracy of the system

Reference: "Developer and vendor plan to cooperate to maintain the continuous accuracy of the system." [16]

1 2 3 4 5 6

* 9.3.3 There is an employee responsible for ensuring the continuing accuracy of the system

Reference: "Whose responsibility is it to maintain the continuing accuracy of the system (e.g. parameter tuning)?" [16]

1 2 3 4 5 6

* 9.4 A designated person will examine the equity and continuous adequacy of the system, in case of a high number of complaints by affected subjects

Reference: "Under what circumstances (e.g. a critical number of complaints) will the operator review the fairness and continued appropriateness of the system?" [16]

1 2 3 4 5 6

* 9.5 The AI system can undergo external audit

References: "Did you ensure that the AI system can be audited by independent third parties?" [6], "Are mechanisms in place to provide access to data/processes for third-party evaluation?" [11] and "The system is subject to external audit" [16]

1 2 3 4 5 6

* 9.5.1 There is an employee responsible for coordinating the external auditing procedure

Reference: "There is a person internally responsible for coordinating the external auditing procedure" [16]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*9.5.2 An external guide, or a third-party auditing process, have been foreseen to supervise ethical issues and accountability measures

Reference: "Did you foresee any kind of external guidance or third-party auditing processes to oversee ethical concerns and accountability measures?" [6]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*9.6 A training was organized to inform subjects on the risks of the AI system and on the potential judicial framework of reference

Reference: "Did you organise risk training and, if so, does this also inform about the potential legal framework applicable to the AI system?" [6]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*9.7 An authority was instituted to solve and regulate eventual conflict tied to the transparency of the AI system

Riferimento: "Has a mediating authority been established to settle and regulate transparency conflicts?" [9]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*9.8 The creation of an Ethics review committee, where to discuss general responsibility and ethical practices, has been considered

Reference: "Did you consider establishing an AI ethics review board or a similar mechanism to discuss the overall accountability and ethic practices, including potential unclear grey areas?" [3]

1 2 3 4 5 6

*9.9 Affected subjects can challenge any decision made about them by the AI system

Reference: "Channels are provided whereby affected individuals can challenge a specific decision concerning them" [16]

1 2 3 4 5 6

* 9.9.1 The procedure to challenge decisions is clear and easy to initiate

? References: "The challenge procedures are clear and easy to follow" [2] and "Is there any mechanism for redress if individuals are negatively affected?" [18]

1 2 3 4 5 6

* 9.9.2 There is a person responsible for guaranteeing that disputes are followed and regularly updated

? Reference: "There is a person responsible for ensuring the procedures are followed and regularly updated" [16]

1 2 3 4 5 6

* 9.10 Affected subjects can opt out from automated decisions made about them by the AI system

? Reference: "Affected individuals are able to opt out of decisions that are entirely automated" [16]

1 2 3 4 5 6

* 9.10.1 The procedure to opt out from decisions is clear and easy to implement

? Reference: "Affected individuals are made aware of their ability to opt out and the process for doing so is not difficult" [16]

1 2 3 4 5 6

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Results

Thank you!

Your survey responses have been recorded.

Your assessment

Based on your answers, the result of the **risk evaluation** of the AI system is: **MEDIUM RISK**.

Based on your answers, the result of the impact evaluation of the AI system in the domain of **Human Intervention and Oversight** is: **HIGH IMPACT**.

- **Human Intervention and Oversight**

AI systems should not limit **individual autonomy and decision-making processes**. End users should be capable of making autonomous and informed decisions concerning AI systems. It is also necessary to provide adequate tools and information to users as to assist them in understanding and interacting with these systems, so that they could challenge the system if errors were to occur. AI systems should act in the interest of a prosperous, democratic and equal society, supporting user intervention and promoting **fundamental rights**. AI systems should also allow for **human oversight** and allow users to decide when and how to use the system in any given circumstance.

Based on your answers, the impact evaluation of the AI system in the domain of **Privacy and Data Protection** is: **MEDIUM IMPACT**.

- **Privacy and Data Protection**

AI systems can collect, process and infer data. As a result, the impact of these technologies on the right to privacy and personal data protection must be considered. Data collection must adhere to the **General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)**. Mechanisms for monitoring data processing and notifying of privacy threats should be implemented.

Based on your answers, the result of the impact evaluation of the AI system in the domain of **Technical Robustness and Safety** is: **LOW IMPACT**.

- **Technical Robustness and Safety**

AI systems must be effectively safeguarded against vulnerabilities that might expose them to malicious cyber attacks. These systems should have safeguards that activate an emergency plan in case of problems (e.g., allowing human intervention). Processes for clarifying and evaluating possible risks related with the deployment of AI systems in various sectors of application should be put in place. If potential risks are particularly high, it is necessary to proactively develop and test security measures.

AI systems should be accurate, resulting in a correct output: an explicit and well-structured development and evaluation process may support, mitigate and correct the unintended risk deriving from imprecise predictions. When imprecisions are unavoidable, the systems must be capable of identifying the probability of error.

AI systems must be reliable, exhibiting the same behavior under equal conditions.

Based on your answers, the result of the impact evaluation of the AI system in the domain of **Transparency** is: **LOW IMPACT**.

- **Transparency**

Datasets, decision-making processes (including those of data collection and data labelling) and the algorithms used must be well documented to allow for **traceability** and enhancing transparency. Decisions made by the systems should be documented, too: this would aid in understanding why an AI system has made an incorrect decision, helping in preventing future errors. Training data should reflect the context of use, and measures should be in place to continuously evaluate the quality of input data. The affected subject must have the capability of receiving **explanations** on the benefits of the use of the system, on the decisions that will be made about them, on which data will be used, and on the functioning of the system itself.

Based on your answers, the result of the impact evaluation of the AI system in the domain of **Diversity, Non-discrimination and Fairness** is: **HIGH IMPACT**.

- **Diversity, Non-discrimination and Fairness**

AI systems may lead to unfair results for some individuals. A reliable AI system must be developed by considering and including stakeholders during the whole development process. **Equality of treatment and access** should be ensured to all stakeholders without discrimination based on gender, race, age, disability, language, income, etc. The fairness of datasets used by AI systems may be affected by unintentional historical distortions, incompleteness and poor governance models. Identifiable discriminating distortions must be removed already from phase of data collection. The process of development of an AI system can, too, be affected by unequal distortions: to avoid them, it can be useful to activate oversight processes that analyze and clearly deal with the purposes, constraints and decisions made by the system. Moreover, the systems should be user-centered: it is necessary to ensure everyone has the opportunity to utilize AI goods or services, keeping in mind the issue of the **accessibility** of these technologies for people with disabilities.

Based on your answers, the result of the impact evaluation of the AI system in the domain of **Social and Environmental Wellbeing** is: **MEDIUM IMPACT**.

- **Social and Environmental Wellbeing**

AI systems should be used for the benefit of all human beings, including future generations. Given their promise to tackle urgent environmental issues (e.g., climate change), AI systems must function in a way that is as **environmentally mindful**. The development, deployment and use of the system, as well as the entire supply chain, should be evaluated in relation to their environmental sustainability (e.g., through a critical exam of the energy and resource consumption during development). AI systems can also radically alter the work sphere, as they can contribute both to **enhancing social skills** and to **impairing them**. This can affect in an equal measure the physical and psychological wellbeing of people. The effects of AI systems must therefore be attentively monitored.

Based on your answers, the result of the impact evaluation of the AI system in the domain of **Accountability** is: **LOW IMPACT**.

- **Accountability**

It is necessary to put in place mechanisms that ensure the accountability of AI systems and their results, both before and after they are enacted. It should always be possible to verify algorithms, data and development processes (this, however, does not mean making available business models and intellectual property relative to the AI system). AI systems should undergo both internal and external audit, especially for applications that affect fundamental rights. It is necessary to guarantee the possibility of reporting on actions or decisions that contribute to a given output of the system, as well as the possibility of responding to the consequences of such output. Identifying, evaluating, report on, and minimize the potential adverse effects of AI systems is particularly important to those who are directly or indirectly affected. It is also necessary to put in place accessible and adequate redress mechanisms in case of unfair negative impacts.

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